

A MORPHOLOGY OF EDO

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ABSTRACT

Previous studies have only paid attention to the syntax and phonology to the detriment of the internal structures of words in the Edo language. This study, therefore, examined the morphological structures and processes in Edo such as nominalization, compounding, reduplication, affixation, clipping, number formation and ideophones. The structures of Edo personal names and the roles of tones in the morphological processes in the language were also investigated. The study also appraised the Yorùbá loanwords in Edo based on philological facts, which appear to link Ifè-Benin.

Data were collected from six native speakers (both monolinguals and bilinguals) in Benin City, Ilé-Ifè and Lagos. Ibàdàn-400 wordlist was utilized as a tool for collecting data. Additional 400 varied morphological patterns and 600 randomly selected words were collected from the six informants through audio recording. The data collected were analyzed using the theory of autosegmental phonology and morphology, a geometric approach to the analysis of language that states that the phonetic representation be composed of a set of several simultaneous sequences of these segments, with certain elementary constraints on how the various levels of sequences can be interrelated. This theory was adopted because it is capable of solving the various issues encountered in the data, taking into account insights from related studies

The work discovered the significant roles of tones in the morphology of Edo language as nominalization and reduplication constructions were categorized on the bases of the tones they bear. The study further shed lights on the discourse on the status of Odúduwà and Órànmiyàn in Ifè-Benin relations. The study on compounding revealed that Edo constitutes an exception to Williams' Right-Hand Head Rule since Edo is a head-first language. While other processes such as affixation and number formations have not negated the established facts, the study proved that tones in Edo ideophones do not have any semantic connotation as it is the case with related languages. It also showed that clipping can be from any part of the name as against what was earleir reported. The study

established that although Edo names have common core domains of terminology with other classes of noun as a lexical category, they exhibit some distinct morpho-syntactic and lexico-semantic idiosyncrasies, such as their behaviour with modifiers and qualifiers. Finally, the work showed clearly that Edo names are abridged versions of syntactic structures, which lexicalize the people's folk-psychology and their language morphological structures as previously observed by Yorùbá scholars.

The study revealed that the morphology of Edo language is distinctive because of the unique roles that tones play in the various nominal constructions we examined. It also showed that, through the study of the relationships of Yorùbá and Edo words, we can clearly and intuitively comprehend the history of these people. The results, through corpus of data from Yorùbá loanwords in Edo, tend to suggest that both the Yorùbá and Edo people have common progenitor. The study therefore broadened the discourse of morphology and its philological importance, not only in Edoid languages but also in African linguistic studies.

Keywords: Edo, Morphology, Autosegmental, Lexicalist, Tones.

Word count: 499

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by Mr. Harrison 'Rótími Adéniyi in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibádán.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND NOTATIONS

The following abbreviations and notations were used in this work:

PMH	Prosodic Morphology Hypothesis
σ	Syllable
μ	Mora
PrWd	Prosodic Word
WFR	Word Formation Rule
BSC	Basic Syllable Composition
SPE	Sound Pattern of English
SLH	Strong Lexicalist Hypothesis
WLH	Weak Lexicalist Hypothesis
MSR	Morphosyntactic Representation
UBH	Unitary Base Hypothesis
Pro.	Pronoun
N	Noun
V	Verb
H	High tone
L	Low tone
↓	Downstep
Nom. Pre.	Nominalizing prefix
PE	Proto Edo
#	Morpheme boundary or word boundary
∅	Null or zero
FHT	Floating High Tone
→	Write as or sum total of
⊙ H	Floating High tone
⊙ L	Floating Low tone

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Edo Language and its People

According to the 1991 Nigeria census, about 2¼ million people, occupying about 10,372 square kilometers speak Edo. It is located in the mid-western part of Nigeria. The area lies between latitude 6° 12' and longitude 5° 45'. Elugbe (1989) classified Edo as one of the languages that constitute the North-Central Edoid group. The Edoid group is in turn a branch of (New) Benue-Congo (Williamson 1989). Edo-speaking area is bounded by Ondo State in the West. On the south by the Urhobo of Warri, Ethiope and Ugheli areas and to the Western side by the Okpe, Ika and Ndokwa Local Government Areas of Delta State of Nigeria. This language is spoken in predominantly seven out of the fourteen Local Government Areas that constitute Edo State. These are Oredo, Orhionmowon, Uhumwode, Ikpoba Okha, Ovia North-East, Ovia South-West and Egor Local Government. Some of the towns where Edo is spoken include Benin-City, Oluku, Abudu, Okada, Igieduma and Ehor. There is a little controversy as to whether Edo is spoken outside Edo state. Agheyisi (1986) pointed out that 'there is believed to be other communities of Edo native speakers in the Okitipupa Division of Ondo Province, as well as in and around Akure in Ondo State. Also, Imasuen (1980) noted that '... some Edo speakers are in parts of Ondo State in such areas as Okenuhen, Akotogbo and Idoani'. There may be no justification for the above claims that Edo is spoken in some parts of Ondo State. Linguists like Adetugbo (1976), Akinkugbe (1976, 1978), Oyelaran (1976), Olumuyiwa (1994), Awobuluyi (1998) and Adeniyi (2005) in their discussions of dialects and languages of Ondo State as part of their work did not mention that Edo is spoken in some part of Ondo State. Elugbe (1989:13) referred to Oke (1970) who identified additional communities such as Akotogbo, Gbelebon, and Iju-Osun in Okitipupa areas of Ondo State as western Edoid people in Ondo state. Iyayu (an Edoid language spoken in Idoani) is part of the languages mentioned by him.

Both Imasuen (1980) and Agheyisi (1986) in their classifications and analyses may have confused Edo language with Edoid languages. This writer is familiar with

Ídoàní town (in Ondo State) where there are five communities with one of them speaking Iyayu (an Edoid language)

Aghyeyisi observed that the Edo language is generally homogenous, characterized by the absence of dialect variation, due to the highly centralized nature of the socio-political structure of the ancient Benin kingdom. This is disputable; notable peculiarities do exist in the speech of the inhabitants of the peripheral communities.

Over the years, there have been a lot of ambiguities in the use of the term 'Edo'. While to some, it stands for a single language and the indigenous name of the ancient city. To others, it is the name of a group of genetically related languages. However, Elugbe (1989) later named this group of genetically related languages 'Edoid languages' thereby freeing the name Edo for the single language.

1.2 Previous Works on Edo

Studies on Edo have not been very extensive until lately and most of them had to do with the grammar of the language.

Melzian (1937) wrote a dictionary titled *A Concise Dictionary of the Bini Language of Southern Nigeria*. This, according to Amayo (1976), is the first systematic study of the language. The transcription of items in the work is very accurate and there are also very useful grammatical notes in the dictionary. The introduction of the work also contains a very detailed description of the sound system including the tonal structure of the language. In 1942, Melzian's book – *Vergleichende Charakterized Verbuns in Bini* was published. This work was a great improvement on his earlier work. According to Amayo (1976) '...by the time of writing this book, Melzian has got what can be considered a very accurate picture (especially considering the time at which he wrote) of the structure of the language.

Wescott's three volumes of Benin Grammar was published between 1962 and 1963. Wescott devoted part of the grammar to the phonology of the language. He did not, however, model the grammar after any particular theory.

Elugbe's (1973) Ph.D thesis – *A Comparative Edo Phonology* had a brief discussion on the phonology of Edo. This is because his work discussed about 11 languages. However, Elugbe made a major contribution to the study of Edo phonology in

his analysis of the tone system. He analysed Edo as having a terraced level system with two tones plus downstep (cf. Amayo 1976:45).

Amayo's (1976) Ph.D thesis – *A Generative Phonology of Edo (Bini)* contains a comprehensive discussion on the phonology of Edo (Bini) within the framework of Generative Phonology. In his work, issues such as general phonological processes, which operate in the language, the structure of the sentence constituents and grammatically conditioned phonological processes were discussed. Amayo analyzed the language as having two basic tones, high and low each of which has a downstepped variant arising from the deletion of a preceding low tone.

Agheyisi (1986) published *An Edo-English Dictionary* that has about 4,000 lexical items that were entered both orthographically and phonetically with tones. The dictionary also provides both phonological and grammatical information for each of the entries in anticipation of the specialized needs of language researchers and others interested in the linguistic information on Edo.

Adeniyi's (2003) M.Phil dissertation – *Tone and the Noun-Phrase in Edo* contains a discussion on the interface between tone and Noun-phrase (between phonology and syntax) in Edo. The work observes that tonal behaviour in the Noun phrase is a function of construction types and not of any other independent consideration relating to lexical tone patterns or syntactic structures. Using the autosegmental phonology, the work explored various options for analyzing the morphotonemic alternations and other tonal changes observed in the language. Some of these options include polarization, postulating tonal melodies and tonal morphemes, developing floating tones and establishing specific changes defined in terms of identical morphological and grammatical environments.

In all, the work was able to account for the various tonal behaviours in a principled way. Hitherto, this had posed a challenge to linguists.

Omoriegbe's (2005) *Edo Names for Cultural Studies* has about 3,555 Edo personal names. These names are carefully arranged alphabetically with meaning provided for each of them. These personal names are categorized under the following: ancient, dynasties, ancestral, deities, royal setting, colonial, modern, philosophical, idiomatic and divine deity. In all, this collection of names provides the readers with detailed meanings of the personal names in Edo.

1.3 Aims and objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to describe, in detail some aspects of the morphology of Edo. The theoretical framework employed in the analysis of this work is that of Autosegmental phonology and morphology.

In this work, we are concerned with various word formation processes, names and naming processes in Edo. Some of these processes include nominalization, compounding, reduplication and affixation. We also looked at number formation in Edo. We will also be concerned with ideophones, loan-words and personal name constructions in Edo language.

The aim of this study is, therefore, to contribute to linguistic theory while still making the work practically relevant to the language users. It is hoped that the result of the study will be useful, not only in the teaching and learning of Edo (both to native speakers and second language users) but also supplement the existing literature on Edoid linguistics.

We seek to establish facts about the morphology of the language using possible alternative analysis. Where necessary, we compare our study with related Edoid and non-Edoid languages.

1.4 The Data

The variety of Edo that is under focus in this study is called the standard one. Although the present writer is not a native speaker of Edo, we were able to maximally utilize all the linguistic knowledge at our disposal. Data were elicited from both monolingual and bilingual native speakers in Benin City, Ibàdàn, Ilé-Ifè and Lagos. Ibàdàn –400 word list was utilized as a tool for collecting the data. The present researcher also prepared additional 400 varied morphological patterns and 600 randomly selected words which were collected from the informants through audio recording. Secondary data sources consulted included Aghyeyisi (1986) *An Edo-English Dictionary*, Egharevba (1972) *Eleherhe Vbe han Edo* and Omoregie (2005) *Edo Names for Cultural Studies*.

CHAPTER TWO

PHONOLOGY

2.1 Introduction

Under this section, we give a brief account of both the consonant and vowel segments of the language. We will not go into detail because almost all writers on Edo phonology have dealt with them (cf Elugbe 1973:155, Amayo 1976:77 and Adeniyi 2003:08). Their various accounts of both vowels and consonant segments are adequate.

However, we will give a fairly detailed account of both the tones and the syllable structure of the language since the focus of this work is on the morphology of the language.

2.2 Edo Segments

Edo operates a twenty-three consonant phoneme system. Elugbe (1973:155), Amayo (1976:77) and Adeniyi (2003:8) attest to this. Elugbe went further to give the various environments where these consonants occur.

The consonant chart of Edo phonemes can be graphically given below:

p	b	t	d	g	kp̄	gb̄	
	m	[n]	r				
	f	v	s	z	x	ɣ	h
	l						
	l̄						
	l̄						
			y	w			

Figure 1

We will not go into the description of these individual consonants, as the descriptions of earlier writers are adequate.

Edo has seven oral vowels and they are all significant in the language. These are /i, e, o, ɔɔ, ɜɜ, a, u/. These oral vowels contrast minimally. The language also has five nasal vowels that contrast minimally. These are /ĩ, ě, ā, ɔ̃, ũ/. These vowels co-occur freely in the language.

2.3 Edo Tone System

Edo is a tone language. Tone plays significant roles in distinguishing between lexical items in the language. The following minimal pairs are distinguished only with the tones they have on them. These are:

1.
 - i. áká 'a hearth shelf'
 - ii. ákà 'a grass snake'
 - iii. áká 'trumpet'

2.
 - i. ɔɔkpá 'cock'
 - ii. ɔɔkpá 'one'
 - iii. ɔɔkpá 'staff'

Tone also plays a significant role in making a distinction between syntactic constructions

Some of these include:

3.
 - i. mà dɛ!wévá 'we bought two goats'
 - ii. mà dɛ!wévá 'we are buying two goats'

4.
 - i. Òsà débɔkpá 'Òsà is buying a book'
 - ii. Òsà débɔkpá 'Òsà bought a book'

Almost all works on Edo grammar touched the issue of tone. Some of these include Melzian (1973; 1942), Wescott (1963), Dunn (1968), Wolff (1959), Ogeriayi (1970),

Elugbe (1973, 1989), Amayo (1976) and Adényi (2003). One common denominator among these writers is the recognition of the presence of terracing in the tonal system of the language. However, they all differ in the number of the phonetic variants of these tones. It must also be noted that of all these writers mentioned above, only four gave useful insights into the tone system of the language. While Elugbe (1973, 1989) and Welmers (1973) were the first to give correct analyses of Edo tone as 'two tones plus downstep', Amayo (1976) was the first to reveal an interesting aspect that 'downstep applies not only to high tones but also to low tones. Adényi (2003) in his own account of Edo tones gave a vivid description of the various roles of tones in Noun-phrase constructions in the language.

In his Ph.D thesis titled *A Generative Phonology of Edo (Bini)*, Amayo (1976) said two basic tones, high and low can be identified in the language. He said further that these two basic tones have a number of variants. Some of his submissions as regards tone in Edo include:

- i. When two high tones are separated by one or more low tones, the second high tone is realized on a slightly lower pitch level than the first.
- ii. When two low tones are separated by one or more high tones, the low tone is realized on a slightly lowered pitch level than the first. The example he gave is:

5. ówásèlé $\left[\begin{array}{cc} \bar{\quad} & \bar{\quad} \\ \underline{\quad} & \underline{\quad} \end{array} \right]$ 'the leg of a cricket'

- iii. A sequence of low tones without an intervening high tone does also drift downward.
- iv. A sequence of high tones without an intervening low tone does not drift downward.

2.3.1 The High tone

The high tone is realized phonetically as a high tone in word initial positions or after another high tone in a high tone sequence as shown in examples below:

- 6 i. [á dá] / / 'sceptre'
- ii. [á wó] / / 'a large bird'

- | | | | | |
|------|-------|---|---|------------|
| iii. | [itā] | / | / | 'proverb' |
| iv. | [ówá] | / | / | 'epilepsy' |

Without a preceding low tone, the high tone maintains its level in a high tone sequence.

2.3.2 The Low Tone

The low tone is realized phonetically as a low tone in a word initial position. However, as Amayo (1976) rightly observed, there is the lowering of the low after another low tone. Let us consider the examples below.

- | | | | | | | |
|----|------|-----------|---|---|---|--------------------------------|
| 7. | i. | [èvé] | / | — | / | 'elephantiasis of the scrotum' |
| | ii. | [ètè] | / | — | / | 'sore, ulcer' |
| | iii. | [ókò] | / | — | / | 'parcel' |
| | iv. | [ùkpòkpò] | / | — | / | 'harassment' |

2.3.3 Downstep

Apart from the two level tones that we have in Edo, we also have downstep. Downstep is often used to refer to both the automatic downstep (downdrift) and the non-automatic downstep. While downdrift occurs when a low tone lowers the pitch of succeeding high and low tones, downstep refers to the lowering of high or low where no low tone is seen at the surface level. (cf. Amayo 1976:23)

This issue of downstep was first recognized over four decades ago by Winston (1960) when he said that downstep is not just a third (mid) tone in a three-tone system. He defined it as an intersyllabic feature, which occurs arbitrarily and normally, distinguishes or helps to distinguish some particular meanings or syntactic relationship or both (cf. Elugbe 1985, Egbokhare 1990). We must add under this section that tones are phonemic in Edo language. Yip (2002) mentioned the fact that we sometimes and erroneously too, think of morphemes only as segments, and that purely tonal morphemes abound. He went ahead to divide them into two based on where the tones surface in the word. Type one are those tonal morphemes that affix to the beginning or end of a word, and thus precede or, more commonly follow the tones of the root. Type two are tonal morphemes that overwrite the tones of the root, if any, replacing them entirely. It must

however, be noted that languages with morphemes of the second type are often analysed as having an underlying affix of the first type, and starts as a prefix or suffix, and that the larger surface manifestation of the tone can be derived from the general phonology. The two types of tonal morphemes can be found in the Edo language as would be seen later on in the work.

2.4 Syllable Structure

The awareness for units such as syllables (and other suprasegmentals) increased following the birth of autosegmental phonology. Prior to this, a formulation of the position of the syllable in phonemic process, its structure and relationship to other units in the phonological components proved intractable. Studies on the syllable (cf. Khan 1982; Clements and Keyser 1982 and Selkirk 1982) dealt more with the roles of the syllable in proper characterization of phonotactic constraints and suprasegmental phenomenon previously represented in an ad hoc way in terms of boundaries. Current researchers have shown clearly that proper analyses of such phenomena could best be carried out through the syllable.

According to Egbokhare (1990:164), Selkirk (1982) proposes a three template structure for the syllable. These are the syllable, CV and feature template. The syllable template (σ) is a binary branching node dominating an onset and a rhyme. The rhyme dominates a nucleus, which is the only obligatory part of a syllable, and a coda.

Following Egbokhare (1990), below is a schematic representation of the hierarchy.

Figure 2

Any tangible analysis of the syllable of any language must involve a specification of the universal and language specific 'Basic Syllable Composition' (BSC) and principle of re-syllabification (cf. Egbokhare 1990).

For syllable weight and sub-syllable structure, Steriade (1984) notes that linguistic rhythm phenomena, chiefly stress and meter (and for us tone), are frequently based on the distinction between LIGHT syllables (those that end in a short vowel) and HEAVY syllable (all others), making clear two facts beyond dispute which are central to the issue of representing syllable weight:

- a. Non-syllabic segments at the beginning of the syllable do not add to the weight of the syllable.
- b. Weight contrasts are in a vast majority of cases, not scalar, but rather on a strictly binary nature.

Hyman (1974:206) noted that a syllable core consists solely of a short vowel (V). This short vowel cannot be stressed, therefore the stress must be passed to a neighbouring syllable. Such syllable is said to be light. A syllable whose core consists of a long vowel VV or VC sequence or combinations of these can be stressed is said to be heavy.

The undermentioned universal conditions must be met before a syllable can be termed as well-formed.

- a. The onset and the coda must be filled by C – elements, while the nucleus must be a V – element.
- b. Each V must define a syllable. Thus, apart from the fact that there cannot be a syllable without a V, the number of syllables in a string coincides with the number of Vs in the string.

The number of C-elements in the coda and onset are decided specifically. Where there is more than one C- element, auxiliary node will specify the collocational restrictions on the combinations of C allowed.

2.4.1 The Syllable Structure in Edo

The template below specifies the gross features of the Basic Syllable Structure in Edo.

Figure 3

At the underlying level, Edo has a simple syllable structure with a non-branching onset and rhyme while some onsets are the optional result of vowel prefixes. Optional, in the sense that these prefixes may or may not be added, depending on the construction that is to be produced. Examples in (8) below are a few lexical items of the syllable types represented in figure (3).

- | | | | |
|----|----|---------|----------|
| 8. | a. | /i+yó/ | 'money' |
| | b. | /ó+kpé/ | 'flute' |
| | c. | /è-tó/ | 'hair' |
| | d. | /ó/ | 'use' |
| | e. | /rhòó/ | 'praise' |

Edo operates an open syllable system. All words end with vowels. (Even loanwords with consonant initials and final are made to conform with the syllable structure of the language). While majority of the verbs (which are monosyllabic) begin with consonants and end with vowels. There are no traces of syllabic nasals in the language. With this open syllable structure, the V-element is obligatory, while the onset is optional and the coda is consciously absent.

CHAPTER THREE

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.0 Introduction

An attempt will be made in this chapter to review all the theories that will be employed in this work. These are the autosegmental phonology and morphology that we employed in chapter four and the lexicalist hypothesis in chapter five. However, Unitary Base Hypothesis (henceforth UBH) was also used as supporting framework in chapter five.

The version of autosegmental theory employed in this work is fully discussed in the works of Goldsmith (1976a, b; 1979; 1990), Clements (1977), Clements and Ford (1979), Clements and Goldsmith (1982), Halle and Vergnaud (1982), Pulleyblank (1986), Hulst and Smith (1982), McCarthy (1979; 1981), McCarthy and Prince (1990).

What is presented in this chapter is, however an abridged version of both the autosegmental phonology and morphology, which draws abundantly from the works mentioned above. Other theories, would however, be employed in the course of the work, based on the demands of the data.

3.1 Autosegmental Theory

The theory of autosegmental phonology and morphology came up as a result of the inadequacies of the earlier theory propounded by Chomsky and Halle (1968) in their book, *The Sound Patterns of English* (SPE). They are of the view that phonetic representation is linear. They describe utterance as 'bundles of unordered features arranged in an ordered sequences. However, in reality, it was discovered that '... Ever since there have been segment in phonology, there have been phenomena that evaded segmental classification, and so there have been suprasegmental' (Goldsmith 1976b: 05). It is this fundamental shortcoming of SPE that gave birth to autosegmental phonology. This theory makes an attempt to provide adequate understanding of phonetic representation. The theory was proposed by Goldsmith (1976a: 120).

He asserts that:

Autosegmental phonology constitutes a particular claim, then, about the geometry of phonetic representations; it suggests that the phonetic representation be composed of a set of several simultaneous sequences of these segments, with certain elementary constraints on how the various levels of sequences can be interrelated.

He differs from Chomsky and Halle (1986) with the following proposals:

- i. Phonetic representation is multilinear or multitiered (Goldsmith 1976a);
- ii. Tiers are linked;
- iii. Feature specifications have an internal hierarchical structure (Steriade 1982; Clements 1985; Sagey 1986).
- iv. Some tiers may be morphemes (McCarthy 1979, 1981; Sagey 1986)

The model of standard generative phonology was unable to tackle some phonological phenomena in natural languages. One of this is that it sees segments as atomic elements which are linearly ordered, some of which bear suprasegmental properties, for example, tone, arranged in a neat sequence but the relationship between the segmental and suprasegmental levels is not given a serious consideration within this theory.

There are two different representations given by SPE. These are underlying and surface representations. There is a rule that converts the underlying representation to surface representation. These rules are capable of adding or deleting features. But the kernel of autosegmental phonology is that the underlying and surface forms consist of parallel strings of segments arranged in two or more tiers. Goldsmith (1976a) further affirms that:

...parallel sequences of segments, non of which 'depend' or 'ride on' the others. Each is independent in its own right, hence the name autosegmental level(p. 08)

Despite the fact that the tiers are independent, they still need to be connected to each other for one to obtain a well-formed phonological representation. This is done with the aid of association conventions, which we shall discuss later.

Apart from the inadequacies of the standard generative phonology discussed above, there are other phenomena in tonology that generative phonology cannot cater for, but which autosegmental phonology can fully resolve.

One of the classical problems of tonology which autosegmental phonology resolves is the representation of contour tones. In SPE, there is the problem of how to effectively explain and account for the situation where a single vowel segment could have two different tonal specifications; high and low tones or low and high tones on the same vowel segment. These are falling and rising tones respectively. Any attempt to account for this within the standard generative framework will give us two contradictory specifications.

Woo (1969) (cited in Goldsmith 1976b: 26) suggests that all contour tones are necessarily the concatenation of two level tones. That is, a rising tone actually comprises a sequence of low-high tones; falling tones comprise high-low tones which Goldsmith represents as [v] and [^] respectively.

Examples 9 (i) and (ii) are taken from Melzian (1937) by Erhahon 1995:19).

(i) idadán 'a guess'

(ii) ògìgbàn 'a wild yam'

They are presented thus:

9a (i)

(ii)

Examples (9b) i and ii are however our own

9b (i)

ekpehan 'six bags'

(ii)

inwoka 'how many maize?'

These two constructions are represented above. In examples 9a and 9b above, we have two different tones residing on a single vowel segment. Using SPE to analyse the contour tones in the above examples 9 (i) and 9 (ii) will be: [- high] and [+ high]

9 (i) and (ii) will be given as:

[+ high] and [- high]

Since contour tones are treated as single segments, the above examples pose a big problem for SPE because it is not possible for a single segment to be specified for both [+] and [-] for a particular feature. The conclusion, according to Goldsmith, will be to simply say that we cannot represent the contour tones if we stay within the assumption of

ii)

iii)

iv)

b. i)

ii)

iii)

iv)

Notice the stability of high tones and the deletion of vowel segments that bore them in the two examples above. This type of stability cannot be accounted for within the standard theory. Odden (1995:446) concluded by saying that 'given the independence of the tonal and segmental tiers, deletion of a vowel does not entail deletion of tones linked to the vowel.

The third issue which autosegmental phonology was able to resolve is the issue of melody levels. Goldsmith (1976a: 46) sees melody levels as 'significant levels in the grammar which refer to just one or two features in the utterance'. He further said that some sequences of features do form linguistically significant melody levels whereas others do not.

In Edo, vowels can have the following four different tone patterns on them in citation. These are High, Low, Rising and Falling.

- | | | | | | | |
|-----|----|------|------|------------|---|------------------|
| 12. | a) | High | ---- | gá | ; | ówá |
| | | | | 'to save' | | 'epilepsy' |
| | b) | Low | ---- | dé | ; | ìghégbé |
| | | | | 'to buy' | | 'security' |
| | c) | HL | ---- | ògìgbàn | ; | inwókā |
| | | | | 'wild yam' | | 'how much maize' |
| | d) | LH | ---- | éhà | ; | éwòngbón |
| | | | | 'six' | | 'new robe' |

The tone melodies in the above examples may be abstracted from syllables which bear them phonetically, mapping tone to vowels from left to right creating contour tone only at the end of the word when no toneless vowels remain (cf. Odden 1995: 447).

A fourth motivation for the autosegmental theory is the issue of floating tones. Floating tones are independent of vowels. Schachter and Fromkin (1968), within the standard generative theory represent a floating low tone in Akan with a matrix [-segment; + L] with no other segmental specification. Leben (1973) criticised this proposal as being ad hoc since no other segmental feature has been shown to be capable of this sort of representation. Amayo (1976: 196) in his analysis of Edo floating tone and using SPE said that the floating tone is not analysable as the initial 'segment' of the adjectival qualifier. He said that the floating tone is regarded as a linker, which links the head and the qualifier together. Therefore, according to Amayo, the floating tone and the qualifier can be regarded as constituting the qualifier construction. All the above explanations given by Amayo (1976) seem complicated and cumbersome when compared with the non-linear approach which straightforwardly explains the surface attestation through the universal association convention. Nonetheless, we will provide two examples here for emphasis.

- | | | | | | | |
|----|----|-----------|---|-----------|---|-----------------|
| 13 | a) | ámè | + | ámè | → | ámámè |
| | | 'water' | | 'water' | | 'watery' |
| | b) | òtá | + | òtá | → | òtótá |
| | | 'evening' | | 'evening' | | 'every evening' |

The derivations of the two examples above can be given as:

a (i)

ii)

iii)

iv)

surface representation

b. (i)

underlying representation

ii)

by vowel deletion

iii)

iv)

Finally, the issue of bi-directional spreading in language, which posed a problem of analysis for the standard theory has been resolved with autosegmental phonology. This theory recognises the fact that there are some natural languages in which spreading is bi-directional rather than just unidirectional. This means that spreading can be to the right and to the left whereas in the standard theory, it was only to the left.

Goldsmith (1976: 51 – 52) provides examples of bidirectional spreading from Guarani language, one of which will be given below:

14.a

do + ro + ha i hu + i

N

O (underlying form)

(N represents a nasal autosegment while O is the oral autosegment)

b.

N

O

→ do + ro + haihu + I

In (14a) the first consonant is linked to a nasal autosegment underlyingly while the vowel with the star or accent, as Goldsmith refers to it, is linked to an oral autosegment underlyingly. Since the first consonant is linked underlyingly to a nasal autosegment, it should be realised on the surface as [n], but we observed that in (14a) it is realised as an oral stop though prenasalised as a result of its being linked to a nasal autosegment. This is accounted for by the fact that the oral autosegment spreads both ways to the left and to the right, affecting even underlyingly nasal segments as we see above.

Pulleyblank (1983) went further to say that spreading should be conditioned by the grammar of the language. The implicit prediction by the accepted notation for phonological rules is that spreading should be simpler if it occurs only to the left or only to the right. The spreading is not as a result of a specific phonological rule, but rather as a result of the geometry of autosegmental representation, and its well-formedness condition.

Well-Formedness Condition (WFC)

The parameters for the implementation of an autosegmental phonology model are Goldsmith's (1976) well-formedness conditions, popularly referred to as WFC. These conditions, which are three, are set out in 15 below:

- 15 i) All vowels are associated with at least one tone
- ii) All tones are associated with at least one vowel
- iii) Association lines do not cross

These conditions above act as guiding principles on the linking of tones to tone bearing units. Goldsmith (1976a) earlier on referred to autosegments as though being independent of their segment tiers, they still need to be linked to the segments in order to have a well-formed output. However, these WFC's left many questions unanswered. They include:

- a) Which features are autosegmentalised in the language and how many tiers are there (cf. Ewen 1980, 1982; Hulst and Smith 1982 a & b)?
- b) What is the relationship between tiers (McCarthy 1979 1981; Halle and Vergnaud 1980, Clements and Keyser 1981 and Marantz 1982)?
- c) What is the possibility of a core tier (Hulst and Smith) 1982a; Pulleyblank (1983)?

Williams (1976) came out with a mapping proposal, which, to a large extent, was able to provide adequate answers to the three questions raised above on how the autosegments should be linked.

These Mapping Proposals are:

- a) Map from left to right, a sequence of tones onto a sequence of syllables;
- b) Assign one tone per syllable, until you run out of tones, then,
- c) Assign the last tone that was specified to the remaining untoned syllable to the right.
- d) Until you encounter the next syllable, to the right belonging to a morpheme with specified tone.

- e) If the above procedure runs out of syllables, more than one tone may be assigned to the last vowel only if the grammar of the language includes a stipulation to that effect.

In comparing Williams' (1976) mapping proposals with Goldsmith's (1976) WFC, we discover that the former is better because we would require more than the WFC's to handle 16 below.

Williams' Mapping Proposal in (c) above will adequately take care of 16a, whereas Goldsmith (1976a) would need some extra tone-linking rules.

Apart from the issue of how autosegments may be linked, another question that was raised was when the conventions should apply. The initial assumption was that the conventions apply throughout a derivation when they can. Pulleyblank (1983; 1985) changed this general opinion. It is now the view that the conventions apply only at the beginning of a derivation, but not automatically elsewhere. He noted that the results that would be obtained from the two approaches would be quite different. For example, in a deletion-rule that involve vowels, an automatic application of the association conventions will give us 17 below, but the output of (20) will be unaffected if the application of the convention was applied at the beginning of the derivations unless a relinking rule applies. The examples below are from Pulleyblank (1983:33).

17.

18.

The two approaches will give two different outputs in a number of cases and Pulleyblank (1983) suggests that the choice to adopt in either of the two approaches will depend, to a large extent, on empirical considerations.

Evidence from Edo supports Pulleyblank's claim that relinking or delinking of tone is not automatic. Relinking may or may not occur when a tone is set afloat as a result of a phonological process such as vowel elision or glide formation.

Let us consider the examples below:

19a

ii)

by vowel elision

iii)

by (H) linking and L delinking

iv)

The above examples in 19 a & b show that relinking and delinking should occur in Edo or else, some of our derivations will be anomalous. We will wrongly derive *[idôzi] and *[byêgbé].

Pulleyblank revised the WFC and came out with what he called Association Convention and WFC. This is stated in 20 below:

20 a. **Association Conventions:**

Map a sequence of tones onto a sequence of tone bearing units:

- i. From left to right
- ii. In a one – to – one relation.

b. **Well-Formedness Condition**

Association lines do not cross.

We shall therefore uphold the position that tone assignment rules should be language specific (where necessary). This is because different languages have various rules in assigning tones to tone bearing segments while some tones are left unassigned.

Associating the Tiers

The fact that all phonological representation is multitiered and that all these tiers are connected or co-ordinated in order to obtain a well-formed phonological representation is not contested by any autosegmental phonologists. What is however, in dispute by these autosegmentalists is how this co-ordination is implemented. While some phonologists are of the view that autosegments are linked to consonant and vowel segments or syllables as we have in the example below:

Others believe that autosegments should be linked to a structural (CV) tier as we have in example below:

The former position was held by early phonologists like Goldsmith (1976a, 1979) and Clements and Ford (1979), while the latter position was held by phonologists like McCarthy (1979, 1981), Halle and Vergnaud (1982), Clements and Keyser (1983) and Pulleyblank (1983, 1986a).

The major shortcoming of the earlier position is that it does not show the actual independence of the tiers since the autosegments are shown to be properties of the units bearing them after the application of the association convention. The more acceptable option, and which we are adopting in this study is as expressed by the latter phonologists (i.e. McCarthy 1979, 1981, Halle and Vergnaud (1982), Clements and Keyser (1983) and Pulleyblank (1983, 1986a). They propose that autosegments are indirectly linked through a structure CV skeleton which has a different status from the autosegmental tiers. These CV skeletons are made up of C and V elements through which these autosegments are linked and from which they are linked to tone bearing units.

The CV tiers determine the timing relation of the autosegmental tiers. There are two major advantages of this. One, this CV node allows us to maintain the independence of the tiers (unlike the former position, which does not show the actual independence of the tiers). Second, it enables a clearer representation of different process in language simultaneously.

According to Aziza (1997: 45) Clements and Halle (1983) propose that the skeleton is part of the universal phonological representation and serves multiple roles. They include:

- i) Forming the basis of syllabification rules which require that V element on the skeletal tiers dominate syllable peaks (vowel and syllabic consonants)

- ii) Forming the basis of phonological quantity such as long segments are represented as single phonemes which are linked to two units of the CV tiers (long segments count one unit from the point of view of their segments quantity but as two from the point of view). On the other hand, complex segments such as affricates and prenasalised stops are represented as two phonemes linked to a single C slot on the CV tiers (that is, they are two units from the point of view of their feature substance but as one from that of segmental quantity).
- iii) Compensatory lengthening by which deletion of one segment is accompanied by the lengthening of another (usually adjacent) one is expressed as the spreading of a neighbouring phoneme on the skeletal position left vacant by the deleted one.

Pulleyblank (1983; 1986a) further suggests the constraints, which are reproduced below.

- 22. Autosegmental tiers can only link to slots in the skeletal tiers.

While Goldsmith (1990:53) re-echoes these constraints which he calls linkage condition and which is reproduced below:

- 23. **Linkage condition**

A segment will not be phonetically realised if it is not linked to a position in the skeletal tier.

With the above argument, the skeletal tier is thus an integral part of phonological representation.

The theoretical framework discussed above is relevant in chapter four where we discuss the interface between tones and syntax in Edo.

3.2 Autosegmental Morphology

Goldsmith's (1976a) fourth proposal shows that individual tiers may constitute independent morphemes. McCarthy (1979, 1981, 1983), Sagey (1986) and Leiber (1987) contain many examples of this phenomenon.

In many natural languages of the world, morphological categories are expressed mainly by morphemes have fixed canonical patterns that might be called shape invariant

morphology. The most common shape invariant morphology is reduplication, but it is also central to the somewhat rare template morphology of most Kwa languages (Aziza 1997). McCarthy (1979, 1981) shows us convincingly, in his account of semitic morphology that consonantal roots, vocalic inflections and CV skeleton are different morphemes and must be placed on different tiers. To explain and expatiate such problems of morphological structure, McCarthy (1979;1983) proposes the following structure for the morpheme:

Figure 5

The morpheme node (not node in McCarthy's terminology) identifies a string as a morpheme. It contains all non phonological information associated with the morpheme, such as rule diacritics, its status as a root or affix, its identity as a morpheme and the structure of the morpheme (i.e CV combination). McCarthy shows convincingly that this structure is descriptively necessary and therefore theoretically desirable (Egbokhare 1990:73). We will base our account of the morphological structures of Edo on this proposal. However, we will extend this theory further to Prosodic template morphology. We will show further in this work that prosodic theory is not only a viable alternative to those before it, but also superior to them, revealing and capturing regularities that have played no role before now.

3.3 Lexicalist Hypothesis

Lexicalist Hypothesis is useful in the analysis of names in Edo. Chomsky (1970) argued in "Remarks on Nominalization" that word-formation cannot be accounted for by means of transformational rules as had until then be assumed. Instead, he suggested that a

lexical approach was appropriate, where the term lexical, essentially means the complex words (such as those formed with derivational affixes, and in the case of Edo language, compounding and nominalization) are accounted for in the so-called lexical component of the grammar.

Other exponents of these views that later emerged within the same field include Lieber 1980, 1983; Moortgat et al, 1981; Selkirk 1982; Toman 1983; Williams 1981a, b, and others. However, Selkirk's (1982) monograph *The Syntax of Words* and a series of articles by Edwin Williams (including his 1981a, b,) become the most representative examples of this. These researchers made others to see Lexicalism as superior to any other theory that does not explicitly consider the existence of the lexicon (or a lexical component) in the grammar.

In some sense, however, the focus on the lexicon leads away from the classical question of generative theories. In generative syntax, for instance, the declared aim has been a principled representation of the human linguistic faculty rather than the study of the lists. In view of these, some researchers have argued that the lexicon itself is not the primary focus of morphology or word-formation theories, especially, if understood as a real-time object. The 'real-time' lexicon (Di Sciullo and Williams's (1987) "psychological lexicon") remains a legitimate object of inquiry, as witnessed by numerous psycholinguistic studies; but one cannot presume that list-based mechanisms of storage and retrieval are the basic mechanisms of human "word-faculty". Discussing this issue, Di Sciullo and Williams have suggested that:

Morphology is more like syntax than hereto fore thought. Both of course have lists- the list of primes, which are the words in syntax and the morphemes in morphology. In syntax, there is of course no further list of "actual" versus "potential" phrases; the whole theory is about potential objects, though some are in fact actual (How are you, kick the bucket). In our view morphology is a theory of potential objects in exactly the same sense. (Di Sciullo and Williams 1987:21; emphasis added)

To us, this approach frees up the investigator to study principles that govern "the ability to create and understand new words" (Toman 1983:6) rather than stick to superficial differences in the material nature of the data investigated.

One of the cardinal points of Lexicalism, as discussed above is that certain derived nominals are lexical in nature. This theory claims that word-formation should be accounted for in the lexicon, and that the word-formation rules are structure-building rules of non-transformational pattern. In other words, Lexicalism allows us to concentrate on morphological issues rather than treat morphology as a subject of syntax or phonology.

Halle's (1973) schematic representation of the Lexicalist Hypothesis as produced by Spencer (1991:78) is shown below.

Morphemes → WFR → Filter → Dictionary → Syntax → Phonology → Output.
(Phonology can also be an input into WFR)

The above representation starts with the *morpheme* that is the minimal, indivisible unit of grammatical description, a set of *Word-Formation Rules* (WFRs), which over-generates, in that it produces all intending words in the language, the *filter* sorts out actual words, and a *dictionary* of existing words that gives the phonological, syntactic, morphological, and semantic interpretation of the words.

It must however be stated that there are different versions of the Lexicalist Hypothesis. We have the Strong Lexicalist Hypothesis (SLH), which asserts that syntactic transformations cannot analyze word-internal morphology at all. (cf Chomsky 1970, Jackendoff 1975). We also have the Split Morphology version. This version asserts that all derivations are assigned to their bases because they are lexically derived (Perlmutter 1988, Anderson 1992). The last version is the Weak Lexicalist Hypothesis (WLH) which claims that some words are syntactically derived, while others are not. In other words, the WLH allows some transformations to affect word-internal morphology. The kernel of WLH claim is that there is indeed a way that morphology and syntax interact (Baker 1988, Lieber 1992). Pulleyblank and Akinlabi, (1988) put it succinctly in their study of Phrasal Morphology in Yorùbá, when they assert that there is a symbiotic relationship between morphology and syntax in Yorùbá with their diagram:

Morphology → Syntax → Morphology

Because of their generic relationship, we have discovered, in this study, that the principle of word formation rules as we have in Yorùbá is also applicable to Edo personal names because they are derived nominals, through the operations of some morphological

processes of nominalization, compounding, and prefixation (as will be shown later in this section). Since many Edo personal names have argument structure which indicates the kind of internal structure existing within a personal name, we proposed that the only version of the Lexicalist Hypothesis which can accommodate what we have in Edo personal names is the one that allows for an interaction between morphology and syntax. Therefore, our analysis of morphosyntactic structures of Edo personal names will be carried out within the WLH that allows for syntax to affect morphology, where possible. Therefore, the only aspect of the word that is visible to syntax is its morphosyntactic representations. (MSR) (Anderson 1992).

Adényi (1997:116) proposes a derivational pattern for all Yorùbá personal names. Given the genetic similarities between Yorùbá and Edo, we follow this derivational strategy for Yorùbá personal names to propose same for Edo personal names as shown below:

24. Name = Nominal + (NP) + (VP)

The above rule shows the derivational sources of Edo personal names.

We will also use the Unitary Base Hypothesis (henceforth UBH) as our supporting framework in this section. According to Napoli (1996:177), all word formation processes must select the domain over which they operate and that this domain must be definable as a single morphosyntactic or semantic type. Thus, it is quite common to find affixes that can attach only to adjectives, or only to verbs, or only to nouns. Affixes therefore have the potentials of selecting the stem to which they will attach. If we assume that there are two features: [$\pm$ noun], and [$\pm$ verb], we can then say that the four lexical morphosyntactic categories (often called the major categories) have these feature values (cf. Chomsky (1986b: 2; Haegeman 1991:134, Napoli 1996:177-178).

- | | | |
|------|-------------|------------------|
| 25 a | Noun | [+ noun, -verb] |
| b. | Verb | [-noun, + verb] |
| c. | Adjective | [+ noun, +verb] |
| d. | Preposition | [-noun, - verb]. |

We can then explain, convincingly, the fact that a noun and a verb do not share any feature accounts for why they select different affixes in Edo. Let us compare the examples in 26 (a) to the ones in 26 (b).

26. i. **Íyórré**
 Í yó rré
 1st sg go arrive
 "I have arrived safely"
- ii. **Ídémúdià**
 í dé múdià
 1st sg fall stand
 "I am stabilized"
- iii. **Ígbinédiòṅ**
 Í gbinná èdiòṅ
 1st sg seek protection elders
 "I seek the protection of the elders"
- iv. **Àbíyúwà**
 à bié yé ùwà
 Nom prefix give birth in wealth
 "Born into wealth"

We can equally have Edo personal names with initial nouns as mentioned above. We will only repeat one other example here.

27. i. **Íghómò**
 Íghó ómò
 money child
 "money spent on children is not wasted"

The structural representations of the above constructions can be given below:

28.a.

ì gbinná èdiòn
1st sg seek protection elders
"I seek the protection of the elders"

28.b.

money child
"money spent on children is not wasted"

CHAPTER FOUR

WORD FORMATION PROCESSES IN EDO

4.1 Introduction

Morphology is at the conceptual centre of linguistics. This is because it is the study of word structure, and words are at the interface between morphology, syntax and semantics. Spencer (1988:146) said that morphology is the study of the structure of words, and of the ways in which their structure reflects their relation to other words, both within some larger construction such as a sentence and across the total vocabulary of the language. The overall task of any morphological theory is to adequately study the structure of the words of any language so as to bring order and coherence to our understanding of the various ways of word formation and how they relate to one another. 'Word' is used here to refer to an entity which can neither be separated by movement rules nor can any of its elements be pronominalised. Words are usually the easiest units to identify in the written language. In most writing systems, they are the entities that have spaces on either sides. Our definition of 'word' must, to a large extent, pass the five tests, of word identification as exemplified by Crystal (1997:91). These are potential pause, indivisibility, minimal free forms, phonetic boundaries and semantic unit.

The goal of this chapter is to describe, within autosegmental morphology, the various word formation processes in Edo. First, we shall discuss the structures of some lexical categories such as nouns and verbs. This shall then be followed by detailed analyses of some word formation processes in the language. Some of these include nominalization, compounding, reduplication, affixation and number formation. We shall also discuss into detail, ideophones and loanwords in the language. We will, as part of this work, look at different tonal behaviours in different word formation processes in the Edo language.

4.2.1 Noun Structure in Edo

According to Welmers (1973:159) in all branches of the Niger-Kordofanian language family, with the exception of Mande, it is typical that a noun in its simplest form can be analysed as constituted of a stem and an affix. In a number of West African

languages such affixes are prefixes which distinguish number. Elugbe (1989) accounts for the Proto-Edo (PE) as having a noun class system in which the initial vowels function as class prefixes. Egbokhare (1990:77) notes that the noun class system is still observable in Degema (DE), (Elugbe 1989) and Oloma (NWE) (Elugbe and Schubert 1976). Egbokhare further states that in Emai, traces of this class system can be observed in number formation in nouns and the pattern of vowel selection in nominalization.

The noun in Edo can theoretically be of any length. However, nouns in the language always have vowel initials and are basically bisyllabic or trisyllabic. Longer nouns in our own view, are regarded as derived nouns. The vowel initials by these nouns are historically class markers. In the case of bisyllabic nouns in Edo, four tonal combinations are possible on them. These are HH, LL, HL and LH. Although we have H!H in the language, we will regard this as underlyingly a sequence of H(L)H. We will consider these bisyllabic nouns based on their tones.

Examples:

29. **Group A: H – H**
- i. ākā 'trumpet'
- ii. áwé 'a large band'
- iii. ékhué 'garden egg'
- iv. ádẹ̀n 'hooked pole used for plucking fruits'
- Group B: H – L**
- i. ākà 'a grass snake'
- ii. ěkpà 'firt' (a blow with a clenched fut)
- iii. údẹ̀ 'a children's disease'
- iv. ibà 'mud bench'
- Group C: L – H**
- i. ọ̀ká 'leader'
- ii. ọ̀hà 'wide'
- iii. úwú 'death'
- iv. ùké 'hair dressing pad'

	Group D:	L – L
i.	óhá	'catarrah'
ii.	àdà	'crossroads'
iii.	òkò	'parcel'
iv.	èsi	'bush pig'

We also have eight tonal patterns for trisyllabic nouns. Some examples of these are:

30.	Group A:	H – H – H
i.	íyóyó	'a kind of vegetable'
ii.	ágbádá	'flowing robe'
iii.	ígéngén	'a small branch' (of a tree)
iv.	ósisí	'gun amunition'
	Group B:	H-H - L
i.	èbétè	'a variety of brown bush rat'
ii.	ùgóngòn	'the sharp edge of something'
iii.	égnówè	'a very narrow path'
iv.	ábòkpò	'a matchet – like wooden staff'
	Group C:	H – L – H
i.	ìkòlò	'earthworms'
ii.	òhóghá	'an empty state'
iii.	ádòlò	'reconciliation'
iv.	ádiyè	'chicken, fowl'
	Group D:	H – L – L
i.	éghòdìn	'African black kite'
ii.	ìhòkpò	'tent/mosquito net'
iii.	ìgwèsè	'expert'
iv.	ùhírì	'a variety of large ape'
	Group E:	L – H – H
i.	ìkpìghó	'cowries'
ii.	òdóré	'the front of a house'
iii.	òkóbó	'a foolish person'
iv.	ùkéké	'a piece of stick; a peg'

Group F: L - H - L

- i. ẹdógbó 'neighbourhood'
- ii. Igwábó 'elbow'
- iii. ọgbígbí 'excitement'
- iv. ùgbégbé 'cross' (in the christian way)

Group G: L - L - L

- i. ùkátà 'straw hat with broad rims'
- ii. ọbàlọ 'pain; misery'
- iii. isòkẹ̀n 'contentment; satisfaction'
- iv. ẹ̀bùbẹ̀ 'fine sand; dust'

Group H: L - L - H

- i. ẹ̀khùnkhùn 'sweat fly; gnat'
- ii. idàgbó 'a public place'
- iii. ọ̀mùhẹ̀n 'beginning; start'
- iv. ádàzẹ̀n 'an affluent and respectable person in a community'

There are also derived nouns in the language. Some of these include:

- 31. i. ifwẹ̀kò ← i fú ẹ̀kó
'being gentle of the belly', gentleness, calmness
'np gentle belly'
- ii. igbógyẹ ← i gbé ọ̀giẹ̀
'making fun, jesting' np do laughter
- iii. àgùkìsínmwinngiẹ̀ ← a guẹ̀ ùkì sìnwi ọ̀giẹ̀
'the morning star' np know moon struggle superior
'that who with the moon struggle for supremacy'
- iv. ibàlẹ̀gbẹ̀ ← i bálọ̀ ẹ̀gbé
'hot temper' np hurt body

There are also some words with more than four syllables whose derivational history we are unable to discover.

32. i. àgánmwinsósó

'a serious case of whitlow, believed to be caused by the poison of a certain kind of caterpillar known as 'isúé'

ii. ákuénrhánkuinri
 'packer of twigs and strings'

iii. óghòdó|gbò
 'a kind of weed; wild sugar-cane not edible'

In view of the discussions concerning various segmental structures of the nouns, we may then represent the noun with the structure below:

(cf:Egbokhare1990)

Figure 8

4.2.2 Verb Structure

4.2.2.1.Simple Verb

The structure of the simple verb in Edo can be graphically captured by the following

$$33 \quad V \longrightarrow C V ((C)V)(V)$$

The verb sequence structure condition states that a verb stem in the language always begins with a consonant. Amayo (1976:96) observed that verb stem in Edo may be a maximum of two consonants each followed by a sequence of two vowels and a minimum structure of one consonant. From the available data at our disposal, we found out that Edo verb can have up to four consonants each as against two observed by Amayo (1976). We conclude then that the verbs with about four consonants are complex verbs. These are as given in examples (e) and (f) below.

34.

a) CV

- i. dẹ 'buy'
- ii. lá 'resound'
- iii. gbé 'beat'

b) CVCV

- i. wẹwẹ 'drizzle'
- ii. yìghẹ 'weak'
- iii. tilá 'despise'

c) CVV

- i. tée 'decorate'
- ii. múán 'multiply'
- iii. kàá 'carve'

d) CVVCV

- i. khùnmwòn 'sick'

e) CVCVCV

- i. sọyènmwèn 'rejoice'
- iii. dàmwènhọ 'obey, head'

f) CVCVCVCV

- i. sùnnósùnnó 'slow'

4.2.2.2 Tonal Structure of the Verb Stem

There are two views of the tonal structure of the verb stem in Edo. Melzian (1937:XII) is of the view that verb stems in Edo exhibit lexical tones. Westcott (1963:146-147), Elugbe (1973:17) and Amayo (1976:230) all agree that verb stems exhibit purely grammatical tone. From our analysis of the data, we discovered that it is not possible to elicit any minimal contrast of the tone on verb stem independently of their grammatical context. This is because in citation, tones on verbs are predictable (they are always high tones), but within phrases or sentences, the tone are determined by the syntactic construction. We therefore have no basis for representing tone on verb stems in the lexicon. The present study will therefore support the position of Westcott (1963),

Elugbe (1973) and Amayo (1976) that Edo verb stems exhibit exclusively grammatical tone. We will also postulate, therefore, that though Edo verb stems do not have tonal representation in the lexicon, they acquire tonal representation at the syntactic level. Therefore, verb stems obligatorily have tonal representation at the systematic phonemic level. (cf. Amayo, 1976). At the phonetic level, verb stems have high tones if they are monosyllabic and low-high if they are bisyllabic.

However, every syntactic context in Edo has its own phonetic realization of tone on the verb stem. We will illustrate with a few examples of these various realizations with noun object. In constructions involving past-tense, past-perfect, habitual negative, past progressive, the tone of the verb stems are high. Some of these examples are:

35. i. i dè | wòkpá 'I bought a goat' (past tense).
 ii. ii dè | wòkpá 'I didn't buy a goat' (habitual negative).
 iii. i dè | wòkpá nè 'I have bought a goat' (past perfect).
 iv. i gháá- dè | wòkpá 'I was buying a goat' (past progressive)

In contrast, in constructions involving present progressive, future tense and habitual, the tones of the verb stems are low. Some of these examples are:

36. i. i dè | wòkpá 'I am buying a goat' (present progressive)
 ii. i ghá dè | wòkpá 'I will buy a goat' (future tense)
 iii. i dè | wòkpá 'I always buy a goat' (habitual)

We will identify two verbal suffixes in the language. These are the iterative or plural verbs represented as *lv* and the past tense morpheme represented as *rv*. We have a situation where some category of verbs are reduplicated, giving us the intensive sense of the verb stem. (This will, however, be discussed fully under affixes).

The iterative suffix is added to a verb to indicate plurality or an action that is repeated. The suffix agrees with the verb stem in vowel height and nasality. These are as shown below:

- 37 a)
- | | | |
|------|-------|------------|
| i. | wúló | 'die' |
| ii. | vúló | 'dip up' |
| iii. | sóló | 'shout' |
| iv. | kúlú | 'dip' |
| v. | délé | 'fall' |
| vi. | gbèlé | 'beat' |
| vii. | wióló | 'slip out' |

- b)
- | | | |
|------|-------|--------------|
| i. | zóló | 'pick out' |
| ii. | vbóló | 'extract' |
| iii. | táló | 'say/state' |
| iv. | sáló | 'sting' |
| v. | lóló | 'press over' |
| vi. | bèlé | 'slice' |
| vii. | vèlé | 'burst' |

- c)
- | | | |
|------|--------|----------------------|
| i. | mánó | 'mould' |
| ii. | gbènné | 'carve' ; 'to write' |
| iii. | súnnó | 'be slow' |
| iv. | vinnó | 'dart' |
| v. | fànnó | 'loosen' |
| vi. | kinnó | 'coil around' |

From the various examples above, the intensive (plural) form of verbs is derived by adding a CV suffix to a monosyllabic, or bisyllabic CVV verb stem. The consonant of the suffix is either 'l' or 'n' depending on whether the vowel of the stem is oral or nasal. Since the distribution of 'l' is more in the data, we posit an underlying 'l' for this consonant. This then becomes 'n' in the environment of nasal vowels.

Also in the language, the simple past tense is marked on the verb by the suffixation of the morpheme 're' to the verb stem. Let us consider these examples:

38.

i.	kúú	'play'	'kùní'	'played'
ii.	dó	'weave'	'dòró'	'wove'
iii.	dé	'buy'	'dèrè'	'bought'
iv.	kókó	'gather'	'kókóró'	'gathered together'
v.	hé	'refuse'	'hèrè'	'refused'
vi.	lé	'cook'	'lèrè'	'cooked'
vii.	wú	'die'	'wùrú'	'died'

The above examples show that the simple past morpheme is phonologically conditioned. While the consonant 'r' is constant, the vowel of the suffix copy totally, all the features of the vowel of the stem. In this case, the vowel of the suffix becomes identical with that of the stem as can be seen in examples 38 above.

Both the plural and the simple past tense can occur together in the same verb. That is, it is possible to have the simple past tense suffix and the plural verbs together. When this occurs, the plural suffix occurs first and the vowel of this suffix takes all the features of the vowel of the stem. Some of these examples include:

39. i.	sí	'drag'	siló	silóró
ii.	sáán	'jump'	sánnó	sánnórèn
iii.	tón	'dig'	tónnó	tónnórèn
iv.	dé	'fall'	dèlé	dèlèrè
v.	sé	'sew'	sélé	sèlèrè
vi.	vú	'uproot'	vuló	vulóró
vii.	wú	'die'	wuló	wulóró
viii.	só	'tear'	sóló	solórè

Our earlier claim above is that monosyllabic verbs have high tone at the phonetic level. We however discovered that after the suffix and the simple past morpheme are added, the tones on them become LH. We will account for this tonal output by postulating a tone polarisation rule. We will say that after suffixation the tone on the output is LHL. This is because a bisyllabic verb in Edo has a LH tone on it.

4.2.2.3 Complex Verbs

Another category of verbs in Edo are those regarded as complex or idiomatic verbs. They comprise of either a verb and another verb or a verb and a noun. They are so called because it is difficult to determine their meaning from the combination of the constituents.

Let us consider some of these examples:

The verb may even be a verb + (verb) (noun) + verb + noun or a combination of a verb, another verb or noun and or another verb.

40.a) Verb + Noun constructions

- | | | | | | |
|------|------------------------|---|-------------------|---|---|
| i. | kpéé
shout | + | úrù
voice | → | kpóórù
'shout voice' (to preach) |
| ii. | mié
find | + | árò
eye | → | miáró
'find eye' (to have the opportunity to do sth.) |
| iii. | lǎ
cross | + | èvbò
town | → | lèvbò
'pass town' (to roam through town) |
| iv. | zè
choose | + | ùnù
mouth | → | zùnù
'choose mouth' (to be fastidious about what one eats) |
| v. | rú
'to do' | + | ésè
'kindness' | → | rwésè
'do kindness' (to bestow favour) |
| vi. | khòò
'to be bitter' | + | èkó
'belly' | → | khèkó
'spoil stomach' (to upset or be upset) |
| vii. | gbàèn
'shift' | + | ègbé
'body' | → | gbàègbé
'shift body' (to move out of the way, to avoid) |

b) Verb + Verb Constructions

- | | | | | | |
|-----|--------------|---|--------------------|---|--|
| i. | yá
cause | + | gbá
gather | → | yàgbá
'to become stuck; develop a stalemate |
| ii. | yá
'make' | + | yi
'make'(know) | → | yáyí
'believe' |

- iii. zé + tá → zètá
'choose' 'say' 'fabricate'
- iv. zé + yí → zèyí
'select' 'take note of' 'pay attention to'
- v. fí + dón → fídón
'shoot' 'construct' 'throw and miss' (to miss a target)
- vi. gbé + kué → gbékwé
'break' 'over' 'break and spill over' (to abuse vituperatively)

c) **Verb + Noun + Noun + (Verb) Construction**

- i. zé + èné + ùnú → zènúnú
'speak' 'the' 'mouth' 'speak that of the mouth' (to state one's case)
- ii. tón + ègbé + mú → tèngbénú
'lift' 'body' 'carry' 'to lift body' (to be arrogant)
- iii. rhié + ùkó + rrọ́ → rhiúkórọ́
'hang up' 'calabash' 'turn over' 'to hang up the gourd' (to commit suicide by hanging)
- iv. rhié + òbó + yé + èbé → rhiòbóylébé
'take' 'arm' 'make' 'paper' 'put hand on paper' (to sign or certify a document)
- v. rhán + vbè + àrò → rhàànrò
'untie' 'at' 'eye' 'open at the eye's (to be civilised)
- vi. fian + yán + ègbé → fiányànègbé
'cut' 'tear off' 'body' 'to cut over body' (to overestimate one's worth)

The examples above indicate that it is possible for both verb and noun to occur independently or be separated in a sentence by another noun, but whether they are together or separated, they are fixed collocations with a single meaning. They are semantically non-compositional. The meaning of the verbal constructions cannot be worked out on the basis of the meanings of the words which they contain. We must however recognise them as an atomic unit if we must understand their meaning within

that context. In addition, we see that the verb incorporates the meaning of the nouns to express an action, state, or process. Within this context, the noun cannot be said to be performing a nominal but rather a verbal function.

We observe under this section that when two verbs with high tones are collocated, what we have is low-high. This observation tallies with our earlier comment that monosyllabic verbs have high tones on them, while bisyllabic verbs have low-high tones. How then, do we account for this low-high tones after collocation of two simple verbs with high tones. In our view, there are two possible ways of accounting for this. One is to suggest a LH tomorph on the verbs after collocation; with the assumption that the verbs are toneless prior to collocation. With this in mind, the tonal output after collocation will be then LH. Another option is to suggest that immediately after collocation, the initial tone on the verb takes a tone that is polar opposite the second verb, starting with a low tone. Any of the two options, can be employed to get the fact of the language.

4.3 Nominalization

In this work, we will define nominalization as a process of deriving nominals from a combination of other lexical categories or phrasal entities. In Edo, a noun is formed from a combination of a prefix and a verb phrase or from the combination of a prefix and other lexical categories such as verb phrase and others

We can categorise nominalisation into two on the basis of the tones they bear. These are the LLL(L) and the LHL(L) patterns.

The LHL(H) tonal patterns are formed by the affixation of a discontinuous morpheme *ù...mwè* to a verb stem. While the LLL(L) tonal patterns are formed by the affixation of prefixes to verbs or verb phrases, the tones on these category of nominals are peculiar; they all have low tones i.e. LLL(L). In Edo, nominalisation as a word formation process is very productive. Nouns are formed from other lexical categories, including the noun itself. The structure of Edo nominalisation that we will examine in this work can be represented as:

41. Derived noun → nom. prefix + vb + (vb) + Nn + (Nn)

The above representation says that derived nouns can be formed with the concatenation of a nominalising prefix (which can be any of the following six oral vowels i; ú; ò; ò; è; à), a verb; and optionally, another verb; a noun and, optionally, another noun.

Let us consider these examples:

42. i) ò # dólò # èvbò → ò # dólèvbò → òdólèvbò
 nom. prefix 'reconcile' 'people/kind' 'social conformist'
- ii) i # ghè # ègbé → i # ghègbé → ighègbé
 nom. prefix 'support' 'body' 'selfsupport, security'
- iii) ò # só # árábá → ò # sóárábá → òsóárábá
 nom. prefix 'tap' 'rubber' 'rubber tapper'

Omozuwa (1997) and Aziza (1997) noted the peculiarity of the tonal pattern of the non-gerundive nominals in Edo and Urhobo respectively. Omozuwa (1997:116) said that "all instances of CV # VCV (CV) collocation or indeed all verb phrase in Edo could be nominalized by means of a low tone prefix ɔ/ò/. Thus, irrespective of the tones on the verb phrase, the nominalised forms are realised with a low melody on successive syllable". Some of his examples include the following:

43. i. ɔò # lè # izé → ɔòlizé
 'cook' 'rice' 'boiling rice'
- ii. ɔò # tò # óxá → ɔòtóxá
 'tell' 'story' 'a story teller'
- iii. ɔò # kpá # èèkpèti → ɔòkpáèèkpèti
 'make' 'box' 'maker of boxes'

Omozuwa (1997:116) in his statement above, made two assertions. First, that it is only vowel ò that can occur as a nominal prefix in verb or verb phrases. Second, that the tonal outputs of the nominalisation are always low tones. From the available data at our disposal, we will not agree with this. This is because after collocating nominalising prefixes with certain verb phrases, their tonal outputs are not always low. Hence, the sub-categories of LLL(L) and LHL(H). Also, it is not only the low tone prefix ò that can be

used to nominalise the verb phrase. In fact, six of the oral vowels with low tones in the language can be used.

44. Let us consider these examples:

- i) ò # fūá → òfūá
 Nom.prefix 'perish' 'destruction; annihilation'
- ii) ò # khié → òkhié
 Nom.prefix 'mourn' 'mourner'
- iii) è # tàlò → étálò
 Nom.prefix 'talk' 'the act of talking'
- iv) ì # yámá → 'iyámá
 Nom.prefix 'put a mark' 'an identification mark'

However, the above examples from our data shows that tonal outputs of the nominalisation are sometimes not low. It is also seen that other vowels in the language may also participate in the nominalisation process.

Aziza (1997:217) also noted the influence of a nominalizing prefix on a verb phrase in Urhobo (an Edoid language) when she said that most nominals, which signal agentive meaning, are derived from verb + noun sequences and they bear only low tones. The process of nominalisation includes alternating the original tones borne by the nouns so that all the vowels in the nominals are realised on the low tones. Some of her examples include:

45. i) jèrè + ìghó → òjòrìghò
 'hold' 'money' 'treasurer'
- ii) tà + òtá → òtótá
 'say' 'word' 'spokesman'
- iii) rèrè + ótá → òrèròtá
 'watch' 'ground' 'security guard'

We discovered that she has only two nominalizing prefixes ò and ó, which we assume, are driven by vowel harmony.

However, we will like to look at the various types of stems that are utilised in this nominalization process. Based on their morphological behaviours, Edo verb stems can be categorised into five main groups. These are simple verb stems; serial verb stems; verb +

noun stems; verb + verb + noun stems and verb + noun + noun stems. Any of these stems can be collocated with the vowel prefixes to give us the various nominals that we have in the language. We will give samples of these stems with their various vowel prefixes.

4.3.1 Simple Verb Stems

In Edo, a simple verb stem may be either monosyllabic or bisyllabic. It is monosyllabic when it is CV and bisyllabic if it is either CVV or CVCV. Examples of monosyllabic simple verb stems are stated below:

46. i) é # kpá → èkpá
 nom-prefix 'vomit' 'vomiting'
- ii) í # vè → ivè
 nom-prefix 'price' 'a price'
- iii) ù # wú → úwú
 nom-prefix 'die' 'death'

Examples of bisyllabic simple verb stem with CVV pattern are stated below:

47. i) à # rhúé → àrùé
 nom-prefix 'circumcise' 'circumcision'
- ii) ô # khòó → ɔ̀òkhòó
 nom-prefix 'evil' 'malicious act, evil deed'
- iii) è # fùá → èfùá
 nom-prefix 'white' 'whiteness'

Examples of bisyllabic simple verb stems with CVCV structures are stated below:

- 48 i) í # lèlé → ile!lè
 'follow' 'procedure'
- ii) è # hòhó → èhòhò
 'blow' 'wind'
- iii) ò # ɣghághá → òghághá
 'brag; show off' 'brag; boast; swaggering'

4.3.2 Serial Verb Stems

These consist of two root morphemes. They are of two types, it may either be two root verbs or a verb with a particle: some of these include:

49. i) ò # mù # rù → ò # múrù → ómúrù
 nom. pre. 'carry' 'do' 'cheating'
- ii) à # sí # kókó → à # síkókó → àsíkókó
 'pull' 'gather' 'gathering'
- iii) à # fián # gbé → à # fiàngbe → àfiàngbè
 'cut' 'add' 'blessing'
- iv. à # kù # gbé → à # kùgbè → àkùgbè
 'join' 'add' 'unity, accord'

Some of the structures of verb stems that we discussed above are not peculiar to Edo language. Egbokhare (1990:80-84) had a similar classification in respect of Emai. However, his classification includes the following structures, which cannot be attested in Edo. These are VV, V and CVVV.

4.3.3 Verb + Noun Stems

These are verb stems that are derived from a verb plus noun combinations. They are numerous in the language. Some examples of these include:

50. i) ò # gbé # ehénz → ò # gbèhèn → ògbèhènḗ
 'pick' 'fish' 'fisherman'
- ii) ò # zẹ # édú → ò zèdù → òzèdù
 speak a language 'translation' 'interpreter'
- iii) i # yín # ehónz → i # yèhónḗ → iyèhòn
 block' 'ear' 'deafness; disobedience'

4.3.4. Verb + Verb + Noun Stems

These are verb stems with splitting verbs plus a noun as an object. Some of these examples will include:

51 i) ù # tònṣ̄ # yé # òtò → ù # tónyòtò → ùtónyòtòṣ̄
'bury on the ground' 'set' 'ground' 'a big drinking pot buried to the rim into the ground in order to keep the water cool'

ii) ù # dè # fí # àgbòṅṅò → ù # défyàgbòn → ùdéfyàgbòn
'fall' 'throw' 'world' 'one who dropped into the world', "an orphan"

4.3.5 Verb + Noun + Noun Stems

These are verb stems with a verb and two-noun combinations. Some of these examples are:

52 i) ì # ré # òkó # òdé → ì # ròkòdè → ìròkòdè
'eat' 'a parcel' 'way' 'eating of a parcel on the way' "mis-appropriation of property", etc.'

ii) ɔ̀ò # màá # òmwán # emwín → ɔ̀ # màmwànáemwín → ɔ̀màmwànáemwín
'teach' 'person' 'thing' 'teacher'

4.3.6 Verb + Noun + Verb Stems

These are verb stems with verb + noun + verb combination. Some of these examples are:

53 i) ọ̀ # myẹ́n # ọ̀mwán # fá → ọ̀ # myọ̀mwánfá → ọ̀myọ̀mwánfá
'see' 'person' 'set free' 'saviour (in the Christian sense)'

ii) ì # fàá # ègbé # rùá → ì # fàègbwá → ìfàègbwá
'disgrace' 'body' 'extreme' 'the act of disgracing oneself, "disgrace; embarrassment"

4.3.7 Meaning of Vowel Prefixes in Nominalization

Majority of these nominal prefixes that we have do not occur haphazardly in the language, but can have the following semantic implications. We must however note that this claim is not absolute as there are a examples in the language that do not fall into this category. Majority of the vowel prefixes, however, fall into the category that we discussed below.

4.3.7.1 Instrumental

/ù/, The prefix denotes instruments for achieving the action or state expressed by the verb or verb phrase to which it is attached (cf. Omoruyi 1990:109). This instrumental prefix is not peculiar to Edo. Elimelech (1976) and Egbókhare (1990) attest to this in Emai and Etsako respectively. Egbokhare (1990) even goes further to say that the meaning comes out clearly in verb phrase nominalization where objects are involved in the process. Some of his examples include:

54. i) ù # kpè # akòṅ → ùkpàkòṅ
 'wash' 'teeth' 'chewing stick'
- ii) ù # kpè # abò → ùkpàbò
 'wash' 'hand' 'bowl for washing hands'
- iii) ù # gbè # ɛɛwè → ùgbèwè
 'kill' 'goat' 'plague/disease that kills goats'

When this vowel prefix is attached to the verb stems in Edo (as we have in Emai above) the output will be derived a nominal with the meaning, 'an instrument used for performing an action'. Some of our examples are:

- 55 i) ù # ghèé # ɛɛdè → ù # ghèdè → ùghèdè
 nom prefix 'look at' 'day' 'sun glasses'
- ii) ù # gbé # èkún → ù gbékún → ùgbékún
 nom prefix 'tie' 'waist' 'belt'
- iii) ù # gbé # údyàn → ù # gbidyàn → ùgbidyàn
 nom prefix 'kill' 'tsetsefly' 'fly-whisk'

iii) i # wó # àkòṅ → i # wákòṅ → iwákòṅ
 'be strong' 'tooth' 'lit; being strong of teeth' 'avarice; greed'

4.3.7.4 Verbal Nouns

/é/ and /ò/ these prefixes can be said to express the result of the action, process or state expressed by the verb.

58 i) ò # mú # hén → ò # múhén → òmúhén
 'carry' 'begin' 'beginning'

ii) ò # lèé # gáá → ò # lègáá → òlègáá
 'run' 'round' 'a ring'

iii) è # zùrò → èzùrò
 'be stupid' 'stupidity'

vi) è # zàghàzàghà → èzàghàzàghà
 'scatter' 'scatter' 'disorderliness'

Despite the prevalence of noun prefixes in Edo and in many Edoid languages, it might be misleading to conclude that all initial vowels of nouns in Edo are prefixes. Welmers (1973:184); Elimelech (1978); Donwa (1982) and Elugbe (1989) have all observed that these initial vowels could be vestigial prefixes of a decadent noun class system.

4.3.8 Types of Nominalisation in Edo

Basically, there are three types of nominalisation that we identified in Edo. We identified them from the point of view of different tonal patterns that they bear. These are nominalisation with tone polarisation, nominalisation with an all-low tones patterns and the third group have no tonal changes.

4.3.8.1 Nominalization with All Low Tone Patterns

In this section, we will examine the structures with low tone patterns. As mentioned above, six oral vowels that take part in this process, are: i; ù; ò; è; é; à

The following undermentioned examples illustrate each of the vowel prefixes in Edo combining with stems involving diverse tonal patterns

59.a) Structures with prefix /i/

- i) i # wó # akò → i # wákò → iwákò
 'strong' 'tooth' 'lit. being strong of teeth' 'avarice; greed'
- ii) i # bò # ówá → i # bòwá → ibòwá
 'build' 'house' lit: the act of building a house "house-building"
- iii) i # hehèhè # ùnú → i # hénhènnú → ihénhènnú
 'level up' 'mouth' lit: levelling of mouth 'a consensus'
- iv) i # ré # òkò # ódè → i # ryókódè → iryókódè
 'eat' 'a parcel' 'way' lit: eating of a parcel on the way 'misappropriation of fund'

b) Structure with ù

- i) ù # gbé # ádiyè → ù # gbádiyè → ùgbádiyè
 'kill' 'chicken' lit: that which kills chicken "a fatal disease of chicken"
- ii) ù # gbé # ùdya → ù # gbidya → ùgbidya
 'kill' 'tsetsefly' 'fly-whisk'
- iii) ù # mú # òkhòkhò → ù # mwòkhòkhò → ùmwòkhòkhò
 'catch' 'chicken' 'tiger cat'
- iv) ù # ghèè # èdèc → ù # ghèdè → ùghèdè
 'look at' 'day' 'sun-glass'

c) Structure with prefix ò

- i) òò # gbé # èhén → ò # gbèhèn → òògbèhèn
 'pick' 'fish' 'fisherman'
- ii) òò # gbè # èbé → ò # gbèbè → ògbèbè
 'write' 'book' 'clerk'
- iii) òò # má # àkhé → ò # màkhè → òmàkhè
 'mould' 'clay pot' 'potter'

iv) oò # gwí # èzòn → ò # gwèzòn → ògwèzòn
 'quarrel' 'case' lit: one who argues a case, "litigant"

d) Structure with prefix /ò/

i) ò # ɣghághá → òghághá
 nom prefix 'brag, show off' "brag, boast, swaggering"

ii) ò # ɣghèḗ → òghè
 nom prefix 'fornicate' 'prostitution, adultery'

iii) ò # báǎḗ → òbáǎḗ
 nom prefix 'painful' 'pain, misery'

iv) ò # sòḗḗ → osòḗḗ
 nom prefix 'irritate' 'irritating sight'

4.3.8.2 Nominalization with LHL (H) Patterns

Under this section we will examine nominals with alternating tones i.e. LHL(H). In this case, the tones are polarised. These are also sub-divided into two. The first type is called gerundive nominals (cf. Elugbe 1989; Egbokhare 1990) while the second type of nominals are those that state actions or abstract nouns. In the case of the latter, four vowels (i, ò, à, ò) take part in these types of constructions, while in the former, it is only vowel ù that takes part in the constructions.

The following examples below illustrate each of the vowel prefixes in Edo combining with stems involving diverse tonal patterns.

60 a) Structure with prefix /i/

i) i # yáyí → iyáyí
 nom prefix 'to believe' 'belief'

ii) i # tótáá → itótá
 nom prefix 'sit' 'sitting'

iii) i # zòzò → izòzò
 nom prefix 'wander' 'wandering'

iv) i # yámá → iyámá
 nom prefix 'put a mark' 'an identification mark'

b) Structure with prefix /ú/

- i) ú # dé # fi # àgbòn → ú # défyàgbón → údéfyàgbón
'fall' 'throw' 'world' lit: one who drops into the world' "an orphan/one without relation"
- ii) ú # hiá # mwèn → ú # hámwèn → úhámwèn
'struggle' 'being' 'struggling' (coping with problems or difficulties)
- iii) ú # bó # mwèn → ú # bómwèn → úbómwèn
'predict' 'being' 'the act of predicting through the oracle'
- iv) ú # ṽghán → úghámwèn
nom prefix 'behave haughtily' 'being' 'arrogance; haughtiness'

d) Structure with prefix ò

- i) ò # fùrré → òfùré
nom prefix 'calm' lit: coolness; calmness; 'tranquillity'
- ii) òò # khòò → òkhòò
nom prefix 'evil' 'malicious act; evil deed'

e) Structure with prefix à

- i) à # hòó # bèkú → à # hòbèkún → àhòbèkún
'look' 'unsuccessful' 'state of being lost'
- ii) à # gbé # ètè → à # gbètè → àgbètè
'bring about' 'sore, ulcer' 'afflicted with one or more bodily ulcers'
- iii) à # fyàngbé → àfyàngbè
nom prefix 'bless' 'blessing'
- iv) à # gbé # àkpán → à # gbákpán → àgbákpán
'cause' 'bald head' 'a bald person'

4.3.8.3 Nominalization without any Tonal Change

In this case, we discover that there is neither tonal polarization nor the creation of all-low tones. What we notice is that all the elements that constitute the nominal still retain the tones they bear after collocation. Some of these examples are:

61. i) $\text{ɔ̀ɔ̀} \quad \# \quad \text{fùá} \longrightarrow \text{ɔ̀fùá}$
 nom prefix 'perish' 'destruction; annihilation'
- ii) $\text{ɔ̀ɔ̀} \quad \# \quad \text{khíé} \longrightarrow \text{ɔ̀khíé}$
 nom prefix 'mourn' 'mourner'
- iii) $\text{ɔ̀ɔ̀} \quad \# \quad \text{khòó} \longrightarrow \text{ɔ̀ɔ̀khòó}$
 nom prefix 'evil' 'evil'(n)
- iv) $\text{ò} \quad \# \quad \text{ròó} \longrightarrow \text{òròó}$
 nom prefix 'transgress' 'sin; wrongdoing'

In the analyses of these two different tonal patterns above, first, we discover that, when the nominalizing prefixes (which can be any of the six oral vowels) are collocated with the verb and noun stems, what we realize, from the available data, is that all the tones on the verb stems are realized as low tones. Thus, irrespective of the tones on the verb and noun stems before collocation, the outputs are always low tones. The first analysis, which one may be tempted to use is the low tone spreading rule arising from the low tone of the nominalizing prefixes. In this case, we will postulate low spreading to potentially indefinite H tones in the construction. But as good as this analysis is overtly, we may not be able to justify it because such rule will be too powerful, if we consider the fact that we have never had a situation where L tone have such a domineering behaviour in Edo or even in any Edoid languages. Another option is to postulate a rule that will replace all the high tones with low tones after vowel elision. If this is done, the outcome of all the collocations will then create all low nominals. We can equally postulate a grammatical floating low tone, which has been referred to as 'tomorph' by Elugbe (1985). This low tone will then link to other tones in the construction after vowel elision. The output will also give us all low tone nominals. We must say that any of the last two analyses can be adopted to give us the fact of the tone in Edo. However, we will adopt the latter option by postulating a grammatical floating low tone because of its simplicity. Semantically, it is

seen that most of the examples in this category (non-gerunds) signal agentive nouns. We must remark that these types of all low tones are not peculiar to Edo. Aziza (1997) noted that 'most nominals which signal agentive meaning are derived from verb + noun sequences and they bear only low tones. Although, Aziza (1997) did not tell us how she derived these all low tone patterns.

The second pattern is that in which after collocating the nominalizing prefix with the verb and noun stems what we have is LHL(H) tonal pattern. These, as mentioned earlier, are either gerundive or those nominals that state actions or abstract nouns. The former, according to Elugbe (1989) and Egbokhare (1990) are called gerundive nominalization. Gerundivisation is a process, which turns verbs into gerunds. It is marked by the polarization of tones on the syllable peaks in Edo as we have in examples 60 above. They are formed by the affixation of the discontinuous morpheme *ù...mwè* to a verb stem. What we observed here is that the initial tone of the verb takes a tone that is opposite the tone on the vowel prefix /*ù*/. therefore, we will postulate a polarisation rule for the tones in this category. We support Elugbe (1984:86), where he examines six Edoid languages, these are Degema, Uvbie, Isoko, Edo, Yekhee and Emhalhe. He concludes that 'the full morpheme was **ù...Amhi* in Proto Edoid'. Some of his examples include:

62. i) *gò* → *ùgómwè*
 'shout' → 'shouting'
- ii) *gbè* → *ùgbémwè*
 'beat' → 'beating'
- iii) *fù* → *ùfúmwè*
 'be calm' → 'be calm; calmness'
- iv) *mè* → *ùmémwè*
 'hiss' → 'hissing'

From the examples given above, it is seen that the tone of the verb stems take the tone that is polar opposite the tone of the nominal prefix *ù*. Elugbe (1984:87) raises the possibility of functionally separating the prefix from the suffix. According to him "since PE is assumed to have employed only prefixes to mark noun classes, the possibility that the class marking U-prefix was originally different from the suffix...Amhi cannot be

discarded. Thus, while Amhi was used after the verb stem to de-verbalise it, U was prefixed to the stems to mark it for a particular class". We agree with Elugbe (1984) in functionally separating the prefix and suffix. There are numerous examples where U-is prefixed to verb stems, and in such cases, this prefix identifies the result of the action or process of doing. Thus, the gerundiveness is the result of the suffixation of ... Amhi. The addition of U-follows the process of deverbalization, which requires that the resultant noun be allocated to a class. Egbokhare's (1990) account of Emai is closer to what Elugbe reported and which is confirmed by this study. In its case, it is marked by the affixation of a discontinuous morpheme /ú...ú/ as well as a high tone on the third syllable of a gerundive nominal. Some of his examples include:

63. i) /á/ 'run' [úlámi] 'running'
 ii) /ṵ/ 'drinking water' [úṵmi] 'drinking'
 iii) /è/ 'eat' [uémi] 'eating'
 iv) /fi/ 'throw' [úfimi] 'throwing'

From our observation, it is seen that the tonal patterns of the gerundive nominals in Emai are similar to the tonal patterns in Edo.

Our analyses of the second types of constructions that state action or abstract nouns will be somewhat similar to the analysis of gerundive nominals. We will equally postulate a polarisation rule. We will assume that it is the nominalising prefix that trigger off this polarisation.

Before rounding up this section, we have observed a few things from our analyses of nominalization in Edo. One, we note from the available data that it may not be possible to subject the same inputs to the two tonal changes. That is, the same nominalizing prefix and verb stem may not produce nominals that will have all low tones and a LHL(H) tonal patterns. Secondly, we also note that it is the process of nominalization that create these various tonal reflexes that we observed. This is because prior to nominalization, the tones on these different components are not as rhythmic as we have in the output after nominalization. i.e. LLL(L) or LHL(H). Even, when a fraction of them are collocated, each of the components have different tonal patterns on them. We therefore conclude that it is the process of nominalization that create the various tonal patterns that we have in

the language. The various tonal structures that these different types of nominalizations have are to the left side of arrows as seen in various examples in 46 to 60 above.

4.4 Loanwords In Edo

4.4.1 Introduction

We will focus our attention on the various strategies by which the Edo language absorbs loanword from source languages into its lexicon. Though the Edo language had contacts with many languages, i.e. Portuguese, English, Yorùbá, Hausa, Igbo, etc, we will restrict our discussions here to the contacts it has with both the English and Yorùbá languages. The reason for this is not far fetched. Yorùbá is a neighbouring language to Edo with considerable influence. English is the language of the colonial masters in the region. We will analyse and account for these various changes noticed in loanwords in a principled way.

Haugen (1992:75) defines borrowing as 'the attempted reproduction in one language of patterns previously found in another language. This definition, according to Ojò (1977:77), is particularly useful since it leaves open the question as to the manner of the reproduction, thereby making it possible to still define 'borrowing' more narrowly, if necessary. Borrowing, Haugen (1992:84) said later, is a general and traditional word used to describe the adoption into a language of a linguistic feature previously used in another. The metaphor implied can be misleading, since borrowing usually refers to temporary possession and repayment. However, linguistic loans are usually permanent, and of course do not imply a *quid pro quo*. Loans were mostly lexical items, which came to be known as loanwords. Haugen further said that loanwords, which came to denote borrowed lexical items, did not enter the English language until 1874 when A.H. Sayce used it in his *Principles of Comparative Philosophy*. The term itself was a loanword obviously modeled on the German 'Lehnunt'.

4.4.2 The Domains of Loanwords in Edo

This section is divided into two. We will discuss the various domains of Yorùbá loanwords in Edo. We will also look at the various changes that take place when Yorùbá

words are borrowed into Edo language. With this, we will attempt to contribute to on-going debate about the relationships between Edo and Yorùbá languages from the linguistic point of view.

We will also take a deeper look at the various English loanwords in Edo. Based on the available data, we will look at the various motivations for borrowing. We will also look at the various phonological and morphological changes that take place when words are borrowed into Edo language from English.

4.4.3 Domains of Yorùbá Loanwords in Edo

Although it is possible for a language to absorb words from another language from diverse domains, the data available to us show that Edo language absorbs many words relating to governance and leadership, traditional religion and belief system, from Yorùbá language.

One of the major reasons for this borrowing is the need to express something new in their language. Some of these words that were borrowed, are the names of things that are genuinely new to the speakers of Edo. There is, therefore, the need for their vocabulary to accommodate these concepts when there is no equivalent of such words in the matrix language.

The data also reveal that words relating to governance, leadership and human interaction were borrowed from Yorùbá. Some of these include:

		Yorùbá	Edo	English
64	i	ọba	óbá ²	king
	ii.	alága	ólágá	the chairperson
	iii.	olópàá	ólákpá	policeman
	iv.	eléwọn	óléghọn	prisoner
	v.	olori	ólói	wife of the ọba
	vi.	olóótú	ólótù	group leader
	vii.	isòtè	isòtè	rebellion
	viii	adé	edé	crown
	xi	àbá	àbàn	native hand-cuff

x	akòwé	ákòwé	clerk
xi	iyi	úyi	honor, prestige
xii	agada	àgàdà	a two edge sword used mainly by butchers

We also have words relating to traditional religions and the belief systems of Yorùbá, which Edo borrowed. Some of these are:

65.	Yorùbá	Edo	English
i.	sàngó	isàngó	the god of thunder
ii.	olókun	ólólkùn	goddess of the sea
iii.	orò	órò	secret practices
iv.	égbà	égbà	armlet
v.	ayé	áyé	world
vi.	àwẹ	àwẹ	a fast
vii.	omi òkun	àmólókùn	sea water
viii.	ògbóni	ògbóni	the name of a secret society
ix.	òkun	ókùn	sea
x.	èewò	àwùà	taboo
xi.	ájé	àzén	witch
xii.	ẹti	ẹti	obstruction; confusion
xiii.	osó	ósó	wizard; sorcerer
xiv.	òrúnmilá	oronmila	diviner

4.4.4 Morphophonological Modification

As can be seen from the examples above, words borrowed from one language into another are at times altered to conform to the morphophonological canons of the borrowing language, in a way that ranges from changes in individual segments to more global deformation of structure (although, we shall see later that there might not be any changes at all after borrowing).

Edo and Yorùbá languages belong to the same language group. They are a putative Western Benue-Congo arm of NBC (Williamson and Blench 2000:103).

However, while Edo belongs to the Edoid sub-group, Yorùbá belongs to the Defoid sub-group. With this familiarity, the two languages have many linguistic commonalities. The phonological nativisation of Yorùbá words with Edo is not as complex as we have in other unrelated languages such as English, Portuguese, etc. The two languages (i.e. Edo and Yorùbá) have almost the same syllable structures, where we have (V)CV. The V- element is usually an obligatory constituent of the syllable. The Edo language is even stricter, while Yorùbá permits a few of these nouns (the loan words) with consonant initials, Edo does not. This is why prothesis occurs in some of the words (as can be seen in the examples below). This insertion is motivated, strictly by morpheme structure considerations. The three types of vowels that can be inserted at word initial positions are [i, e, and a]. The type of vowel to be inserted depends, to a large extent, on the heights of the final vowel of the borrowed words. In some cases too, it might agree in roundness of the lip with the final vowels of the borrowed words. Examples below illustrate this:

66.	Yorùbá	Edo	English
i.	Dàdà	Ídádá	'frizzed hair person'
ii.	Gẹ̀dú	Ígẹ̀dú	timber
iii.	Giripá	Ágikpá	full grown male
iv.	Tòbí	itòbí	women underwear
v.	Tata	átéété	grasshopper
vi.	Sàngó	Ísàngó	god of thunder.

The language even moves a step further to delete the initial consonant of a borrowed word in an attempt to conform strictly to its syllable structure. This is the case with *pásán* in Yorùbá, which changes to *ásán*, 'cane usually used for beating people or animal'. Because of the similarities of the two syllable structures, we did not observe any major internal restructuring in the form of vowel insertion.

Yorùbá has a type of restriction on the types of vowels that can co-occur within a word with V-CV structure (cf. Owólabí 1989, Adéniyi 2000). However, the reverse is the case in Edo. The vowels of Edo do not follow a particular pattern in its occurrences. This explains why when Yorùbá words are borrowed into Edo, the vowels co-occur freely. Some of these examples are as we have in 64 ii-iv, viii above.

We also noticed that there are some words that were borrowed into Edo language without any modification whatsoever. All the segmental and suprasegmental features that they have in Yorùbá are still intact in Edo. This, however, contradicts claims by some earlier writers on Loanwords (cf. Tiav 1994, etc.) that when words are borrowed from another language, it must undergo morphological changes. We submit here that some words are just borrowed into the language without any modification whatsoever.

Some of these words include:

67.	Yorùbá	Edo	English
i.	Àgò	àgò	camp
ii.	àgàn	àgàn	barren woman
iii.	àgbò	àgbò	ram
iv.	igò	igò	bottle
v.	isòtè	isòtè	rebellion

Another striking feature of Yorùbá borrowed words in Edo is that some derived nominals were borrowed either with minimal or even without any modifications. Some of these include:

68. *Alága* in Yorùbá is derived from *oní* 'owner of', *àgá* 'chair'. This derivation can be given as follows:

This is however borrowed into Edo as *ólágá* 'the chairperson'. We mentioned above that there is no restriction on the type of vowel that can occur within a V-CV structure, hence the occurrence of a back round mid-low vowel with a low front vowel i.e. *o* and *a* as in the case of *olága* above. We also have other examples such as *ólópàá* (*oní*+*òpá*) lit. owner of rod 'policeman' which is derived from *oní* 'owner of' *òpá* 'rod' and which is borrowed into Edo as *ólá!kpá*. Also, *elèwòn* (*oní*+*èwòn*) derived from *oní* 'owner of'

ḡwọ̀n 'prison/chain' lit. owner of prison/chain 'prisoner', and borrowed into Edo as *óléghọ̀n*. *Onígbẹ̀gbẹ̀* (oní+ gbẹ̀gbẹ̀), lit. owner of goitre 'someone with a goitre' borrowed into Edo as *ólígbẹ̀!gbẹ̀*. In this case, there is no alternation between the nasal 'n' and the lateral 'l' in Edo as we have in Yorùbá language. We also have *Isọ̀tẹ̀* (i + .se + ọ̀tẹ̀) 'to be rebellious' and borrowed just as *Isọ̀tẹ̀* without any change whatsoever. We also have *akọ̀wé* (a+ kọ̀+ iwé) lit. writer of book 'clerk', and borrowed into Edo as *ákọ̀wé*. The point we are trying to make from the examples above is that the meaning of the component parts of the above derived nominals in Yorùbá do not tally with what we have in Edo. Both the verbs and nouns that constitute the nominals in Yorùbá and Edo have different meanings. Some of these include:

69.	Yorùbá	Edo	English
i.	ọ̀pà	úkpókpo	rod
ii.	ẹ̀wọ̀n	imú	prison
iii.	ọ̀tẹ̀	òwóbhúómón	rebellion/treachery
iv.	iwé	ẹ̀bé	book
v.	gbẹ̀gbẹ̀	ókpóghurù	goitre
vi.	oní	nọ̀yánrén	owner of
vii.	kọ̀	gbén	write
viii.	se	rú	do

4.4.5 Probable Relations between Ifẹ̀ and Benin

Apart from the fact that borrowing gives the opportunity for languages to acquire new words, Crystal (1978) identified a few other reasons that can motivate borrowing in any language. Some of these are religion, culture, economy, and natural disaster. However, Trask (1996:19) identified prestige as an important factor, which in our view, is very germane to this discussion. It constitutes a major factor why languages borrow. People borrow to indicate to the entire world, including colleagues and acquaintances, one's familiarity with the language. Trask (1996:409) went further to say that 'prestige seems to be the most important factor deciding what type of vocabulary will be

borrowed. Since the desire is to 'copy' the speakers of a language, the borrowers assume that the language is superior in whatever form.

With this in mind, it is our view that borrowing of lexical items will occur from most all areas of human endeavors. In most cases too, those who borrow for prestige reasons need not do so because the words they are borrowing are new to their lexicon. There are instances where the borrowers already have appropriate words for such lexical items, but because they want to associate with the speakers of a prestigious language, they borrow new words to replace the ones they already have. With this attitude, majority of the old words might not survive the onslaught of the more prestigious language. Trask (1996:385) gave an illustration of the Norman French in 1066 after conquering the English. He said that the same prestigious influence of the French speaking court and its dominance in warfare and in administration of justice is responsible for the following borrowings:

70. Borrowed from French	Native term(English)
i. royal	king (kingly) queen
ii. arms	weapons
iii. Justice	law
iv. court	(yard)

It seems from the examples above that some of the native terms survive the onslaught of the French language(which was the more prestigious language then), although some other words are not as lucky as those mentioned above.

It is from the above point of view that we will take a look at the various Yorùbá loanwords in Edo with a view to contributing to a vexious issue on the relationship between Ifẹ (Yorùbá) and Benin (Edo).

Scholars as well as eminent personalities on both sides are sharply divided as to the actual status of Odùduwà and Ọ̀rànmiyàn within the history of Edo. One camp believes that Odùduwà was actually Ekeladerhan, an escapee Benin prince who went to Ifẹ to establish the Ifẹ dynasty. He however, refused to return to Benin later, instead he sent his son, Ọ̀rànmiyàn on a 'homecoming' mission to establish the present Benin dynasty. The other group is of the veiw that Odùduwà was the projenitor of the Yorùbá

and the king of Ifè who volunteered his son, Òrànmiyàn to the Benin people when they desperately needed a king to rule over them.

Given the Edo account, Ekeladehan was to have been killed because of certain offences he was alleged to have committed while he was in Benin. His supposed executioners left him off the hook and he went on asylum to Ilé-ifè. Our assumption here is that he was recalled from Ifè based on the fact that Benin had no choice at that particular point in time. (There was no king in Benin at that time.) It is therefore concluded that it was not out of joy that Òrànmiyàn was welcome back home because of the circumstances mentioned above.

Judging from the above, it might not have been possible for people to borrow some of the Yorùbá words he 'brought' from Ifè. This is because, people would not have seen him as an hero based on the circumstances that led to his recall from Ifè. But just because they did not have any choice at that particular point in time, they might then be left with no choice rather than to accept him. Even if people were forced to accept him because of the enormous power Òrànmiyàn was said to have possessed at that particular point in time, it is expected that the people would have jettisoned those words they copied from the king and his entourage after his exit from Benin and those words and phrases would have gone into extinction by now.

On the other hand, the second account to our mind, looks more plausible. According to their analysis, because of the problems in Benin at that time, the oracle commanded them that there cannot be peace in the land except they bring a king from Ifè. This, they did, and peace and tranquility returned to the land. With this in mind, there is every tendency for the Benin people to see Òrànmiyàn as a saviour and God-sent at that time, who liberated them from the unseen and unknown pestilence. We also assumed that when Òrànmiyàn got to Benin, he was given a rousing welcome. Since he did not speak Edo language, he spoke Yorùbá, his language. In an attempt to be associated with the Oba, and the palace, our assumption here is that the Edo people started picking words from the Oba's language. Based on our discussion that prestige is a major reason for borrowing, we assumed that it was socially prestigious and fashionable to use Yorùbá words and expressions then. We also suspect that speaking the language then was like identifying oneself with the ruling class and associating with the palace. Moreso it was

reported that up till 1934, the official language of the palace of Benin was Yorùbá (Akinolá 1976)

Another evidence in support of the above argument is in the various names currently borne by the Edo people. Such names include, but are not limited to Folorunsho, Ògèdègbè, Obásuyi, Alóngé, Ozo(Òjò), Azayi(Ajayi). These are Yorùbá names, both in structure and in meaning. Some of them have, however, undergone one modification or another. But the fact still remains that they are Yorùbá names derived from nominalization. Talbot(1926) quoted by Akinolá (1976), was reported to have said that a retinue of advisers and courtiers followed Òrànmiyàn to Benin. Talbot was quoted as saying that:

According to tradition the first king of the country was Igudu... A Yorùbá chief named Erhe, stated to be the Awgenni of Ufe (in Yorùbá Awni of Ife) arrived with **small following**, but did not gain much power. His son Ogiso also made little headway and returned to Ife... c1300. The Awni of Ife sent another son called Orhamiyan, accompanied by a **large following** (emphasis mine). He lived at Use for three years before returned to Ife...

Based on the reports by Talbot above, it is our view in this work that some of the names were borne by the contingents who followed, first, Awgenni of Ife, and then Òrànmiyàn to Benin.

Some of the above names can be decomposed into morphemes as shown below:

71. i. Fólórunshò → mo fun Olórun só.
I give God watch
"I gave God (this child) to watch for me"
- ii. Omóruyi → omò re uyi
Child is honour
"Children are prestige"
- iii. Obásuyi → obá se uyi
King is honour
"It is prestigious to become the king."
- iv. Òzó → (Òjò in Yorùbá) name of a child...
- v. Àzàyi → (Àjàyi in Yorùbá) name of a child

Some of the examples of Edo names above follow the Yorùbá patterns of naming. Before we conclude, we shall take a look at some other arguments advanced in some quarters as to why Yorùbá words found their ways into Edo vocabulary.

There is an argument that Yorùbá words crept into Edo language through military conquests of Àkúrẹ̀, Òwò and Lagos by the Edo warriors some centuries ago. While we agree that these conquests were facts of life, the Yorùbá now as it is spoken is an aggregate of all the dialects of Yorùbá, (with over 30 of them) lexico-statistic analysis of Yorùbá words (Akinkugbe 1978) show that these three dialects (Àkúrẹ̀, Òwò and Èkó) constitute less than five percents of the entire lexicon of Yorùbá.

Another view, not too distant from the above is that since it is the same 'master' that conquered the two groups (i.e the British), that it was during these period of conquest by the British that the Edo people assimilated many of the Yorùbá words as we have today. This view, to us, would also seem untenable because it will be illogical for one 'servant' to assimilate features from the other's language as extensively as we have in the case of Yorùbá and Edo now. What has always happened is that the two 'servants' acquire the features of the language of the master, as we have in the case from English to Edo and Yorùbá.

Another argument is that Edo might have assimilated these Yorùbá words during the period of the Western region when they were all together under the same head. To us, this is not justifiable as it is a known fact that these words predate Western Region era (which was just about 50 years ago). As earlier mentioned, Yorùbá was the language of the palace of the Oba of Benin till 1934).

We have attempted in this section to look at Yorùbá loanwords in Edo with a view to contributing to on-going debate on the actual relationship between Yorùbá and Edo language. It is our view in this work that the relationship between Yorùbá and Edo goes beyond what was claimed by the view that Odùduwà was actually Ekeladerhan. In this work, we discussed borrowing in languages, various domains of Yorùbá loanwords in Edo, the various morphophonological modifications that we noticed in the borrowed words. It is our opinion in this work that it was Odùduwà as the progenitor of the Yorùbá

race, who sent his son, *Oránmíyàn* to Benin to bail them out of the predicament they had at that particular point in time.

We will note here also that in the course of carrying out this study, we discovered that though the direction of the loanwords are unidirectional, less of these words were borrowed from Edo to Yorùbá. The words that were borrowed from Edo to Yorùbá were quite insignificant. Some of these include:

72. a. *Èkó* (another name for Lagos) 'which means a war camp in Edo'
- b. *Ìgbèdè* 'the name of a village near Lagos, meaning blacksmith's workshop'

4.4.6 Domain of English Loanwords in Edo

The fact that Edo borrowed more words from English than any other language should not come to us as a surprise. English is the language of our colonial masters in Nigeria. The English language therefore infiltrated all aspects of our lives including Edo speakers. Words borrowed from English to Edo include those relating to religion, social activities, education, kitchen utensils and day to day life. We can conclude here that there is no area of human endeavour that Edo has no English loanwords.

By colonising Nigeria (Edo people inclusive), the English brought with them their religion and its various practices. The missionaries were the active agents of the spreading of Christianity to the different parts of Edo land. English language serve as the language of wider communication. Part of the goals of the missionaries then was to evangelize, teach and enlighten the people in the 'ways of the Lord'. This brought about English loanwords to refer to new items or ideas that were associated with religion. Examples of some of these words are shown below:

73.	English	Edo
i)	Apostle	ápósù
ii)	Bishop	èbisóbù
iii)	Bible	èbáibù
iv)	Mass	èmási
v)	Catholic	ékátólikì
vi)	Cathedral	ékátidíyá
vii)	Methodist	èmétódìsì

viii)	Seraphim	èsérafí
ix)	Mission	émisíon

Words relating to commerce and economy were also borrowed from English to Edo. From available data, some of these include:

74.	English	Edo
i)	Bank	ébáńki
ii)	Brocade	ébiókédi
iii)	A penny	épini
iv)	Insurance	isóráńsi
v)	Hotel	éhòté
vi)	Passbook	épásibùkù
vii)	Receipt	èrisiti
viii)	Account	ákáúnti
ix)	Cheque	èséki

We also have words relating to farming and agriculture borrowed from English.

Some of these include:

75.	English	Edo
i)	Agriculture	àgirikósò
ii)	Bread fruit	èbléfiúútù
iii)	Flour/flower	ifiáwà
iv)	Gardner	égádiná
v)	Cashew	ékású
vi)	Cocoyam	èkòkóyàmù
vii)	Mango	èmángò

Other words borrowed into Edo language include food items, kitchen utensils, etc.

76.	English	Edo
i)	Butter	ébótà
ii)	Bread	ébiédi
iii)	Kettle	èkétò
iv)	Kitchen	èkisini

v)	Spoon	èsùpùnú
vi)	Milk	ènúlikì
vii)	Sugar	èsúgá
viii)	Pot	èpótù
ix)	Rice	èràisi
x)	Semovita	èsémóvitá

Apart from nouns, Edo also borrows verbs from English. These verbs occur frequently in the day-to-day activities of the Edo people. Some of these include:

77.	English	Edo
i)	to safe	èséfi
ii)	to survey	èsófè
iii)	to repair	èpé
iv)	to renew	èriníù
v)	to rig	èrígì
vi)	to reverse	èrivási
vii)	to measure	émézò
viii)	to lease	èlìsì
ix)	to gauge	ègéjì
x)	to charter	èsátà
xi)	to fail	èfééli
xii)	to deliver	èdilivá

In the area of governance, administration of justice etc, Edo borrowed a lot of words. Some of these include:

78.	English	Edo
i)	The accused	àkiúzi
ii)	Appeal	àpiill
iii)	Bullet	èbúlétì
iv)	Democractic	èdémókíátìkì
v)	Double barrel	èdòbùbàrè
vi)	Governor	ègòviná

vii)	Councillor	èkànséìṣ
viii)	Court	èkòtù
ix)	Commissioner	èkòmíṣòṇà
x)	Law	èlò
xi)	Soilder	èsójà
xii)	Magistrate	émàgíṣètì
xiii)	Politics	èpòlìtìsì

4.4.7 Morphophonological Analysis of English Loanwords in Edo.

The linguistic structures of different languages may diverge considerably, necessitating in most cases, at least some adjustments of loanwords to the native structure of the recipient language. These adjustments will therefore allow them to conform to the sound patterns of the 'host' language. These adjustments may be phonological, morphological, semantical or lexical. After the adjustments, it will then conform to the syllable structures of the matrix language.

The phonological system of Edo language is considerably different from that of English. Because of this, when a word is borrowed from English, there are a number of morphophonological changes that have to take place. We shall discuss these processes in our subsequent sections.

Edo syllable structure permits no consonant clusters at the underlying level, while at the surface structure, double consonants exist. English permits clusters of up to three consonants both at deep and surface structure. Also, Edo does not permit consonants in final position, whereas, English does. Edo makes it obligatory for all non-verbal categories to begin with a vowel. In English, however, this need not be. Edo is basically a tone language, whereas stress plays prominent roles in English phonology. The above mentioned changes and many more take place when words are borrowed into Edo language. These processes shall therefore be our focus in subsequent sections.

4.4.7.1 Vowel Substitution

In this section, we shall examine how English phonemes are realized in Edo language. Our goal here is not intended to undertake a detailed comparative analysis of the sounds of English and Edo, but to merely set up correspondences, which English phonemes are usually represented by which Edo phonemes:

Under vowel system, English language has twelve pure vowels, five closing diphthongs and four centring diphthongs. On the other hand, Edo has seven oral vowels and five nasal vowels.

The examples that follow show the correspondence between English vowels and those substituted by the Edo speakers.

	English	Edo
i)	film	éfiimù
ii)	key	éki
iii)	chiorister	èkórisà
iv)	obituary	òbitúári
v)	native	enétívi
vi)	austerity	òséríti

80. English /ɛ/ → Edo /ɛ/

i)	belt	èbèliti
ii)	letter	èlétà
iii)	hotel	èhótèli
iv)	television	ètèliviṣòn
v)	cement	èsimétì
vi)	verb	èvèbù

81.

	English	Edo
i)	bag	ébági
ii)	bat	ébáti
iii)	barber	ébábá
iv)	gardner	égádinà
v)	camphor	ékánfò
vi)	calendar	ékálédà

82.

	English	Edo
i)	force	éfòsi
ii)	company	èkònpínni
iii)	cup	èkópù
iv)	gutter	ègótá
v)	gum	ègòtímù

83.

	English	Edo
i)	glue	égúlò
ii)	spoon	ésúpúnnù
iii)	ruler	érulá
iv)	blue	ibúrù

84

i)	clippers	èkilipàsi
ii)	corner	ékòná
iii)	commissioner	èkòmíṣòná
iv)	jiggar	àzigán
v)	hour	áwà
vi)	machine	émásini
vii)	doctor	èdókitá

Diphthongs

The Edo language does not have any diphthongs in its inventory. When words are borrowed into Edo, two things are likely to happen, the diphthongs either come out as a single sound, usually the first, (if we consider English diphthongs as biphonemic, or as a

sequence of two vowels, corresponding to usual realization of these vowels when they occur alone.

85. English /e/ → Edo /e/
- i) crayon èkiréyónnú
 - ii) radio èrèdiò
 - iii) brake èbirééki

	English	Edo
i)	bicycle	èbáisikò
ii)	wire	èwáyà
iii)	plier	èpiláyà
iv)	nylon	èláini
v)	license	èláisènsi

87. English /au/ → Edo /a/
- i) vowel èváwẹ(li)
 - ii) tower ètáwá

88. English /oi/ → Edo /oi/
- i) boy iboi
 - ii) boiler èbùélà

89. English /ou/ → Yoruba /o/
- coat èkótù

4.4.7.2 Centring diphthongs

90.	i.	English /iə/	→	Edo /i/
		Nigeria		ènégiriyà
	ii.	English /ɔə/	→	Edo /ɔ/
		court		ékótù
		floor		èfilò
	iii.	English /eɔ/	→	Edo /e/
		area		èrià
	iv.	Eng /uə/	→	Edo /ɔɔ/
		tour		étò

4.4.8. Vowel insertion

Vowel insertion takes place in three positions in Edo. These are morpheme initial, medial and final. Vowel insertion in the language is strictly motivated by the asymmetry between the morpheme and the syllable structures of Edo and English. Vowel insertion occur to rectify unacceptable syllable structures presented by loan words. The morpheme structure of Edo makes it obligatory for all non-verbal categories to begin with a vowel; whereas in English, this is optional.

Most common vowels that can be inserted at the word initial positions in Edo are 'e' and 'i', (there is however an exception where a is inserted i.e jiggàr → àzigán) while vowels 'a', 'o', 'u' and 'ɔ' appear to be the common vowels that can be inserted intervocalically. Whereas, any of the oral vowels can be inserted at word final positions. We must however note that the occurrence of vowels 'e' and 'i' are predictable. Loanwords beginning with high tone vowels have the vowel 'i' inserted at the beginning of words whereas, words beginning with low tone vowels have vowel 'e' inserted.

4.4.8.1 The Inserted Vowel

As observed in Emai by Egbohare (1990), [u] occurs also as the epenthetic vowel after labial consonants in Edo, it also occurs after other consonants if a rounded vowel occurs in an adjacent syllable. [i] occurs as the epenthetic vowel in non-labial environments. Egbohare further observed that a similar situation is observed in Yoruba Awobuluyi (1967; 1978), Pulleyblank (1988). He said that Pulleyblank accounts for the phenomenon in Yoruba in terms of the application of redundancy rules and labial harmony rule. Redundancy rules account for the occurrence of / i / being the underspecified vowel while labial harmony ensures that / i / becomes / u / in labial context. According to Pulleyblank, "since consonants can only occur in onset position, any unsyllabified consonant must be assigned a rhyme. And since there would be no motivation for any particular vowel quality to be present on that rhyme, the unmarked expectation will be for redundancy rules to fill in feature values for such an epenthetic vowel". He illustrates epenthesis in Yoruba as involving the following: (Pulleyblank)

figure 8

Pulleyblank provided strong motivations for recognizing / i / as supplied by redundancy rules in Yoruba. However in Edo, (just as Egbokhare (1990) noticed in Emai), we cannot find any compelling phonological evidence to accept such analyses. We will nonetheless, agree with Pulleyblank that "a vowel whose sole rationale for existence is considerations of syllable structure ought to exhibit no feature specifications other than those supplied redundantly". With the above quotation, we hold that vowel insertion in Edo has the three layers in figure 8 above. We will therefore postulate / i / as the epenthetic vowel in Edo. Vowel / u / in a labial environment because of the application of the labial harmony rule which spreads the labial feature of a tautosyllabic consonant or a vowel occurring in an adjacent syllable on the inserted vowel. (/i /). Egbokhare (1990) gives an accurate picture of the insertion process in Emai which fits squarely into Edo. This is captured by the derivation below:

91.ə → i → u / +labial
 by insertion by labial harmony

He illustrates the labial harmony process which can be captured schematically in the figure below:

Figure 9

The above structures are two fused into one. The upper part shows the process applying progressively while the lower part shows it applying regressively.

4.4.9 Consonants

Except for those Edo consonants that are similar to those ones in English, English consonants are usually substituted with their equivalents or nearest equivalent in Edo language. Consonant phoneme inventory of Edo is a bit restricted than that of English, just as we have with the vowel phoneme inventory. Another point to note in the assimilation of English consonant in Edo is the treatment of consonant clusters, a striking feature that cannot be found in Edo language. Similar to that is the treatment of consonant in word final position; i.e. closed syllable. As mentioned earlier, all Edo syllables are of the open kind. Let us see how the individual English consonants are realised in the Edo language.

In the case of plosives there are no strikingly differences in their realizations from English to Edo language. Some of these examples include;

92. English	Edo
i. Appeal	ápiili
ii. Bishop	ébisóbù
iii. Kettle	ékètò
iv. Gardner	égádínà
v. Hospital	ásikitù
vi. Butter	ébòtá

However, in the case of affricates, there is simplification of some of the consonants. For instance, there is the simplification of palato-alveolar consonants to either velar or alveolar consonants, i.e. /tʃ/ → /g/ or /k/ or /s/, as in the following examples below:

93. i. Eng	/tʃ/	→	Edo	/g/	bench	ébéngi
				/k/	chancellor	ékánsélò
				/s/	to charter	ésátà
					challenge	èsáléngi
					cheque	èsèki

We also have cases of some dental fricative and palato-alveolar sounds that are substituted for alveolar consonants. Some of these examples include:

- | | | | | | | | |
|------|-----|-----|---|-----|-----|-----------|-----------|
| ii. | Eng | /ð/ | → | Edo | /d/ | brother | èbíòdá |
| | | | | | | father | èfádá |
| | | | | | | mother | émòdá |
| iii. | Eng | /θ/ | → | Edo | /t/ | Catholic | èkátólikí |
| | | | | | | Cathedral | èkátídýà |
| iv. | Eng | /ʃ/ | → | Edo | /s/ | shampoo | èsánpú |
| | | | | | | shepherd | èsépádè |
| | | | | | | fashion | èfásóní |
| v. | Eng | /ʒ/ | → | Edo | /z/ | measure | èmézò |
| | | | | | /s/ | mission | èmíson |

Glottal fricatives sounds are also deleted when words involving these sounds are borrowed in to Edo language as in the examples below.

- | | | | | | | | |
|-----|-----|-----|---|-----|-----|-----------|---------|
| vi. | Eng | /h/ | → | Edo | /ø/ | holiday | ólidé |
| | | | | | | hospital | ásúkitù |
| | | | | | | honorable | ónórèbù |

Voiced alveolar fricatives are also substitute for voiceless alveolar fricatives as shown below

- | | | | | | | | |
|------|------|-----|---|-----|-----|-----|-------|
| vii. | Eng. | /z/ | → | Edo | /s/ | zip | ésipi |
|------|------|-----|---|-----|-----|-----|-------|

When words involving consonant clusters are borrowed into the language, two things happen, it is either we have one of the consonants deleted or a vowel is inserted between these consonants. Some of these examples are as seen in:

- | | | | |
|----|----|--------|---------|
| 94 | a. | appeal | àpiilli |
| | b. | kettle | èkétò |

In conclusion, there are no striking examples of loanwords in other lexical categories like adjectives, adverbs prepositions etc. We will therefore agree with Appel Rene et al (1987) that the commonest thing about loanwords in most language is that they are usually nouns (and in the case of English loanwords in Edo, verbs) since these words name and describe certain items that are not propably part of the cultural experience of the people.

4.5 Reduplication

Sapir (1921:76) observed that "nothing is more natural than the prevalence of reduplication, in other words, the repetition of all or parts of the radical elements. The process is generally employed, with self-evident symbolism, to indicate such concepts as distribution, plurality, repetition, customary activity, increase in size, added intensity, continuance...". He noted further that in English, reduplication is not altogether unknown. He pointed to examples like these:

95.	pooh -	pooh	goody -	goody	brain-drain
	sing -	song	poly -	poly	
	harum -	scarum	wishy -	washy	

Banner (1988) defines reduplication as a special way of making affixes, or a way of creating a special kind of compound, which may act differently from other affixes or compounds in a given language (McCarthy 1981, Marantz, 1982). Awóyalé (1989:16) is of the view that reduplication is a morphological process whereby a copy of morpheme (free or bound) in either slightly altered or identical form, is added to the form in a syntagmatic relationship to produce a new word. Ogunkéyè (2002) in her own account says reduplication involves using some part (a partial reduplication) of the base, or the entire base (a total reduplication), more than once in a word in order to express a morphological category. Reduplicated constructions may differ in:

96. a) the type of unit that is reduplicated
- a) the number of times it is reiterated
 - b) whether the copies are exactly or partially alike.
 - c) The position within the syntagm where the reduplicated elements occur – initially, medially or finally.

Another feature of reduplication is that it can take place to the left of the root, as a prefix, to the right, as a suffix, or inside the root as an infix. The material reduplicated can be a word, a whole morpheme, a syllable, or a sequence of syllables, or simply a string of consonants and vowels which doesn't form any particular prosodic constituents. (i.e. syllable, foot, morpheme etc).

Scholars working on reduplication have two divergent views about reduplication. The first view are those working within a linear phonology framework. They are of the view that reduplications are handled by means of (a set) of transformation rules which automatically have the effect of copying a string from the root to the left, to the right, or in the middle of the root. Those who hold this view are Carrier (1979), Lieber 1980 and Aronoff (1976). In the second group are those who, based on the weakness of the earlier claims, came out with a modified version.. Marantz (1982) leads this group. He sees reduplication as:

a process relating a base form of a morpheme or stem to a derived form that may be analysed as being constructed from the base via affixation of phonemic material which is necessarily identical in whole or in part to the phonemic content of the base form.

Marantz's argument above is that reduplication is essentially affixation but that what is affixed is a CV skeleton or a prosodic template. The phonemic content of the reduplicative affix is then obtained by copying the complete phoneme melody of the root and linking it to the affixal CV template respecting the principles of association familiar from autosegmental phonology. Taking the first set of examples from Agta, Marantz proposes the derivation below:

Agta Reduplication taktakki 'legs' (Marantz, 1984)

2.

Figure 10

Marantz imposes four conditions on the linking of melody tier to prosodic template. These are paraphrased below: (Spencer 1991:152)

Condition A: Melody consonants link to C slots and melody vowels link to V slots.

Condition B: Linking is strictly one-to-one; no multiple links are allowed.

Condition C: CV slots may be prelinked to specific phonemes, prelinking take precedence over autosegmental linking from root melody.

Condition D: Directionality of linking; either the left-most melody phoneme links with the left-most appropriate C - V slot and linking proceeds from left to right; or the right-most melody phoneme links with the right-most appropriate C - V slot and linking proceeds right-to-left. It is unmarked case, linking proceeds towards the roots, that is, left-to-right for prefixes, right-to-left for suffixes.

ii) Linking is 'melody driven' in the sense that the association algorithm starts with a melody phoneme and then tries to find an appropriate CV slot, not the other way around.

Reduplications abound in languages. However we observe full and partial reduplications in Edo. Under this section, we shall discuss the following in relation to their reduplications: verb, adjective, adverbs, noun, numeral and full reduplication with an interfix. Partial reduplication are only found in ideophone. We will therefore discuss it in the section dealing with ideophone.

97.

	Verb	Total
i.	piên → 'to press against'	piênpiên 'same as pien'
ii.	sùnnó → 'to be slow'	sùnnòsùnnò 'describes slow lifeless gait'
iii.	bà → 'to watch'	bàbà 'reiterative sense of bà'
iv.	ká → 'to dry, to be crisp'	káká 'to become dry, 'to be dehydrated'
v.	dé → 'to fall'	dédé 'plural or reiterative sense of dé'
vi.	guá → 'to adultrate'	guáguá 'to admix'

98.

	Adjective	Total
i.	bètè → 'fat; stocky'	bètèbètè 'sense of bètè'
ii.	bigò → 'to be crooked'	bigobigò 'very crooked'
iii.	gèlè → 'really; indeed actually'	gèlègèlè 'infact; in truth'
iv.	khérhé → 'small; little'	khérhékhérhé 'very small; tiny'
v.	mòsé → 'to be beautiful'	mòsèmòsé 'beautifully'
vi.	règhé → 'describes sth very high'	règhérèghé 'very high; far beyond reach'
vii.	sònó → 'soft; tender, immature'	sònòsònò 'describes sth soft; tender & delicate'

99.

Verb**Adjective**

- i. gòlò → gòlògòlò
'to walk gracefully' 'describes a manner of walking'
- ii. khìrhí → khìrhìkhìrhí
'to do hurriedly' 'in a hurry; hurriedly'
- iii. làghá → làghàlàghá
'to dangle; 'to hang' 'describes sth. that is dangling'
- iv. lòghó → lòghólòghó
'to dangle' cf. of làghàghàgbà
- v. mítán → mítánmítán
'to be lazy' 'lazy; weak; wretched'

100.

Adverb**Total (plural)**

- i. ùsẹn → ùsún!sẹn
'a period of five days' 'every five days'
- ii. òtá → òtótá
'evening' 'every evening'
- iii. ẹsọ → ẹsésò
'some' 'many'
- iv. ẹsì → ẹsyé!sì
'good' 'excellent'
- v. ẹsé → ẹsé!sè
'well; properly' 'very well, 'very much'

101

Noun**Plurality**

- i. òwá → òwólwá
'house' 'houses'
- ii. ẹdẹ → ẹdẹ!dẹ
'day' 'days'
- iii. axe → àxé!xè
'pot' 'pots'
- iv. àsọn → àsán!sọn
'breast'(female) 'breasts'

- v. èkì 'market' → èkyélkì 'markets'
- vi. àkòṅ 'tooth' → àkòṅkòṅ 'teeth'
- vii. ètẹ 'sore/ulcer' → ètẹtẹ 'sores'

102. Numerals (Distributive)
- i. èhá 'three' → èché!há 'in group of three'
 - ii. èné 'four' → èné!né 'in group of four'
 - iii. èhàn 'six' → èhen!hàn 'in group of six'
 - iv. ìhìròṅ 'seven' → ìhìrìnhìròṅ 'in group of seven'
 - v. ógbàn 'thirty' → ógbòṅ!gbàn 'in group of thirty'
 - vi. iyéwá 'forty' → iyéwí!yéwá 'in group of forty'
 - vii. iyéhá 'sixty' → iyéhí!yéhá 'in group of sixty'

4. 5 1 Reduplication with an interfix

- 103
- i. èghẹ 'time' → èghẹkẹ!ghẹ 'anytime'
 - ii. àkpà 'foolish person' → àkpàkà!kpà 'any foolish person'
 - iii. èmá 'drum' → èmákẹ!má 'any drum'
 - iv. èdẹ 'bush cow' → èdẹkẹ!dẹ 'any bush cow'

v.	àzèṅ 'witch'	→	àzèṅká zèṅ 'any witch'
vi.	àyónṓ 'wine'	→	àyónká yónṓ 'any wine'
vii.	ógá 'net'	→	ógákó gá 'any net'
viii.	ikò 'enemy'	→	ikókikò 'any enemy'
ix.	izè 'rice'	→	izékizè 'any rice'
x.	édé 'crown'	→	édékédé 'any crown'
xi.	ágá 'chair'	→	ágákágá 'any chair'

Examples 96 – 103 above show the various constructions that can be reduplicated in Edo. Examples 96 and 97 show the intensification of the categories that were duplicated i.e. verb and adjective respectively. Reduplication in example 98 is category changing. The reduplicated form changes from verb to adjective. In examples 99, we have those constructions that convey the meaning 'every/each...', 'in group of.. and plurality. The reduplicated nouns in examples 100 above have the semantic meaning of plurality/iterativeness. Cardinal numerals were reduplicated in examples 101 above and they all give us the meaning of 'in group of... The reduplicated constructions in examples 102 above gave us the meaning of "any – X". They are reduplicated with an interfix *kí* with a high tone on the vowel.

In examples 96 – 102 above, we gave various examples of complete reduplication in Edo. In it, a whole root or word is reduplicated, giving us various range of semantic interpretations as discussed above. We will give one example each from 96-102 and explain them using Marantz's method of pre-association.

104.

káká 'become dry'

105.

bètébètè 'fat, stocky'

(a)

106.

(b)

Examples 97 – 103 above with their illustrations in 104 – 106 above are similar in nature. The CV is reduplicated as in 104 above, while VCV is reduplicated as in 107 and 109 above. The reduplicative prefix, copying and association convention rules apply and we have the final output. However, the tonal tiers in 104 and 106 deserve some observations. After all the applications, in 105 and 106 above, the tones on the outputs are incongruous, we have to apply the tone polarization rule in 104 to get the final output and the postulation of the low tone reduplication suprafix to arrive at the output of 106 respectively from 100 – 103 above. We will also give one examples each of the derivation using Marantz's method of pre-association.

(d)

108.

(d)

(e)

= owáwá 'houses'

109. (a)

(b)

(c)

DS insertion

ehanhàn - 'in group of six'

110.

In examples 107 – 110 above, the accounts of samples in 100 – 103 were given. The peculiarity of 107 above against other derivations in 107– 110 was in the spreading of nasality, and the application of tone polarisation rule. For the derivation to be acceptable in the language, especially in example 109 above, after the reduplicative prefix, copying and the association convention rules have applied, the nasal autosegment was prelinked to the oral vowel, while the oral vowel was delinked. This took place after the vowel bearing the nasal autosegments has been delinked. It was after this derivation that downstep takes place. In example 108 above, we apply the tone polarisation rule to capture the outcome of the tones on the construction. Although, this was against what Adéniyi (2003) observed when he postulated a floating H tone for the same construction. We adopted this position here because we consider it to be less cumbersome. We also felt it is easier for us to account for it within this environment. In example 110 above, after all the prelinkings, we postulate a H-tone reduplication suprafix to account for all the high tones on the final output.

4.5.2 Tonal Changes in Reduplication

Tones on the various types of reduplicated constructions are very unique. Combination of tones yield different types of outputs. We are able to account for these various outputs within the framework of autosegmental phonology in a more principled way.

In examples 97, where verbs are reduplicated to give us other verbs, which are intensified after reduplication, while majority of the stem verbs which are monosyllabic

have high tone on them. However, after reduplication, they have LH tones. Some of these examples are repeated below for convenience.

111.	Verb	→	Total
i.	pién 'to press against'		piénpién 'same as pién'
ii.	sùnnó 'to be slow'		sùnnósùnnó 'describes slow lifeless gait'
iii.	bá 'to watch'		bábá 'reiterative sense of ba'

We accounted for this with tone polarisation rule. That after reduplication, the verb takes a tone that is opposite. However, we have an exception in our data, the only bisyllabic verb has a LH tone on it. After reduplication what we have is low tones on the output. We postulate a rule that will replace all the high tones with low tones after reduplication.

In examples 98 where adjectives are reduplicated to give intensified adjectives as output, the inputs to the reduplication process have two types tonal patterns on them. These are LH and LL. However, the output are usually LLLL. Some of these examples are repeated below:

112	Adjective	→	Total
i.	bètè 'fat, stocky'		bètèbètè 'sense of bètè'
ii.	bigò 'to be crooked'		bigòbigò 'very crooked'
iii.	gèlè 'really, indeed actually'		gèlègèlè 'infact, in truth'

As discussed in examples 97 above, we also have two different options in analysing these examples 98. One is to postulate a rule that will replace all the high tones with low tones after reduplication. If this is done, we will have all low tones as the output on all reduplications. We can equally postulate a grammatical floating low tone, which has been referred to as 'tomorph' by Elugbe (1985). This low tone will then link to other tones on the reduplicated constructions. The tonal output will also be all low tones. We must say that we can employ any of the two analyses above to give us the fact of the tone in Edo.

However, we will adopt the latter option of postulating a grammatical floating low tone because of its simplicity. We have two exceptions to our data under this section. The stem of the adjectives have H tone on them. The tonal output is also H tone. This to us is simple, when the stem was reduplicated, the tones on them were reduplicated along with them.

Examples 101 above have the same tonal features with examples 98; that was discussed. We will also adopt the option of postulating a grammatical floating low tone for the output.

The tonal patterns in examples 100 are predictable. When words with both LL and LH are reduplicated, they yield either LH!L or LHL.

Some of these examples are repeated here for convenience and they include:

113	Adverb	→	Total
i.	ùsén 'a period of five days'	→	ùsún!sén 'every five days'
ii.	òtá 'evening'	→	òtó!tá 'every evening'
iii.	èsó 'some'	→	èsé!só 'many'

There are two possible ways of accounting for these tonal outputs. One is to assume that a floating high tone surface between the reduplicated morphemes, then another rule will reduce all final tones after reduplication to low. The second option is to either say that prior to reduplication, the tones that we have on the stems are LH. In this case, we will have something like this:

114. i.	òtá 'evening'	→	òtáòtá	→	òtó!tá 'every evening'
ii.	èsó 'some'	→	èsóèsó	→	èsé!só 'many'

In this case, after vowel elision of V₂, its tone will displace the tone on V₃, while the high tone on V₃ displaces the tone on V₄ and the high tone on V₄ is deleted. Or we may also say that LHL melodies are assigned to the outputs after vowel elision. Whatever the tones of both the inputs and the intermediary, what we have on the reduplicated forms will be

then displace all the adjacent low tones with the exception of the initial and final lows. The other alternatives, which we will adopt, is just to say that the high tone(s) spread to adjacent low tones and cause them to become high with the exception of the final and initial lows. Elugbe (personal communication) is of the view that the final low tones in the data should be treated as falling tones. Initially, we treated them as low tone instead of falling tones because we observed that their occurrences are predictable. However, on a closer look, we agree with Elugbe because we later saw this as a floating low tone suffix morpheme for this construction which attaches obligatorily to the last syllable. By this rule, this predicts a falling tone. In all the constructions, the final syllable always has a falling tone. We will then say that this falling tone survives after reduplication. Downsteps are also created as a result of the deletion of low and high tones respectively. The low tone of the deleted vowel remains floating and causes subsequent tones to be realised as DS.

For those reduplication with an interfix, we will repeat some of the examples before giving the tonal analysis. There are four sets of examples that will be given. These are stems with LL; LH; HH and HL.

120. a) Reduplication of stems with LL

	Input		by reduplication		by vowel elision
i.	èghè 'time'	→	èghèkièghè	→	èghéke!ghè 'anytime'
ii.	àkpà 'foolish person'	→	àkpàkiàkpà	→	àkpàká!kpà 'any foolish person'

b) Reduplication of stems with LH

i.	édé 'bush cow'	→	édékiédé	→	édéké!dé 'any bushcow'
ii.	ázén 'witch'	→	ázénkiázén	→	ázé!nká!zén 'any witch'

c) Reduplication of stems with HH

i.	ágá 'chair'	→	ágákiágá	→	ágáká!gá 'any chair'
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ii. édé → édékiédé → édékédé
 'crown'

d) **Reduplication of stems with HL**

i. izè → izèkizè → izékizé
 'rice'

ii. ógà → ógàkiógà → ógákógá
 'net'

In examples (a) above, it is seen that after reduplication, the high tone of the interfix displaces the low tone of the initial vowel of the reduplicated form. This is after the vowel segment of the interfix has been elided. There is then a regressive assimilation of the high tone to the preceding tone of the stem. The output now gives us LHH!L, the low tone of the reduplicated form that is elided creates a DS. In the case of examples (b) with LH tonal pattern on the stems, DS is created as result of the elision of low tone of the reduplicated form, while the high tone of the interfix is retained. What we now have as output is LHH!H. In the case of HH tones on the examples in (c), what we have is elision of high tone of the interfix with its tone. The output then gives us HHHH. One way of resolving the problem of the final low that gives us high tone at the output is to create a rule that spreads the penultimate high to the final low. The high tone displaces the final low to give us the high tone in the final syllable. The solution profer here does not happen with examples in (a) above because we assume that the DS created in examples (a) block the spreading of high tone in the final syllable.

4. 6 Compounding

Languages often use their own internal resources to create new words, without appealing to other languages. One very frequent technique is compounding: combining two existing words into a new word. Compounding represents the interface between morphology and syntax per excellence.

However, there does not seem to be any disagreement among linguists as to the status of compound words in languages. The difference however, lies in various approaches to its definition. Fabb (1988:66) defines a compound as a word which consists of two or more words. He went further to say that compounds are subject to

morphological and phonological processes which may be specific to compounds or may be shared with other structures, whether derived words or phrases. Spencer (1991:309) on the other hand, sees compounding as prototypically, the concatenation of words to form other words. Lyons (1977:535) says a compound word is one whose stem is formed by combining two or more stems (with or without morphological modification). In this work however, we will define compounding as a word formation process whereby a word is formed from the concatenation of two or more words. These words that act as stems can be from the same lexical category (i.e. $N + N = N$) or from two different lexical categories (i.e. $V + N = N$, $Adj + N = N$) with or without morphophonological modifications. Spencer (1991) however raised a query on how to distinguish a word from a phrase when he said that 'we have often no satisfactory, unequivocal way of distinguishing between a compound word and a phrase'. This view represents the views of the transformationists which see a compound in terms of their relatedness to a phrase in syntax. This view may not be wrong because there are times when there is a correspondence between compound word and a phrase in syntax. Ôgûnkéyè (2002) gave us an example of the construction mad man which is regarded as a compound, because it has a synonymous expression in syntax, which is 'a man who is mad'. She further said that this analysis is problematic because there are syntactic constructions that do not have corresponding compounds. In English, the words 'girlfriend' and 'boyfriend' are compounds with syntactic equivalents 'a friend who is a girl/boy; but the words *childfriend or "adultfriend" are not attested nor acceptable compounds meaning 'a child who is a friend' and an adult who is a friend' respectively, although, no rule precludes their formation. The other view put into consideration, the meaning of the construction. It is said that if the meanings of the elements are unpredictable, then they qualify as words, but if they are not, then they will be regarded as phrases. It is from this angle that we will look at compound words. Di Sciullo and Williams (1987) and Egbokhare (1990) have all said that compound words should be seen as atomic units which can neither be separated by movement rules nor can any of its elements be pronominalised. Egbokhare went further to say that atomicity does not only involve structural immobility, it also has some semantic implications, the movement of a member of a compound word must either render the construction semantically anomalous or destroy the lexical meaning expressed

by the compound. For instance, the separation of *áziǵhó* 'bank' into its components *ázi* and *ǵhó* renders the structure incongruous. We will therefore conclude that whatever internal structure a compound word has, that structure is inaccessible to the rules of syntax, which means that syntactic rules apply only at the level of the phrase and do not take into account the internal structure of words.

Writers have at one time or the other use two criteria to identify compounding in languages. One of such is phonology. It was suggested that phonology is a more reliable indicator of identifying compounds in languages. According to Bloomfield (1933:228) 'accent subordination is the hallmark of compound. One word accent dominates the rest in a compound, but not in a comparable syntactic phrase. Based on the fact that we are dealing with an African language, which is tone dominated, accent will not assist in any way to distinguish between a compound and a phrase. However, the caveat that we will add, which Bloomfield (1933) did not mention is in the area of phonological processes. We have discovered that in some languages, phonological processes apply to compound words and not to phrases. Let us consider some of these examples:

121.	i.	òmó 'child'	+	òbó 'arm'	→	òmóbó 'child of the arm (infant)
	ii.	àkòṅ 'tooth'	+	èní 'elephant'	→	àkéni 'elephant tooth' (ivory)
	iii.	ékpó 'gap'	+	iyèkè 'back'	→	ékpíyèkè 'space of the back'
	iv.	yín 'be blocked'	+	èhó 'ear'	→	yènhó 'to be deaf'
	v.	vín 'swear'	+	ihén 'oath'	→	vinhén 'to swear an oath'
	vi.	tie 'call'	+	ikó 'meeting'	→	tikó 'to assemble'

If we look at the examples above, we discover that there are elision of vowels and tones at morpheme boundaries. This, to us, is a major distinguishing factor between a compound and a phrase in Edo. While phonological processes like elision, coalescence, and the likes can apply to the former, they cannot apply to the latter.

Katamba (1995) also suggested that orthographic conventions are a major guide to compounding. He said that some very well established compounds are written as one word, with or without hyphen. Some of the examples he gave were breakfast and ice-cream. We will however say that not all compounds are conventionally identified as such by (the) orthography; even in English that he cited as example. For instance, a compound like free trade sometimes appears as two separate words, with a space, and sometimes as free-trade, a single hyphenated word. Going through the data that we have in Edo, we discover that majority of the compound words are written as a word (which to us they are). There are however, a few of these hyphenated compounds in the language and these are mostly complex verbs which are separated by a space.

The notion of head plays a key role in the work of generative morphologists like Williams (1981a; 1981b), Di Scullo and Williams (1987) and Selkirk (1982). Using the x-bar syntax, they highlighted the fact that just like phrases in syntax have heads, derived words also have heads. Williams (1981a) concluded that after an extensive study of English compounds he found that, most compounds in English have a head. He further said that the head elements appears as the right-Hand Head within the constituent of the word. Based on the data available to us, we will conclude here that William's Right-Hand Head Rule (RHR) is not universal. Edo, just like Ògúnkẹ̀yẹ (2002) observed for Yorùbá, constitutes an exception to this rule. This is because 'head' in Edo language is predominantly left-hand. Consider some of these examples.

122. a) i. ùkó + àmè → ùkámè
 'calabash' 'water' 'calabash of water'
- ii. èkà + ókà → ékókà
 'cake' maize 'maize cake'
- iii. ètó + ùhé → ètúhè
 'hair' 'vagina' 'hair of the vagina' (female public hair)
- iv. òkpèn + èzè → òkpènzè
 'side' 'river' 'bank of the river'
- v. òkpé + évbò → òkpévbò
 'big' 'country' 'a big town, country'

vi.	ówá 'house'	+	èkèn → 'soil, mud'	ówékèn 'mud house'
vii.	úrúhù 'neck'	+	àbó →	úrúhábó 'neck of the head, wrist'
viii.	úrò 'line'	+	isè → native game'	úrísè 'the tray of isè'
ix.	óló 'grinding stone'	+	èkí → 'market'	ólékí 'grinding stone for market'
b. i.	bá 'guard'	+	ègbé → 'body'	bégbé 'be on guard'
ii.	gbé 'dó	+	òvó → 'grudge'	gbòvó 'to begrudge, to resent'
iii.	rhié 'take'	+	òhá → 'bride'	ròhá 'to take a bride'
iv.	mié 'accept'	+	ilè → 'bet'	milè 'to accept a bet'
v.	gbe 'undertake'	+	irúhù → 'shade'	gbirúhù 'to make a shade'

The two groups of examples are clear attestation to both the noun compound and verbal compounds that we have in Edo. The word on the left side of these compounds determine the lexical categories that they belong to. Based on our examples above, and as a reaction to Williams's (1981a) universal rule for compounds, we propose what we call left-Hand Head Rule. This serves as a modification to Williams' Right-Hand Head Rule. Our rule correctly predicts that the leftmost member of the word is the head of the word.

4.6.1 Endocentric and Exocentric Compounds.

Endocentric compounds are those in which one element functions as the head. The modifier element of a compound has the function of attributing a property to the head, much like the function of an attributive adjective. A sizeable proportion of Edo compounds are endocentric compounds and are highly productive (i.e. headed compounds) with the head normally on the left. Semantically, an endocentric compound

indicates a sub-group within the class of entities that the head denotes i.e. *àmótó* (*àmè + ótó*) groundwater, *ùkpèhèn ukpèn + èhè* 'a type of dressing used for menstruations; *èdèki* (*èdè + èki*) market day.

Endocentric compounds have constituent structures and are semantically compositional; the meaning of the compound can be inferred from the meaning of its various parts (examples above indicate this). Below are further examples of endocentric compounds in Edo.

123. a) i.	<i>òbó</i> 'arm'	+	<i>òbó</i> 'native doctor'	→	<i>òbòbó</i> 'native doctor's arm'
ii.	<i>ùnù</i> 'mouth'	+	<i>ùrò</i> door	→	<i>ùnùrò</i> 'the mouth of the door' (entrance)
iii.	<i>ègùè</i> 'hoe'	+	<i>ógbòn</i> 'new'	→	<i>ègùógbòn</i> 'new hoe'
iv.	<i>èkjá</i> 'penis'	+	<i>èni</i> 'elephant'	→	<i>èkjéni</i> 'elephant penis'
v.	<i>èkpò</i> 'bag'	+	<i>òdò</i> 'husband'	→	<i>èkpódò</i> 'husband's bag'
vi.	<i>òkpèn</i> 'side of'	+	<i>èzè</i> 'river'	→	<i>òkpènzè</i> 'bank of the river'
b. i.	<i>bibí</i> 'to groupe'	+	<i>òdè</i> 'road'	→	<i>bibòdè</i> 'to get lost'
ii.	<i>dé</i> 'to commit'	+	<i>iyí</i> 'rule'	→	<i>diyí</i> 'to break a rule'
iii.	<i>gbé</i> 'to do'	+	<i>àkiyèyè</i> 'joke'	→	<i>gbàkiyèyè</i> 'to make a joke'
iv.	<i>zè</i> 'to speak'	+	<i>èdú</i> 'interpret'	→	<i>zèdú</i> 'to interpret, to translate'
v.	<i>gbàḗn</i> 'to shift'	+	<i>ègbé</i> 'body'	→	<i>gbàéngbé</i> 'to shift body' (to move out of the way)
vi.	<i>kéé</i> 'to support'	+	<i>ègbé</i> 'body'	→	<i>kéégbé</i> 'to prop up self'

	vii.	ká 'to count'	+	íghó 'money'	→	kíghó 'to count money'
	viii.	mọ 'to do'	+	ètó 'hair'	→	mètó 'to plait hair'
c.	i.	dé 'what'	+	ẹghé 'time'	→	dẹghé 'what time'
	ii.	dé 'what'	+	ẹhé 'place'	→	dẹhé 'what place'
	iii.	dé 'what'	+	ẹvbèné 'manner'	→	dẹvbèné 'what manner; how'
	iv.	dé 'what'	+	óghé 'possessive particle'	→	dóghé 'whose'
	v.	dé 'what'	+	ẹmwín 'thing'	→	dẹmwín 'what thing'

The above examples further provide evidence for endocentric compounds in Edo. Examples c i – v are particularly interesting. They gave further insights into the Left-Hand Head Rule in Edo. This is because the interrogative pronouns provided in the various examples serve as the head and they appear at the left-handmost constituent of the word.

Exocentric compounds on the other hands are those compounds that do not contain an element that function as the semantic head which is modified by the non-head element. They are sometimes called “bahuvrichi” compounds by sanskrit grammarians ‘(having) much rice’. They are semantically non-compositional in that the meaning of the constituents cannot be worked out on the basis of the meanings of the words which they contain.

124. Let us consider some of these examples.

	i.	ẹfẹ 'wealth'	+	òtò 'ground'	→	ẹfótò 'riches of the earth' (mineral)
	ii.	ìgiè 'the base'	+	ẹmwèn 'speech'	→	ìgiẹmwèn 'the base of speech' (the chest)
	iii.	ọkọ	+	ẹhòhò	→	òkẹhòhò

					'boat'				'air'			'boat of the air' (aircraft)
iv.					òkpé 'big'	+			ùnú 'mouth'	→		òkpúnnú 'big mouth' (empty talk)
v.					òwá 'house'	+			òkhómwọn 'ill'	→		òwókhónmwọn 'house of the sick' (hospital)
vi.					òmó 'child'	+			èrhán 'tree'	→		òmérhán 'the children of the tree (fruit)
vii.					ùrhù 'neck'	+			òwẹ 'leg'	→		ùrhuáwé 'neck of the leg' (ankle)
b.	i.				tùá 'to intensify'	+			ùkpé 'lip'	→		tuákpé 'to intensify lip' (to shout; to talk loud)
	ii.				tùá 'to tighten'	+			òbọ 'hand'	→		tuábọ 'to tighten hand' (to intensify effort)
	iii.				zẹ 'to select'	+			ùnú 'mouth'	→		zùnú 'to chose mouth' (to be choosy about food)
	iv.				yán 'to ply open'	+			ùnú 'mouth'	→		yùnnú 'to open mouth' (to be surprised/amazed)
	v.				kpee 'to blow'	+			ùrhù 'neck'	→		kpóórù 'to shout voice' (to preach)
	vi.				miẹ 'to see'	+			àrò 'eye'	→		myàrò 'to find eye' (to have the opportunity to do with)
	vii.				khọ́ 'to be bitter'	+			ẹkóò 'belly'	→		khẹ́ékó 'to spoil stomach' (to irritate)

The examples above are both nominal and verbal exocentric compounds in Edo. They are regarded as morphological objects and are not internally analysable by syntax. They are headless constructions (by William's 1981b definition of head). The various examples above are fixed collocations with idiosyncratic meanings. The intended meanings are

difficult to predict by merely looking at the structure of the compounds. The entire word has to be interpreted. None of the components can help to either understand the meaning of the compound, or to determine the grammatical category of the word.

4.7 Ideophones in Edo

We are devoting this section to a group of words in the language which to the best of our knowledge, have not been thoroughly described. We are however aware that Agheyisi (1986)'s dictionary contains hundreds of them, but she does not discuss them although she even describes them as adverbs and adjectives. This present study is therefore an initial attempt to look at the morphophonological features of Edo ideophones. The following questions will ultimately give us clues about what Edo ideophones are.

- i. are there ideophones in Edo?
- ii. what are they?
- iii. how and why are they different from the regular formatives?
- iv. can they be described outside the phonology of the language?

4.7.1 What are Ideophones?

Doke (1935) is often credited with the term "ideophone" which is defined as "a vivid representation of an idea in sound. A word, often onomatopoeic, which describes a predicate, qualificative or adverb in respect to manner, colour, sound, smell, action, state or intensity" (Doke 1935: 118, cited in Voettiz and Kilian-Hatz 2001). Cole (1938: 370) says ideophones are "descriptive of sound, colour, smell, manner, appearance, state, action or intensity...[they] are vivid representation of visual, auditory and other sensory or mental experience. Awoyale (1983: 2) identifies polysyllabicity, tonal patterning and reduplication as part of the iconic strategies of ideophones. Trask (1993: 131 – 132) in his own case, defines ideophones as "[O]ne of a grammatically distinct class of words, occurring in certain languages, which typically express either distinctive sounds or visually distinctive types of action. They represent an attempt at fully exploiting the semiotics of iconicity to convey various sensations in a direct a manner as speech makes possible (Diffloth 1994: 108). Crystal (1997: 189) on the other hand defines an

ideophone as a "... term used in linguistics and phonetics for any vivid representation of an idea in sound, such as occurs through onomatopoeia." Ideophones tend to be generally longer than other lexical classes, thus enabling them to pack meanings into single morphemes to make them semantically multidimensional. Vowel repetition or lengthening is also characteristic of the class. Ideophones are often phonologically anomalous in terms of sounds, sound sequences, tonal structure and phonological behaviour (Welmers' 1973). In this work, we will therefore define ideophones as not only words which convey idea-in-sound, but also as words which are associated with manner, colour, taste, smell, silence, action, condition, texture, gait, posture and intensity in any natural language.

Another issue arising from studies of ideophones is whether or not ideophones constitute a word class. Crystal's definition of ideophones goes on to specify that in Bantu linguistics, "it is the name of a particular word class containing sound symbolic words". In fact, in many other languages of Africa and other parts of the world, ideophones are often treated as belonging to a specific word class (Bodomo (2000) for Dagaare, Kulemeka (1997) for Chichewa, Newman (1968; 2000) for Hausa, etc). However, there is considerable controversy as to whether they constitute a coherent class or are indeed distributed across many word classes. Awóyalé (1981, 1983 and 1989) have all shown that ideophone is unique both morphologically and semantically. He advocated for a re analysis of Yorùbá ideophone in particular to make ideophone a lexical category. Awóbùlúyí (1978), said ideophones belong to a class of adverbs, but they are special in that they are analysed as nouns. They are thus referred to as ideophones, to distinguish them from other adverbs and nouns. Rowland (1970) is of the opinion that ideophones belong to the open class of adverbs, but there is no formal criterion (morphological, phonological, and tonal patterning) which marks them off.

While we respect other people's viewpoints about the status of ideophone, we will, however, pitch our tent with Newman (1968) who argued that ideophones do not constitute a separate grammatical category even though they are amendable to syntactic descriptions and are often idiomatically restricted to appearing with particular predicates.

4.7.2 The Structure of Edo Ideophones

Under this section, we will take a look at the various types of ideophones and their morphophonological features. We shall also try to see if there are syntactic, semantic and pragmatic features of these group of words in Edo. One thing we have to note before proceeding, is to confirm that there is an avalanche of ideophones in the language. This is against the back drop of the claims made by Awóyalé (1974: 138) that "it does not seem that every African language has ideophones. Rundi is said to have three, Gusii has few ideophones". Another observation made is that ideophones in the language obey the phonological constraints of the language. They obey the open syllable constraint. They are all consonant initial. There are no vowel initial ideophones in the language, except when these ideophones undergo nominalization. No single syllable elements can be an ideophone. However, we noted here that some ideophones can be nominalized. When this happens, we have prothesis, which is the insertion of an initial vowel. This insertion is strictly motivated by morpheme structure considerations. Let us consider some of these example:

- | | | | |
|------|------|-------------|---------------------------------|
| 125. | i. | ékénnékénné | 'spotly design materials' |
| | ii. | ésóghósóghó | 'baby's rattle' |
| | iii. | étóghótóghó | 'rooster's crest at its throat' |
| | iv. | étólótóló | 'turkey' |
| | v. | élúkélúké | 'river tortoise' |

From the examples above, we observe that only one type of vowel can be inserted at the word initial position. This is front mid high vowel with a low tone "è". We noticed the tonal patterns on the nominalized ideophones in the language. In examples i – iii, only the initial vowel has a low tone while all other tones are high. The second category, as we have in examples iv – v are those with tone polarisation after the initial syllable. We must note here that the insertion of the vowel initial low tone does not change this tones of ideophones. In all the ideophones with more than two syllables we have both sequences of identical vowels and non-identical vowels. However, a sequence of identical vowels seem to be most common types in all the ideophones. All the 12 oral and nasal vowels in the language are involved.

4.7.3 Types of Ideophones

Phonologically, there are about four types of ideophones that we identified in the language. These are monosyllabic, disyllabic, trisyllabic and quadrisyllabic ideophones.

a) Monosyllabic ideophones

These types of ideophones consist of a single consonant and a vowel. We however found out that the vowel can be further lengthened for idiomatic effect. Some examples are:

- | | | | |
|------|------|------|---------------------------------|
| 126. | i. | kpòò | 'of intensity or brightness' |
| | ii. | vúún | 'of something deep' |
| | iii. | gbúú | 'of bad smell' |
| | iv. | kpíí | 'of a loud applause by a crowd' |
| | v. | gbíí | 'of many things' |

From our observation in examples 126, the nature of the glottis (of the consonants) will be determined by the type of tones that we have on the vowel. For the voiceless consonants, we have low tones, while for voiced consonants, we have high tones on the vowels.

The same type of lengthening phenomenon is found in some disyllabic forms. The final vowels of these forms are similarly lengthened for ideophonic effect. Some of these examples are:

- | | | | |
|------|------|--------|-------------------------|
| 127. | i. | higbóó | 'of heights' |
| | ii. | húròò | 'of dull appearance' |
| | iii. | gbáááá | 'of wide and expansive' |
| | iv. | gbódóó | 'of wide and broad' |
| | v. | kúròò | 'of dull and lifeless' |

The types of ideophones describe below have a CVCV structure where only the vowels and the tones are identical. Some examples are:

- | | | | |
|------|------|-------|-----------------------------------|
| 128. | i. | giri | 'of motion; sudden or unexpected' |
| | ii. | kisi | 'of smartly eh' |
| | iii. | gièrè | 'of small; tiny objects' |
| | iv. | pèrhè | 'of a flat surface that is low' |
| | v. | règhé | 'of something that is high up' |

We must note here that some of these disyllabic ideophones can be reduplicated for intensity within the language.

c) Trisyllabic Ideophones

These types of ideophones have a sequence of CVCVCV where the vowels, consonants and the tones are fully copied. Let us consider these examples:

- | | | |
|--------|----------------|---|
| 129.i. | sòsòsò | 'of excessively foamy' |
| ii. | réréré | 'of a very high pitched sound' |
| iii. | púpúpù | 'of the fluttering of a huge bird in a short distant flight.' |
| iv. | pépépé | 'of a general friskness or liveliness' |
| v. | dúdúdí | 'of very dark' |
| vi. | wówòwó | 'of brightly-burning fire' |
| vii. | wánwánwàn | 'of anything with a sheen' |
| viii. | kùkùkù | 'of the look of sprouting new leaves' |
| ix. | ghângghângghân | 'of weather' |

From the above examples in the language, we discovered that there are no cases of non-identical consonant, vowel and tones. Going by McCarthy's proposal, we will assume that the base of the above constructions or the reduplicants are copied twice hence, the various output. We must however note that some reduplication, such as those shown above have no base or root form. The base forms are non-existent in the language.

d) Quadrisyllabic Ideophones

These idiophones have the sequence CVCVCVCV or CVCVVVCV, where the vowels and the tones are identical. Let us consider these examples:

- | | | |
|-----------|------------|---|
| 130.a) i. | rághórághó | 'of the shade of colour' |
| ii. | sèkèsèkè | 'of an untidy and irritating object or sight' |
| iii. | sóghósóghó | 'of a rattling noise' |
| iv. | málómáló | 'of twisted, rumped' |
| vi. | kpèwèkpèwè | 'of unhealthy, puffy' |
| vii. | mitánmitán | 'lazy, weak, wretched' |

b.	i.	pápáápá	'of sth flat and wide'
	ii.	kpánpánánpán	'of very strong, very hard'
	iii.	gòngòngón	'of appearance'
	iv.	géngéngén	'of sth. very tight'
	v.	bébéébé	'of large extensive'
	vi.	gbégbéégbé	'totally'
	vii.	kókóókó	'of sth that is very solid and firm'

The two categories of examples above show cases of quadrisyllabic ideophones in the language. The examples are all products of one form of reduplication or another. However, in b examples, we have cases where the penultimate consonants of the reduplicated elements are deleted. i.e. $pápápápá \rightarrow pápáápá \rightarrow pápáápá$. We then have double vowels occurring together. This is peculiar to certain group of ideophones that have been faithfully copied. For this category of ideophones, we postulate the penultimate identical consonant rule. This rule will then delete all identical consonant next to the last syllable.

We also note that certain types of ideophones have the base forms that have their independent meanings. The reduplicated form derived their further meanings from them. Some of these include:

131(a).	i.	mitán	'to be lazy'
	ii.	sùkú	'squeeze; to wrinkle'
	iii.	sùnnó	'sth. very slow'
	iv.	vbùyé	'to be lazy'
	v.	túké	'to be small'

While the reduplicated forms are shown below:

131(b).	i.	mitánmitán	'lazy, weak, wretched'
	ii.	túkétúké	'describes very small things'
	iii.	súkúsúkù	'unpleasantly twisted'
	iv.	sùnnòsùnnò	'describes a very slow, lifeless gait'
	v.	vbùyèvbùyè	'indolent, weak'

We also note the tones on these inputs and output. The tones on the bisyllabic input is LH while the tonal output is LLLL, except 134 ii that has HHHH. We will postulate a grammatical floating low tone which Elugbe (1985) referred to as 'tomorph'. This low tone after reduplication spread to other syllables in the construction to give us LLLL.

We also note certain types of ideophones with six syllables, while there is an instance of an idiophone with eight syllables. These are:

132. i. bigóbíbigóbígó 'of sth. very crooked'
 ii. gbérégbèrègbéré 'of a manner of operation'
 iii. khúánkhuánkhuán 'of sth. very close or form'

in the examples i – ii above, the reduplicant is copied twice, while in example iii the reduplicant is copied thrice. However, there is the deletion of penultimate identical consonant. The tones on them are equally unique. When the base is copied, the tones on them undergo changes. We see that the tones on each syllable are at variant with each other. We will therefore postulate a tone polarization rule to handle that. This rule will however, not act on individual syllable as is usually the case; instead it will take the bisyllabic base that will take the tone that is its polar opposite.

Ideophones can equally be partially or totally reduplicated to give us varieties of meanings in the language. We will discuss each of them below.

4.7.4 Partial Reduplication of Ideophones

Partial reduplication involves the copying of either initial syllable or final syllable of the stem. This copy is now used as either a prefix or suffix. Let us consider these examples:

- 133 a) i. pèrèrè 'of the gliding motion of a bird in flight'
 ii. piànrànràn 'of sth. that is thin and long'
 iii. rhínrínrín 'continuously, non-stop'
 iv. siénrénrén 'of water, clean and pure'
 v. sùlèlè 'of carrying sbd. across the shoulder'
 vi. giànrànràn 'of sound'

- | | | |
|-------|----------|-----------------------|
| b) i. | kákábò | 'very much' |
| ii. | kúkùgbé | 'together' |
| iii. | wánwánná | 'just now' |
| iv. | wéwérhè | 'of wide and shallow' |

In examples (a) above, partial reduplication takes place to the right of the root, this invariably attaches to the root as a suffix. In this case, in example 133 (a) i the base form is *pèrè* while *rè* is reduplicated in the output which then gives us *pèrèrè* that we have in 133(a) i above. While in 133 (b) partial reduplication takes place to the left of the root and this attaches to the stem as a prefix. In this case, in example 133 (b) i the base form I is *kábò* while *ká* is added as a prefix. Only a syllable of the entire bisyllabic stem was copied. Examples 133 above all indicate intensification of the root.

4.7.5 Complete Reduplication of Ideophones

In this case, the base is completely copied at least, once. The consonants, vowels and the tones are fully copied to give us this type of complete reduplication of ideophone. This type of copying is used mainly for emphasis or intensification as we have in the examples below:

- | | | |
|---------|--------------|----------------------------------|
| 134. i. | nèkpènnèkpèn | 'gradually' |
| ii. | súkùsúkù | 'unpleasantly twisted' |
| iii. | lāghālāghà | 'of sth. that is dangling' |
| iv. | gólógólò | 'of a manner of walking' |
| v. | gidìgidi | 'of size, big, thick and strong' |
| vi. | bètèbètè | 'of fat, stocky and chubby' |

Tone in Edo ideophone does not have semantic connotation. This is contrary to what operates in Yorubá when Awóyalé (1974), quoted by Ógúnkéyè (2002:280) observed that the function of tones in words is different from when it (tone) functions in ideophones. Whereas in other words in Yorubá language, tones are used to maintain lexical contrasts, in ideophones, they serve to maintain quasi-grammatical/attitudinal contrast as well. Some of her examples include:

135.	i.	sòbólò sòbólò - sòbólò sòbólò-sòbólò	'long and pointed' 'very long and pointed' 'too long and pointed'
	ii.	fèrègèdè fèrègèdè-fèrègèdè fèrègèdè-fèrègèdè	'big and wide' 'very big and wide' 'too big and wide'
	iii.	bì ríkítì bì ríkítì-bì ríkítì bì ríkítì-bì ríkítì	'round and massive' 'very round and massive' 'too round and massive'

In examples 135 i, ii, iii above, the tone have semantic function it is performing. The reduplicated examples with 'high tones tends to suggest smallness or light-weight, the mid tone averageness, or medium proportion and the low tone largeness, heaviness or depth.

This, from our observation of the available data, is not the case with reduplicated ideophones in Edo.

4.8 Number Formation

Robins (1964: 247) observes that the commonest number distinction in natural languages is between singular and plural. Omoruyi (1986:61) however, notes that some languages, such as Ancient Greek, Sanskrit and old slavic formally distinguish three numbers, called singular, dual and plural. Some Fijian languages, on the other hand, distinguish four numbers, singular, dual, trial and paucial or plural. Edo language however, operates the more simple type; singular-plural dichotomy. The differences above clearly show that although the concept of plurality may be universal, the application is specific to individual languages.

Based on the singular-plural dichotomy; we can broadly divide Edo words into two sets. The singular and the plural sets. The singular set is made up of the following vowels, *ɛ*, *ɔ*, *o*, while the plural set is made up of *e* and *i*. There are no cases of nasalised vowels taking part in the number formation in the language. This is because of the fact that no word begins with a nasal vowel. It thereforre shows that back vowels function as singular set while the front vowels functioning as plural sets. Edo also marks plurality

when it replaces one of the singular prefixes with a plural prefix. Let us consider some of these examples:

136.	Singular	plural	'gloss'
i)	òkpià	ìkpià	'man'
ii)	ògiè	ìgiè	'king'
iii)	òkhuò	ìkhuò	'woman'
iv)	nófuá	néfuá	'white'
v)	nókpóló	nikpóló	'large'
vi)	nókpà	nékpà	'the other'
vii)	nókhuá	nékhua	'big'
viii)	òbó	ébó	'doctor'
ix)	òtén	ètén	'relation'
x)	òvièn	èvièn	'slave'
xi)	òkhèn	èkhèn	'customer'

Elugbe (1986:60) notes that "in the typical Edoid language, singular/plural prefix changes are phonologically determined and do not indicate any noun class semantic demarcation". He notes however, the existence of a curious plural form in a- which seems to have some kind of semantic content referred to as (paired) body parts (including 'teeth'). This plural form does not occur in Edo in such body parts.

The data above controverts earlier assertion by Omoruyi (1986:63) that 'only a few Edo nouns which possess the semantic feature [Human] can be pluralized through vowel substitution in word-initial position'. Examples iv – vii show that Edo nouns which possess the feature [Human] can also be pluralized through vowel substitution in syllable-initial position.

We also have the prefix òvbí... which translates as 'child/offspring...' which complements the singular-plural dichotomy. In its literal sense òvbí... possesses the semantic feature [+ Human], when it is pluralised as ivbí... meaning 'children/offsprings...'. However, òvbí is commonly employed as a diminutive prefix

when it occurs with non-human nouns. It can still be pluralised as *ivbí* as we have in the following examples.

137 i)	<i>òvbiÈdó</i>	'a native of Edo'	<i>ivbiÈdó</i>
ii)	<i>òvbiòzó</i>	'ozo's child'	<i>ivbiòzó</i>
iii)	<i>òvbímwèn</i>	'my child'	<i>ivbímwèn</i>
iv)	<i>òvbièrhán</i>	'a young plant'	<i>ivbièrhán</i>
v)	<i>òvbièwé</i>	'a kid'	<i>ivbièwé</i>
vi)	<i>òvibiágá</i>	'a small chair'	<i>ivbiágá</i>
vii)	<i>òvbiódó</i>	'pestle'	<i>ivbiódó</i>
viii)	<i>òvbiábé</i>	'pen-knife'	<i>ivbiábé</i>

The process of adding *ovbi...*, is peculiar when we compare Edo with some other Edoid languages like Emai. In Emai, it seems both human and non-human nouns can be pluralized without any affixes. Let us consider these examples from Egbokhare (1990: 116)

138. i)	<i>éwé</i>	'goat'	<i>é-</i>
ii)	<i>éuènlá</i>	'cow'	<i>i-</i>
iii)	<i>ópiá</i>	'matchet'	<i>i-</i>
iv)	<i>ófè</i>	'rat'	<i>é-</i>
v)	<i>úkpùn</i>	'cloth'	<i>i-</i>
vi)	<i>údó</i>	'stone'	<i>i-</i>
vii)	<i>úi</i>	'rope'	<i>i-</i>

Egbokhare (1990) did not report instances of any prefix in the language. We also like to note the tones on the vowels that take part in the number formation, except those examples of singular-plural formations with nasal consonant initial sounds, other vowels, both at the singular and the plural levels have low tones on them.

4.9 Affixes

In this section, we will discuss affixation in Edo. Though, some of those issues to be discussed here have already been mentioned one way or the other under other sections, such as nominalization, reduplication, compounding etc. However, we will discuss only prefixation and circumfixation here.

Affixation is very productive in the language. This is because Edo is a verb based language, and other word classes such as nouns, adjectives, adverbs and even verbs can be further derived from verbs through, affixation. While some affixes in Edo are category changing, others are category maintaining.

Affixation is considered as the only word building process by some linguists. This is because affixation includes not only the attachment of a bound morpheme to a free morpheme thereby creating a new word, but compounding and reduplication are also regarded as affixation (McCarthy 1981, Marantz 1982).

In this work, we will adopt Ógúnkéyè's (2002: 58) definition of affixation. She considers affixation as a process whereby an element, which is a bound morpheme, is attached to a root, which is a free morpheme. The bound element can precede the root (prefixation), it can follow the root (suffixation), it can be inserted within the root (interfixation), or attached before and after another morpheme or set of morphemes (circumfixation). From the available data, all these types of affixations are available in the language. Affixation applies after morpholexical and morphosyntactic rules have provided the base with derivational features. Since no grammatical or semantic operations are involved, affixation becomes a set of purely phonological modifications of the phonological representations of the base conditioned by the grammatical features. The head of such derivations is the lexical base.

a) Prefixation

These are elements attached to the beginning of a root prefix in Edo are both category maintaining and category changing. They maintain the category when a prefix is added to a root to only modify the meaning. While they change the category when a new word with a different meaning are formed. All the seven oral vowels in Edo can be used as prefixes. These oral vowels are attached to the beginning of a base and a new word is formed. Each of these oral vowels gave the new words that eventually formed new meaning. The meaning of these vowels are as mentioned under nominalization.

139. Let us consider examples of nouns formed from these prefixation.

i) à + gbákpán → àgbákpán
 prefix 'verb' 'a bald person'

- ii) á + bétù 'verb' → ábétù 'beads owner'
- iii) à + rhuáró 'verb' → àrhuáró 'a blind person'
- iv) á + gbíruen 'verb' → ágbíruen 'a dirty person'
- v) á + gbèté 'verb' → ágbèté 'a person with a sore'

140. Vowel è

- i) è + dáá 'verb' → èdá 'rain water'
- ii) è + vèn 'verb' → èvèn 'wrestling'
- iii) è + rèrè 'verb' → èrèrè 'deceit'
- iv) è + bàlọ 'verb' → èbàlọ 'the process of collection'

141. Vowel ẹ

- i) ẹ + h́h́h́ 'verb' → ẹh́h́h́ 'air'
- ii) ẹ + wiá 'verb' → ẹwiá 'smell'
- iii) ẹ + fẹ 'verb' → ẹfẹ 'wealth; property'
- iv) ẹ + gbé 'verb' → ẹgbé 'a quick dancing step'

142. Vowel i

- i) i + muégbé 'verb' → imuégbé 'the acting of dressing up'
- ii) i + fuéró 'verb' → ifuéró 'act of being careful'

- iii) i + dàbọ́ → idábọ́
 prefix 'verb' 'begging for alms'
- iv) i + bówá → ibówá
 prefix 'verb' 'house building'
- v) i + kó → ikó
 prefix 'verb' 'meeting'

143. Vowel ò

- i) ò + bàló → óbàló
 prefix 'verb' 'pain'
- ii) ò + nisàn → ónisàn
 prefix 'verb' 'anus'
- iii) ò + tuẹ → ótuẹ
 prefix 'verb' 'greetings'
- iv) ò + rriàrà → òrriàrà
 prefix 'verb' 'bitterness'

144. Vowel ọ

- i) ọ + bùdẹ́ → ọbùdẹ́
 prefix 'verb' 'advises'
- ii) ọ + bódẹ́ → ọbódẹ́
 prefix 'verb' 'a person who guides'
- iii) ọ + kpòrhù → ọkpòrhù
 prefix 'verb' 'preacher'
- iv) ọ + zìẹgbẹ́ → ọzìẹgbẹ́
 prefix 'verb' 'one who endures'

145. Vowel u

- i) ù + gué → úgué
 prefix 'verb' 'cover'
- ii) ù + gbètó → úgbètó
 prefix 'verb' 'scissors'
- iii) ù + kpákọ̀n → úkpákọ̀n
 prefix 'verb' 'chewing stick'
- iv) ù + ghẹ̀dẹ́ → úghẹ̀dẹ́

process involves affixation by circumfixation. The affix is realised as *ù-mwèn*. The 'ù' part of the affix precedes the verb to be nominalized while the 'mwèn' attaches to the end of the verb to derive a gerund.

As observed in the language, there are varying categories of verbs that can undergo this type of nominalization. Precisely, the stative, unaccusative, transitive and ergative are verbs that can be used to derive gerunds in the language. From the various observations so far made, this is not the only nominal process in the language. Indeed, all cognate nouns are also derived in more or less the same way. The difference lies in the fact that cognate nouns are derived through the use of a prefix only. Any verb that can derive a cognate noun through prefixation of a vowel cannot be nominalized to form a gerund. Conversely, verbs that derive cognate nouns cannot derive gerunds in Edo (cf. Ajiboye 2001). Stewart (1998) also added that cognate nouns and gerunds occur in mutual exclusive environment.

The tones on these gerunds are also interesting. As noted under nominalization, We postulated tone polarization rule to account for the alternating tone on the gerunds. In our own view, that postulation is still very valid. We will however add that when disyllabic verbs are involve, tone polarisation will not be able to capture this. The caveat that we will add is that if the verbs involve are disyllabic, the tones on them change to high tones while the two edge-most tones are still low.

CHAPTER FIVE

EDO PERSONAL NAMES

5.1 Introduction

This chapter attempts a description and analysis of personal names in Edo. In doing this, we shall look at the different views on names in general, and in Edo names in particular. The chapter surveys previous scholarship on Edo personal names, highlighting the different approaches adopted by these writers to the study of the phenomenon and their limitations. Another section of this work looks at the internal structure of Edo personal names. Both the morphological and syntactic structures are analyzed. The last part of the work looks at the Restrictive Principles of Edo personal name constructions. Taking insights from scholars who have worked on Yorùbá names, (Èkúndayò 1977; Akínnásò 1980; Awóyalé 1982; and Šàngótòrò 2002), we present a formulation of restrictive principles guiding the construction of Edo personal names. We concluded this section with evidence that Edo personal names are indeed derived words and not sentences or phrases as they seem to be.

Because of time and space, we have limited our scope in this study to personal names in Edo. We also believe that a thorough understanding of Edo personal names will give us useful insights into other categories of naming in the language. From our investigation, we found out that there are some overlapping between personal names and place-names, animal names and a few tree names.

5.2 What is in a name?

Tan (2004:307) quoting Andrews (1993:616) said that the 36th American Vice-President, Humphrey disagreed with Juliet, when she said:

what's in a name? That which we shall call a rose, by any other name, would smell as sweet' (Romeo and Juliet, 2:1-58). After all, she was trying to justify her love for Romeo. Humphrey declares in a speech made on 26th march 1966. In real life, unlike in Shakespeare, the sweetness of the rose depends upon the name it bears'.

The above quotation aptly illuminates the various angles by which people view naming. While some scholars on names are of the view that personal names have no meaning and do not make any sense, others are of the view that names function to individualize and distinguish people from others. To Euro-Western thought in general, a name is not part of a person, or a personality. The name is just a label, a tag, something to be used in reference to a person, but no more than that. This view is supported by Ziff (1960:174) who insists that "there is nothing in a proper name. It has information content, even so, it is all sound and if the sound is changed, the name is changed" Searte (1971:134) also opines that "proper names do not have a sense, they are meaningless marks, they have denotation but not connotation". Other scholars who shared the views of Ziff (1960) and Searte (1971) include Mill (1949) and Kripke (1977). On the other hand, some scholars are of the view that personal names have meaning. Frege (1992) and Lyons (1977) are in this category. Lyons (1977: 219) states that:

... the most widely accepted philosophical view nowadays is that names have meaning in some cultures and reference in all cultures.

He however missed the point when he said further that personal names have no sense at all and that they cannot be used predicatively purely as names. Our conclusion is that majority of these authors do not seem to have taken into consideration, the peculiarity of African culture. African names are a bundle of information regarding the bearer and the family. Events before, during and after the birth of the child (within both the nuclear and extended family) play significant roles in the name to be given the child. Òla-Orie (2002) quoting Òyélaràn (1976a) puts this rightly when she said that in a North America context, the equivalent of a name is the Social Security Number (SSN). As it is well known, a social security number is a distinctive number that is uniquely assigned to one person, and all vital information about that person, including birth, health, education, profession, residence, tax history, vehicle ownership, and so on, is documented using the assigned number. Access to a social security number provides access to the life of an individual. We argue here that personal names in Africa, nay Edo, perform more than the functions of a SSN. This is because Edo personal names not only personifies the individual (as the

SSN does), it tells some stories about the parents or the family of the bearer and in a more general sense, points to the values of society into which the individual is born. (cf. Ubahakwe 1981:99). It is pertinent to note that it is not only African names that have meaning and stories behind them. Even in the Judeo-Christian culture, names are known to perform special roles in the lives of the people. For instance, in the bible, (New Testament Translation), a widow exclaims:

Don't call me Naomi (pleasant)
Instead call me Mara (bitter), for the
Almighty has made life very bitter for me

(Ruth 1:20)

Edo personal names provides necessary link to the future, in terms of the parent's hope and aspirations for the child, and to the past, in terms of the connectedness of the name to the child's ancestors or identification within a particular community. More often than not, a name is a repository of accumulated meanings, practices and beliefs, and a powerful linguistic means of asserting identity

Edo people carefully select the names given to children during the naming ceremony. This is because of their belief that any name given to a child will ultimately affect him or her throughout the rest of its life. Hence, they give such names as:

147. i. Èvbárúè "prosperous" (a child born where the parents sojourn)
- ii. Ìdélégbàgbón "I have been established"
- iii. Ìdòlò!yi "I have come to repair (what an enemy has destroyed in our family)"
- iv. Òsàkiódè!mè "God has opened the way for me"

5.3 Previous Scholarship on Edo Personal Names

Generally, studies on personal names have been on for quite some time and in many languages of the world. For instance, Kimenyi (1989) studied aspects of naming in Kinyatwanda. Yassim (1978) discussed personal names of address in Kuwaiti Arabic, while Mehrota's (1979) work dwelt on the socio-cultural dimension of name change in Hindi. Chuks-Orji (1972) contains a generalized overview of African names. Asante

(1991) places personal names in Africa in regional context other than with reference to the specific ethnic groups that use the names. Madubuike (1984) offers explanations on the various African names mentioned in his book. Studies in Yorùbá personal names have also been on for quite some time now. Some of those who have worked on Yorùbá personal names include Sówándé and Ajánàkú (1969), Òdúyoyè (1972), Ekúndayò (1977), Akinnásò (1980; 1981), Awóyalé (1982), Adéoyè (1982), Babalolá (1983), Adéniyi (1997), and Şàngótòrò (2002). The treatment of personal names amongst all the scholars mentioned above vary. While some of them are only interested in the socio-cultural aspects of personal names, some only give a list of these personal names, while others attempt a socio-linguistics study of these names.

However, to the best of our knowledge, not much work has been undertaken on personal names in the language.

In the course of our investigation; we came across only three works on Edo personal names (henceforth EPN). These are; Omijeh (1968), Ogie (2002); and Omoregie (2005). We shall attempt an overview of these works.

Omijeh (1968) published a paper titled "Bini Proverbs" in *Nigeria Magazine*. In this work, he discussed what he called proverb-names in Edo. He is of the opinion that proverbs are often used in Bini personal names. He tried to classify some of these proverb names according to the sentiments they express. His treatment of these proverb names is not only scanty in nature, it is merely descriptive.

Ogie (2002) examined some Edo personal names from the socio-cultural point of view. In her work, *Edo Personal Names and World View*, she showed that Edo personal names are major tools for transmitting beliefs, family and communal history, as well as moral and societal values in a society where tradition is passed from one generation to another through oral medium. Finally, she showed that Edo personal names, as part of Edo culture and oral literature, provide useful information about the ethos of the people. Much as this work dwelt on the socio-cultural perspectives of Edo personal names, nothing was said in the work about the morpho-syntactic structure of Edo personal names.

Omoregie (2005), in his book *Edo Names for Cultural Studies* did a compilation of about 3,555 personal names with their meanings. He categorized the names under these headings: ancient, dynasty, ancestral deities, colonial, modern, philosophical, idiomatic, and divine. Much as we will say that this work lacks any in-depth socio-cultural and linguistic analyses of Edo personal names, we have to acknowledge the fact that it is a valuable material, particularly in the area of data provision. This present study benefits from his work because a large chunk of data in our analysis is drawn from this bank of data.

It has been shown clearly above that there is no analytical work in Edo personal names to date. Writers mentioned above have limited themselves to a consideration of socio-cultural aspects of Edo personal names. To the best of our knowledge, no single effort has been made in the formulation of syntactic rules and socio-cultural rules as we have in related languages like Yorùbá (cf. Ekúndayò 1977, Akínnàsò 1980, and Šàngótòrò 2002). As will be shown later, the syntactic restrictive rules and socio-cultural rules however determine the adoption of Edo personal names. We will therefore attempt, to provide a detailed study of the morpho-syntactic analysis of personal names in Edo language. We will formulate syntactic restrictive principles guiding the construction of Edo personal names. We will also discuss the various lexical idiosyncrasies of personal names which make us to accept them as lexical entities on their own despite the fact that superficially, they look like sentences. We hope that this study will open a vista of research into Edo personal name constructions, which will ultimately give us insights, not only into other types of naming in the language, but also insights into properties of universal grammar in which names form an integral part.

5.4 The Sociology of Edo Personal Names

Naming a child is no trivial pursuit in Edo culture. The culture places a great emphasis on the choice of names that are given to a child because it is their belief that a child's name affects its behaviour and ultimately determines its fate, saying:

Èkè nè á hée èni ghèé òré èrè èni lá ghé
 "a person is a reflection of his name"

The relationship between the bearer of a name and the name he/she bears is believed to be an intimate one. Hence, parents consult oracles when names are to be given to the baby.

Traditionally, the naming ceremony, (izòmò) i- zé-òmò "Act of choosing a name" takes place in the morning of the seventh day after the birth, if the baby is healthy and fourteen days if the baby is sickly. During this period of incapacitation, a tentative name Umweni, which means 'you do not have a name' is given to the child. This name is however adopted if the child is not healthy after fourteen days. However, if the child is alright, a proper naming ceremony is conducted and he or she is incorporated into the society. Ogie (2002:145), quoting Guemple (1965:324) mentions that the Eskimos have a similar culture in that they delay the naming ceremony for a few days to ascertain if the child will live. During the naming ceremony in Edo, the ancestral spirits are invoked for blessing. The items used include: **coconut**, (which represents the wealth that the child will bring to the family- coconut was an important item of trade brought by the Portuguese to the Benin Empire), **Orhue** (white chalk- which symbolizes purity and happiness), **native gin** and **colanuts** (used for invoking ancestral blessing for the child), **honey** (which symbolizes the sweetness of life), and **alligator pepper** (which symbolizes the bitter side of life). (cf. Ogie 2002:143).

While the parents give their preferred names, those present at the naming ceremony equally give names depending on their views about life or the various circumstances surrounding the birth of the child. Ogie (2002) reports that prior to the proper naming ceremony, seven different animal names are given to the child to deceive the various forces present and distract their attention from the actual names.

Investigation reveals that several factors motivate the various types of names that are given to children in Edo culture. Some of these include:

- a. The perceived roles of God.
- b. The physical appearance of the baby.
- c. The state of mind of the parents.

- d. The circumstances of birth.
- e. The deities /gods worshipped by the family.
- f. Infantile mortality.
- g. The various types of objects.

5.4.1 The perceived roles of God

While some parents see the birth of children as the work of the family ancestral spirits and the various deities they worship, others, more commonly, see the hand of God in the birth of a child. They are of the belief that the supreme God, makes it to happen. Some of the names they give under this category include:

149. i. **Ọsẹmwénkhà**

ọsẹ mwén khàá
enough me say

"I have good news to tell from what God has done for me"

ii. **Ọvbiòsà**

Ọvbi Ọsà
Child God

"a child of God"

iii. **Tièòsà**

Tiè Ọsà
Call God

"one who calls on God"

iv. **Ọsàgbémwórhùè**

Ọsà gbé mwé òrhùè
God pour me joy

"God has brought me joy"

v. **Ọsàghákhú**

Ọsà ghá khú
God will drive

"God will drive away my enemy from me"

vi. **Ọsàmàgióròmwẹnwé**

Ọsà má gi oro mwen we
God neg. allow secret me my

"God has kept my secret secret"

5.4.2 The physical appearance of the child

The physical appearance of the child might be closely observed during the seven days. Some of the things that might be taken into consideration include the baby's size and height, complexion, any deformity, and so on. This observation then culminates in naming the baby. Some of the names pertain to the physical appearance of the baby include:

- i. **Àgúéyòbò**
A gwé yó òbò
Nom. Prefix cover at hand "small at birth"
- ii. **Àgàdàgúdú**
"mighty"
- iii. **Àkpúkúrú**
À + kpúkúrú
"Small and ugly at birth"
- iv. **Ébò**
"a child born in a glamorous way"
- v. **Ìkpágèlè**
Ìkpè àgèlè
Seed bullet
"a child that is small at birth"

5.4.3 The 'State of mind' of the parents

Names referring to the 'state of mind' of the parents in Edo culture could be either negative or positive. Such names can refer to the constant imminence of poverty or misfortune, jealousy of neighbours, and co-wives or even ancestral spirit. On the other hand, it can be positive to reflect their joy and happiness in new born babies. Parents also feel elated that a child has been born successfully. They can also express the pride they feel in their beautiful children by giving them certain names. Some of these names include:

151. i. **Érúbókún**
 "elegant in beauty"
- ii. **Égbámè**
 Égbé àmè
 Body water
 "beauty"
- iii. **Àgbònmágúmwèngié**
 Àgbòn mà gù mwén gié
 World neg allow mine laugh
 "the world prevents me from my happiness"
- iv. **Òdúnámé**
 Ò dúná mē
 Nom. prefix settle me
 "It is well with me"
- v. **Ònàghisè**
 Onà ghí sè
 this is end'
 "This is where it ends (i.e. end of problem and predicament).
- vi. **Òsèìkpó**
 Òsè i kpó
 friend neg. plentiful
 "real friends are rare"
- vii. **Úsèìgbówà**
 usè i gbé òwà
 poverty neg. kill house
 "poverty cannot overcome the whole house (family)"

5.4.4 The circumstances of the birth of the child

Various events and circumstances under which the child was born might determine the type of name the child is given. Such circumstances might refer to the physical birth itself, a breech presentation, a difficult labour, or something else unusual. The names may refer to the problems that the mother had during pregnancy. Family circumstances may be referred to; sometimes the circumstances might belong to a wider arena than the immediate family or homestead. Names may refer to events of community or clan importance, festivals, the coronation or demise of a chief or king. It might even be the way and manner the baby was born. Sometimes, the birth follows a long period of childlessness. Such long periods causes a great distress and discomfort not only to the woman and the husband, but also to the extended family. Children born after a long wait have peculiar names. The place and timing of birth also determines the names that are given in Edo land. The position of the child within the hierarchy of children in the family also determines the names to be given. Some of these names include:

152. i. **Àbíẹ̀vbòdẹ̀**
à bíẹ̀ vbé òdẹ̀
nom born on road
"A child born on the way"
- ii. **Àbíẹ̀vbẹ̀kí**
À bíẹ̀ vbé ẹ̀kí
Nom prefix. born in market
"a child born in the market"
- iii. **Àzàyi**
"A child who came from his mother's womb with its leg" (breech)
- iv. **Èdíguẹ̀**
èdẹ̀ igwẹ̀
day a type of festival
"A child born on the day of Igwe festival"

- v. **Àlágbódè**
 A lá gbéé òdè
 Nom prefix pass block road
 "the last born"
- vi. **Èbósè**
 Èbòò sè
 charm 'effective'
 "a child born as a result of effectiveness of charm"
- vii. **Ìkpòbà**
 "A child born at the Ìkpòbà river"
- viii. **Èdégúà**
 èdé ègúà
 day yam planting
 "a child born on the day of planting yam seedling"
- ix. **Èdèbò**
 èdé èbò
 'day' 'a deity'
 "a child born on the festival day of community shrine"
- x. **Èdèkì**
 èdé èkì
 day market
 "A child born on the market day"
- xi. **Úgbó**
 "a child born in the farm"
- xii. **Òkpiàvbé**
 òkpià vbèè
 male scarce
 "a male child is scarce"
- xiii. **Òzó**
 'a child who is a warrior who had his placenta around his neck'
- xiv. **Ìtíòsà**
 Ì tié òsà
 Nom. Prefix call God
 "I call God"

- xv. **Òdíṣn**
 "senior twins"
- xv. **Ọ̀yḃókhàn**
 "Junior twins"
- xvi. **Ọ̀gbávbéwá**
 "The second child"

5.4.5 The Deities/gods worshiped in the family.

According to Jacobs (1974), the faith of the people is reflected in the names they give their children. It may be their faith in God or in the spiritual world generally. In African culture, every family has a god or goddess of its own which they worship. Such god or goddess is seen as the succor who acts as intermediary between man and the Supreme Being. When evils and calamities befall a family, the god or the goddess of the family is appeased through sacrifices. They are of the belief that these gods and goddess have the divine power to provide children for its adherents. Some of these deities and gods that they worship include *Ọ̀gún* (god of iron), *Ọ̀sún* (god of healing); *Ọ̀lókún* (god of sea, wealth, and posterity) and so on. When their prayers are answered, and they have children, they acknowledge the gods through the names they give these children. Some of these names include:

153. i. **Ìhàsé**
 ihà sé
 oracle come true + past
 "a child born under the prediction of the oracles"

ii. **Ìgbínàkẹ̀**
 Ì gbinná àkẹ̀
 Nom. Prefix seek protection shrine
 "One who took refuge in Ake shrine"

iii. **Èzizà**
 "a child dedicated to the goddess of the whirlwind"

vii. **Ògúnámẹ̀n**
 Ògún né àmẹ̀n
 God of iron of water (comfort)
 "the comfort from god of iron"

vii. **Òkúnbọ̀**
 Òkún bọ̀
 ocean favour
 "the ocean has favoured me"

viii. **Òkhùárẹ̀súyì**
 òkhùárẹ̀ sẹ̀ úyì
 goddess enough respect
 "Òkhùárẹ̀ is worth respect"

viii. **Ògúnsẹ̀dẹ̀**
 Ògún sẹ̀ ẹ̀dẹ̀
 god of iron visit day
 "A child born under the influence of Ògún shrine"

5.4.6 Infantile Mortality

The names under this category refer to children who are believed to belong to a group of demons that commonly reside in the trees like the *irókó*. Before they came into the world, they already have chosen the time when they will return back to their mates in the spirit world. These demons are connected with women who loose several children in infancy, especially, after a short period of illness. Special names are given to them with the hope that they will not leave upon their pre-arranged dates. This superstitious belief attempts to explain the high rate of infant mortality of the children in the society. These types of children are called *Ìgbàkhiàn*. The names given to this category of children range in meaning from, attempts to persuade them to stay and not be taken away from the unseen forces to threatening them with severe punishment if they should attempt to go again. Some of these names include:

154. i. **Ọ̀nàíwú**
 ọ̀nà i wú
 this neg die
 "this one will not die"
- ii. **Sọnnàràrè**
 sẹ ọ̀nà ràé
 leave this one alone
 "Leave this one behind"
- iii. **Gómwéndià**
 Gun nwem dià
 with me to reside at
 "Remain with me"
- vii. **Ìdiàgbọnyà**
 Ì dià àgbọ́n yá
 Nom prefix reside at world stay
 "I have come to live on earth"
- v. **Ọ̀mọ̀dià**
 ọ̀mọ̀ dià
 child reside at
 "this child has come to stay"

5.4.7 The various types of objects

Some of these objects that the Edo people name their children after are river, animals, plants, ornaments, birds, moon and so on. It might also be for one reason or the other such as the attributes of animals or plants. Some of these include:

- 155 i. **ìkpòbà**
 "the name of a river"
- ii. **ùkì**
 "moon" (beauty)
- iii. **útètè**
 "mountain"(protector)

5.5 The Internal Structure of Edo Personal Names.

The linguistic complexity of Edo personal names is a direct consequence of the variety and richness of the semantic load and socio-cultural information that personal names are made to carry in Edo culture. In fact, a complete grammar of Edo personal names cannot be written within the limited space of this thesis since it is almost a replica of the grammar of the Edo language. What we can do here is to give a sketch of the basic syntactic patterns of Edo personal names. Depending on the amount of information being signaled, Edo personal names can be derived from nominals or from full sentences of varying degrees of complexity. The discussion in this section is carried out within the theory of Weak Lexicalist Hypothesis (WLH) discussed above in chapter three.

Whether they are derived from nominals or sentences, Edo personal names are written as single words because of their syntactic classification as NP and their psychological perception as single words. Morphophonological devices such as contraction, elision, deletion and clipping are used in personal names construction to differentiate them from their NPs and sentences counterparts. We will now examine and analyse the various types of structures that we have in Edo personal names within the model that we have discussed above.

The first structure may be given as Noun plus a verb. Some of these examples include:

156. i. Ògún**b**ò
 ògun bò
 god of iron favorable to
 "god of iron has favoured me".

ii. Òsà**r**ò
 Òsà ró
 the supreme God exist
 "God is alive"

iii. Èrhàbó
 Èrhà bó
 father be good for
 "my father has favoured me"

iv. Òsàkpòlò
 òsá kpòlò
 the supreme God big/huge
 "God is great"

v. Ùwádái
 ùwá dái
 Wealth to retain
 "my wealth has settled"

Given example 156(i) above, we can graphically represent all other examples as follows:

The above schema clearly shows all the illustrations given in examples 156.

Another structure that we observed in the language may be given as noun plus negative marker plus a verb. The negative marker in this position is either *i* or *má*. Let us consider some of these examples:

157. i. **Òsàìgbé**

òsà i gbé
 God neg. kill
 "God does not kill"

ii. **Ònàìwú**

Ònà i wú
 this neg. die'
 "This one will not die". (He is protected)

iii. **Àgbònífó**

Àgbòn i fò
 the world neg. end'
 "The world will not end"

iv. **Òkúnmárhíà**

Òkún má rhíà
 the ocean neg. spoil'
 "The ocean did not spoil anything"

The above examples can equally be represented as follows:

ímáfù

'I did not confiscate what is
 not mine'

However, there is a class of names with no overt negative marker at the surface level. When these names are written, what we have are semantically anomalous words (names). Let us consider the following:

158. i. *Ògbèwí as in
 Ògbè wi
 family lose'
 "The family line is lost"
- ii. *Úwàbí
 Úwà bí
 wealth detect'
 "wealth are easily detected"
- iii. *Ògièìghó
 Ògiè ìghó
 Chieftaincy money
 'Chieftaincy is money'
- iv. *Òkhiònkpàmwọnyì
 Òkhiòn kpà nwọn yi
 "an isolated fellow has glory"

In the above cases, these are not semantically well-formed phrases that correspond to the nominalization (That's why they are starred). Although the verb phrases above are all well-formed, there is a negative marker *i* that we have before the verb but which is not present at the surface level in examples (158) above. Hence, the intention of the speakers of Edo is not reflected in the names above. However, the speakers' exact thought is captured in the corresponding examples below:

- 159 i. Ògbèiwí
 Ògbè i wi
 the family neg. loss
 "The family line will not be lost"
- ii. Úwàíbí
 Úwà i bí
 wealth neg. detect
 "wealth are not easily detected"

iii. **Ógièìghó**
 Ógiè i ighó
 Chieftaincy neg. money
 "Chieftaincy is not money."

iv. **Òkhiònkpàimwònyì**
 Òkhiòn i kpá nwón yì.
 "An isolated fellow has no glory"

We observed in examples (iii) above with respect to the negative marker (i) and noted that the final sound of N¹ is equally identical with the negative marker. After collocation, it is assumed that the initial vowel of N² is deleted while the negative marker is retained. Another structure consists of a noun plus another noun. Some of these include:

160.i. **Àdeśúwà**
 Àdè sẹ ùwà
 'Centre/middle prosperity
 A child born in prosperity"

ii. **Ìghòmọ**
 ìghó ọmọ
 money child
 "money spent on children are not easily reckoned"

iii. **Èdóghòghò**
 Èdẹ òghòghò
 day joy/happiness
 "Day of joy"

iv. **Èsọhẹ**
 Èsẹ ọhẹ
 favour gift
 "Grace"

v. **Àdúwà**
 ádà ùwà
 crossroads wealth
 "The beginning of greatness"

The above examples can equally be represented as follows:

Àdúwà

"The beginning of greatness"

As can be seen from the examples i-v above, two nouns, drawn from the lexicon are combined to form a personal name (i.e. $N^1 + N^2$). The choice of any noun to be used is strictly motivated by Positive Home Condition Principle (which we shall discuss in details in 5.6 below). Although, we can have quite a number of semantic relations holding between the members of this type of nominal compound, the correct semantic interpretation will depend, on the kind of human experience and in Positive Home Condition Principle which motivate such a name.

Morphologically too, Edo language has been described as operating a Left-hand Head Rule (LHR) contrary to William's (1981:248) Right-hand Head Rule. (This was discussed under compounding earlier.)

Another type of structure that we have is a subject + verb+ object (which is a noun plus a verb and another noun). Some of these examples include:

161. i. **Òsàròdiòn**

Òsà ré òdiòn
 God is oldest
 "God is the first"

ii. **Ìhàsúyì**

Ìhà sé úyì
 oracle is honour
 "The oracle is worth glorifying"

iii. **Òsànoگیه**

Òsà né oگیه
 God the king
 "God is worth His title"

The above examples can be graphically represented as follows:

We also identify another type of structure which is made up of a prefix, a verb, and two separate nouns. Some of these examples include:

163.

i. **Ìzódúwà**
 Ì zé òdé úwà
 1st sg choose road wealth
 "I have chosen the road to wealth"

ii. **Ìzédósà**
 Ì zé òdé òsà
 1st sg choose way God
 "I have chosen God's way"

iii. **Ìzèyúwà**
 Ì zé èyè úwà
 1st sg choose promise wealth
 "I have chosen wealth"

The above examples can be graphically represented as follows:

Izédosá
 'I have chosen God's way'

We also have another structure made up of a nominalizing prefix plus a negative marker plus a verb and a noun. Some of these examples include:

164 i. Àizòbò
 à i zé òbó
 1st sg neg select native doctor
 "you refuse to be a native doctor"

ii. Àìgbónà
 À i gbé ònà
 Nom prefix neg. kill this
 "You cannot kill this one."

iii. Àìfókùn
 À i fi okùn
 'Nom. Prefix neg. cover sea
 "You cannot trick the sea"

iv. Àìfúwà
 à i fi úwà
 Nom. Prefix neg gentle wealth
 "One should not be in a hurry to accumulate wealth"

Picking example 164iii above we can graphically represent examples 164 as follows:

Àifókùn "You cannot trick the sea"

We also observed another type of structure with a prefix plus a negative marker and a verb. Some of these examples include:

165. i. Àìgbé
 À i gbé
 Nom. Prefix' 'neg kill
 "My life is protected"

ii. Àìrén
 À i rén
 Nom. Prefix neg. know'
 "Nobody knows"

iii. Ìmágbé
 Ì má gbé
 1st sg. neg cause
 "I am innocent in this case"

vi. Ìmáfù

ì mà fù

1st sg neg snatch

"I did not confiscate (what is not mine)"

vii. Àsìen

À i sièn

1st sg neg. deny'

"I have courage"

The above examples in 165 above can be represented in the schema as follows:

Àsìen
"I have courage"

There are very few Edo personal names derived from the NP = noun(name) rule. They therefore constitute a limited subset of personal names that we categorized under circumstances of birth and the various objects. Some of these examples include:

- 166.
- a. Ózò --- a child who placed its placenta around its neck during birth
 - b. Ídádá---a child born with entangled hair.
 - c. Úgbó--- (Progress) a child born in the farm.

Each of these names is made up of a single morpheme and has a unique meaning which corresponds to the special circumstance for which it stands. These names have to be specially learnt since they are not often suggestive of the special circumstances to which they refer.

5.6 Formulation of Principles for Personal Name Constructions.

In this section, we shall discuss the four register peculiarities which Ekúndayò (1977) observed for the Yorùbá personal names. We observed a relationship between what Ekúndayò discussed for Yoruba and what we have in Edo is quite similar to what we observed in Edo names. We shall attempt to see how these peculiarities are equally applicable to Edo personal names. These peculiarities, according to him, are Home condition, Length restriction, the Singular polarity condition and the Mood restriction. These four register peculiarities are very crucial in severely limiting the expansion possibilities of sentence which make it impossible for Edo personal names to constitute an infinite set of items.

According to Ekúndayò (1977:58) the condition of home determines a child's name. He went further to say that:

Hence, any Yorùbá sentence which satisfies no home condition can never be a Yorùbá personal name. A home condition may be any significant event in the history of a family, particularly at the time a child is born.

This study on Edo personal names agrees with Ekúndayò's assertion that the home condition is a serious restrictive principle excluding some items from the repertoire of personal names. For instance, in Edo, a boy or girl may be born after the family has just overcome major disaster. The baby is usually considered as harbinger of good things into the family, and is given specific and commonly recognized names like:

167. i. **Ọ̀nàghísẹ̀**
Ọ̀nà ghí sẹ̀
this is end'

"This is where it ends (i.e. end of problem and predicament).

ii. **Ọ̀sẹ̀mwénkhà**
ọ̀sẹ̀ mwén khàá
enough me say

"I have good news to tell from what God has done for me"

iii. **Gùmwéndià**
Gú mwén dià
with me stay

"remain with me"

iv. **Ọ̀nàiwú**
Ọ̀nà í wú
This neg die

"This one will not die"

The sentences in i-iv above satisfy some Edo home conditions; hence each of the sentences is qualify for merging into single word nouns which then function as Edo personal names. Since mothers can die some months, weeks, or days before children are born, i and ii in 167 above are names for actual home conditions. Same is also true of examples iii and iv in 167 above where it is equally possible for a child to die at infancy more than twice or even more and then another baby is born who now survives.

The above examples show Edo names that exist for what are now recognized as actual home conditions, and that acceptable (sentence) names can be constructed for potential home conditions. However, there are some events in Edo which can never be interpreted as actual or potential home conditions. For instance, examples below are possible events, and each of them is a single Edo sentence.

168. i. **Ìkpátá gbé ọ̀kpiá vbẹ̀ àdà ọ̀ghé Ìkpóbà ọ̀wié nà**

Armed robbers kill man at junction Ikpoba morning this

"At Ikpoba junction, armed robbers killed a man early this morning."

- ii. *Ózọ má sẹ́tín vbiẹ né àsón rhùnmwúdá imùèn*
Ózọ neg. be able sleep last night because mosquito
"Ózọ could not sleep last night because of mosquito bite".

Though the two sentences in 168 above are possible events in the language, they can never be construed as home condition to warrant the naming of children with such sentences. Hence, sentences not interpretable as home conditions severely limit the repertoire as well as the productive capacity of the Edo personal names since they cannot be members of the same group.

While our examples in 168 above support Ekundayó's claim about home conditions, we will have to add here that it is not possible for every event in the family or all home conditions to motivate personal names constructions in Edo. There are some words like madness, robbery, leprosy, the practice of sorcery and witchcraft or even events in which a family or any of its members has been banished from a town because of misdemeanors and so forth which are regarded as anathema socially and which no family can refer to when naming a child. Such words or events are at the lowest point of the value hierarchy. Hence, no parent will give his child any of the undermentioned names:

169. i. **èmwẹ́mwẹ́má*
 "madness is good"
 ii. **Íkpátámwẹ́yì*
 "armed robbers have respect"
 iii. **àzénmá*
 "witchcraft is good."

We however notice that in the naming system of the language, only those home conditions or events that are positive in nature induce personal name constructions. In cases where some of the above vices exist, they are regarded as negative home conditions and therefore cannot be directly mentioned in the formation of a noun. However, where the conditions are included in names, the vices will either be condemned or the negativity of such events will not be pronounced. Rather, a positive reaction to the vice, observation arising from the vice or a general comment may form part of the name, observation. It is the positive side of the event that will then be utilized in the naming process. In the

examples below, negative events in the family are re-structured to motivate the names below:

170. i. **Iyabòṅgiémwén**
 I yá bọ nọ gie mwén
 "forgiveness" (I have forgiven those that mocked me)
- ii. **Àimíósèvbùsé**
 À í mié ósè vbè úsé
 Nom. neg. see friend in poor
 "no friend in poverty"
- iii. **Úwúìgbẹ̀gbẹ̀fòédòkpá**
 uwú i gbé egbe fò ede okpa
 death neg. kill family finish day one
 "death cannot annihilate everyone in the family at the same time".
- iv. **Òwámwẹ̀ghian**
 Owa mwẹ eghian
 Home has enemy
 "home has enemies" (families are not without enemies)

In the above names, the negativity of suffering is not pronounced in 170(i) and (ii) while in 170(iii) to (v), the arrival of the child herald new life, despite the past tribulations encountered by the members of the immediate family. Despite the fact that it is apparent that the immediate family of the child had terrible experience before the birth of the child, the negativity of such event or experience will never be made known. This is the more reason why the following are ill-formed as personal names whereas, they are accepted as sentences in the language:

171. i. **úwu yé imè**
 "I like death"
- ii. **Usé sé úyi**
 "Suffering is worth glorious"
- iii. **úsé rhiénrhién**
 poverty sweet
 "poverty is sweet"

We will therefore attempt a modification of Èkúndayò's (1977) home condition to prohibit possible destructive, negative and unpleasant events and home conditions.

Rule 1: A personal name in Edo is strictly motivated by positive and constructive home condition by both immediate and extended family.

The second principle that Ekundayò (1977) proposed for guiding the construction of personal names is the reductionist principle. He explains that no personal name can be indefinitely long since personal names have specific functions apart from the fact that they may be meaningful, they are also expected to identify people. Personal names though sentences, tend to be short, they have severely limited the expansion possibilities and the productive capacity of the Edo personal names sentence rule. This is why in personal name constructions, the sentences contain embedded sentence, with each of the embedded sentences not being recursive. Ekundayò (1977) gave an example in Yorùbá:

172. Enilolóbò [S[NP eni tí[Ó lo] S]NP[VP ní[NP^{emí} "S^{ó lo}]S]NP]VP]S

(Person who he left is person who he returned), i.e. the one who left (or died) has returned (been born again).

The example above in Yorùbá, though personal name, is an embedded sentence, dominated by an NP and is non-recursive. Such sentences are usually found in the underlying representations of relative clauses. One major restrictive condition for the Edo personal name is the non-recursive nature of embedded sentences.

These types of Edo personal names are bound in the language. Let us consider some of these examples from the proverbial sources where personal names are eventually derived. The second part of the proverb is obligatorily deleted when the proverb serves as an Edo personal name.

173. i. [S[NP Èno' ghá yin]S [VP àgbon, è i dámwéhò áhíámwén útùòyà]S]S.

'Person' that live life 2nd pl. neg. listen bird lament

One who would live (successfully) does not listen to áhíámwénùtùòyà. (*a type of bird*)

i. [S[Né ò gú mwén gié] S REL [Sòre òsèmwéè]S]S

The pro with me laugh is my friend'

"It is he who laughs with me who is my friend"

iii. [S [S Óvèn ó ser] S REL [S nó gbèn ihùnmwùn èsè]S]S

Sun pro. judge that clear grass well

"It is the sun who decides who has cleared or weeded the grass properly"

iv. [S [Aghábúeze,] S CONJ. [S òni ghá fi] S] S
 À ghá bú ézè òni ghá fi
 Pro. aux. close river cold aux be
 "As one approaches the river, one gets cold"

v. [S[S Àmènnagháwòn,] S AUX [S èi lẹ somwánràè] S] S.
 àmè ne a ghá wòn è i lẹ sé òmwán ràè
 water that pro. aux drink it neg. flow pass person away
 "The water meant for one will not flow past one"

- 174 i. Ènògháyìn--- the person that will live
 ii Ènógúmwengiè--- the person that laugh with me
 iii Òvènsèrì----- the sun judges
 iv Àghábúezè---- as one gets close to the river.
 v Àmènnagháwòn----the water that one would drink.

The above examples in 173 i-v further demonstrate the fact that even when these names are derived out of sentences i.e. both compound and complex, as can be seen in 173 i-v above, they still have to be reduced to smaller units, as we have in 174 i-v above in accordance with the length restriction principle. Without this, unattested utterances will be produced in the language. One may note that there is nothing strange in the phenomenon describe in 174 since the full meaning of any proverb is usually implied by any recognizable part of it. Hence, given 'early to bed', any English speaker can easily complete the final part of it with 'early to rise'. We therefore concur with Ekundayò's second rule which states that:

Rule 2: Any long utterance in the ambit of personal names formation is reduced to its acceptable minimal structure.

The third condition which is the singular polarity condition stipulates that no personal name is obtained from the negation of another personal name. A closer look at personal names in Edo confirms this assertion by Ekundayò. Accordingly, given the examples in 175 i-ii we cannot derive 175 iii-iv sentences. (We are repeating some of the examples above for convenience).

175 i. Òbósúwà
 Òbò sé úwà
 Hand (labour) bring affluence
 "dignity of labour bring wealth"

ii. Àgbónà
 À i gbé òná
 Nom prefix neg. kill this
 "You cannot kill this one."

iii. *Òbóisúwà
 Óbó i sé úwà
 Hand neg. bring affluence
 "Dignity of labour does not bring wealth"

iv. *Àgbónà
 À gbé òná
 Nom prefix kill this
 "You can kill this one."

Ekúndayò (1977:64) therefore claims that negative cum positive polarity, for instance, needs not be indicated in these names, since opposite of names are permissible in the language. Observations from Edo personal names therefore tally with what Ekúndayò (1977:65) mentioned for Yorùbá personal names with rule 3.

Rule 3: No personal name is obtained from the negation of another personal name.

The last of the principles of personal name constructions is the mood restriction. According to him, all the restrictive principles which have so far been analyzed are applicable to the imperative mood. In the case of interrogative mood, however, few restrictions are identified. According to Ekúndayò, the overall restriction could be that no name is obtained from interrogative sentences. For instance, no place or time interrogative sentence can be a personal name. In this case, the restriction here is that no name is obtained from interrogative sentences concerning question word 'wo' which in Yorùbá. Going through our data, we discovered that this assertion is true of Edo language. From the available data in Edo, no name is obtained from interrogative sentences concerning questions *which, what, where, or when* in the language. Going by Ekúndayò's assertion, we cannot derive personal names from the following as well as similar sentences.

176. i. Dèhé giè òkún?
 Where is òkún?

- ii. *Òsà déhè?*
Where is *òsà*
Where is God?

However what seem to be interrogative sentences are indeed truncated form of complex sentences or affirmative sentence with interrogative marker in the language. Let us consider these examples.

177 i. *Àdámòsà*

"What God has done is perfect".

ii *Èmwiómwúsi*

"What belong to the world is admired by everybody"

iii *Èvbádólopyi*

"What you have repaired"(no one can destroyed again)

iv. *Ìyámù*

"What I hold firmly"

Our rule 4 will then state that:

Rule 4: No personal name can be constructed through interrogative pronouns in the language

5.7 Edo Names as Words

This section provides evidence to show that Edo personal names are indeed single words and not phrases which are productively derived out of noun phrases and or sentences. The evidence is provided within the model of morphology and syntax interaction which we have discussed above in chapter three. This evidences are: extraction, pronominals, anaphoric binding, behaviours of these names with modifiers and determiners when compared with their noun phrase or sentence counterparts and non-referentiality.

The first syntactic evidence is extraction or what Spencer (1991:185) called positional mobility. In nominalization, it is impossible to extract some components of the internal structure of a phrase, whereas, as a word it can be moved relatively easily within the sentence.

Bauer (1988) reported that both Latin and classical Greek have greater positional mobility as major lexical constituents may appear in any order. For instance, all the examples in (a) below have the same meaning despite the fact that they have different surface structures.

178. (a) Brutus Caesarem occidit Brutus killed Caesar
 (b) Caesarem occidit Brutus Brutus killed Caesar
 (c) Occidit Caesarem Brutus Brutus killed Caesar

Unlike the case-permitted variant in Latin above, Edo, just like Yorùbá is a case-of movement rules (Move-a) which, according to Ógúnkéyẹ (2002), allows elements of major grammatical categories to be moved for purposes of topicalisation, clefting, etc.

179. [[...x...]]
 (Pulleyblank & Akinlabi, 1988:147)

Consider the examples below:

180. (a) iràn mú òsàgióbàrré kpá
 They carry name away
 "They carried Òsàgióbàrré away"
- (b) Ọ́ ghéré Òsàgióbàrré né iràn mú kpá.
 It was name that they carry away
 "It was Òsàgióbàrré that they carried away"
- (c) *[òsà] né iràn [gióbàrré] kpá
 Name that they VP 'away'
- (d) *[giòbà] né iràn [òsà] mú [] [ré] kpá
 VP that they name carry pt. mk away'
- (e) *[giobarre] né iràn [òsà] mú [] kpá
 VP that they name carry away

In example 180(a) above, there is no extraction; the extraction in 180(b) is the entire derived word (in this case EPN) which shows that nominalization is truly a syntactic operation. The reverse is the case in examples 180 c-e. This shows that no part of the phrase. This supports Pulleyblank and Akinlabi's claim for Yorùbá that no element internal to a word can be moved by a syntactic operation.

Further syntactic evidence is pronominal and anaphoric binding. In this case, Edo names constitute an island; therefore, it is impossible to replace the nouns within the names with pronouns or even replace the pronouns with names. They may be accepted in the context of phrases and/or sentences which are identical to the names but not in the context of Edo names when they are considered as words. Consider the following:

181. (a) (...Pronoun) X^o

(b) (...pronoun...)

In 181 (a) it is shown that, while it is possible to have pronouns within the configuration, the model does not allow pronouns to occur within the category of level X^o. Consider the examples below:

182.(a). *Òsàikhíwúòmwan* "God does not keep malice with any person" (as name)

(b). **éikhíwúòmwan* "he does not keep malice with anyone"

(c) **Òsàikhwúòzò* "God does not keep malice with Òzò"

Example (b) shows that it is prohibited that pronoun *é* be replaced with *Òsà* God. In example(c) a name *Òzò* cannot replace a first person plural pronoun *mwán*. In both cases, it makes the word ill-formed. If we accept the fact that Edo names are derived words of which the structural input is phrasal, then the possibility of having pronouns replacing nouns or vice-versa does not arise. But it is possible in the phrase that corresponds to nominalization for pronouns to replace nouns or vice-versa. This is illustrated below:

183. (a) *Òsà i mú òhú ònwán*

God neg. carry malice person

"God does not keep malice with anyone"

(b) **é i mú òhú ònwán*

"he does not keep malice with anyone"

(c) **Òsà i mú òhú Òzò*

"God does not keep malice with Òzò"

Furthermore, while modifiers or determiners alike can be inserted in the phrases when there are additional information is to be given, this cannot be done with personal names that are considered to be single morphological unit. Let us consider the following:

Personal names

184. a. *Òsàhòn*
Òsà hòn
God hears

Ordinary S/NP
Òsà hòn èbàán
"God hears now"

b. **Òsàhònèbàán*
*'Name' 'now'

c. *Òkúnkpóló*
"Ocean is great"
Ocean big/plenty

mwán òkún kpóló
our ocean plenty
"Our ocean is great"

(d) **mwánòkúnkpóló*

(e) *Ògúnbó*

òná Ògún bó

"One that the god of iron has favoured"

this god favour
"God of iron has favoured this"

(f) **ònáògúnbó*

The above examples, 184. a, c, and e, indicate that as many as other elements can be introduced in ordinary sentences, such is not possible for construction that have been nominalised as personal names in Edo as can be seen in 196. b, d and f above. Additional elements like *èbàán*, *mwán* and *òná* that are inserted in these derived words make them ill-formed.

Another syntactic evidence which shows that Edo personal names are words derived out of syntactic phrases is their behaviour with modifiers. Consider these examples below:

185.(a) *Ògúsóyèn mwén khérhé*
name small
"Ògúsóyèn is small"

Whereas, it is possible for modifiers to modify Edo personal names that are considered single morphological words, the same is not possible of the corresponding phrases or sentence. Also consider these:

186. (b) *àwà khérhé*
dog small

- (c) Ògúnámẹ̀n khérhé
 'name' 'small'
 "the comfort from Ogun is small"
- (d) *Ògún àmẹ̀n khérhé
 "the comfort from Ogun is small"
- (e) Òbáyágbòn né kágùnkángùn
 name is tall and thin
 "Òbáyágbòn is tall and thin"
- (f) *Òbá yáán àgbòn yé kágùnkángùn
 'king posses world at tall and thin
- (g) Òbásùwàrè gùnù
 name shut up
 "Òbásùwàrè kept quiet"
- (h) *Òbá zé ùwá rré gùnù
 king choose wealth acquire shut up

In example b, above, *khérhé* 'small' qualifies the underived word *àwá*. This is also the case with examples 186c, e and g where names as words are qualified with *khérhé*, modified with *kágùnkángùn* and qualified with *gùnù* respectively. However, it is impossible for the corresponding phrases in 186 (d), (f) and (h) to be treated in similar way.

The examples below also demonstrate the fact that it is possible for these names to be replace with pronouns when necessary.

187. (a) ò yé khérhé "it is small"
 (b) ò gùnù "keep quiet"

The above are the pronoun forms of the examples c and g respectively.

Furthermore, these names can be modified by another name in Edo. When this happens, the nominal modifier becomes genitive. Consider the examples below.

- 188.i (a) Ògúnámẹ̀n né òkpè
 name wine tapper
 "Ògúnámẹ̀n the tapper"

(b) Òmómósé né òhà

name bride

"Òmómósé the bride"

(c) Òtamere né n'ákpà

name fool

"Òtamere the fool"

(d) Àimièñemièn né èwòe

name follower

"Àimièñemièn the follower"

The following corresponding constructions to the above are all ill-formed.

188.ii. (a) *Ògún àmèn né òkpè

god of iron water the tapper

(b) *Omo mú òsé né òhá

child carry beauty the bride

(c) *Òtá má eré né àkpà

enemy good profit the fool

(d) A i miẹ ne e mien né èwòe

Nom. prefix. neg. see the pron. see the follower

Another syntactic evidence to show that names are words that cannot be broken down into pieces is that they are referentially opaque to any external elements. It is not possible to refer to any of its component parts in isolation. As with other nominalised words in the language, we assert here that it is practically impossible to refer to any part of a personal name in Edo, rather, reference can only be made to a whole component of a personal name. (cf. Yassim 1997: 96). Let us consider these examples:

189.(a) i hén ghé Òsàródiòn ghá gwán vbé á ghá nó ó

I know that Òsàródiòn will talk if he is consulted.

The pronoun 'he' *òrèn* in the above sentence is referring to the entire component *Òsàródiòn*. Both *Òsà* 'God' and *Ordion* 'elder' in the name under reference are opaque. The pronoun *oren* cannot therefore refer to either of the two nouns in the names. If it happens, however, the construction that will be generated will be ill-formed.

190. (b) *i hén ghé Òsà; Ordion ghá gwán vbé a gha nó òré.

I know ghé name; name will talk if he is to consult

"I know God; elder will talk if he is consulted".

The morphological evidence for the claim that Edo names are words is obvious when we consider that Edo, just like other natural languages, undergo morphological processes. In the language as we mentioned in chapter four above, some word formation processes like, compounding; reduplication; affixation; and so on are very productive in the language. The assumption is that these morphological processes can only derive a word level category. It is therefore possible for some word derivational prefixes to derive a single word from almost any verb phrase without regards to its internal structure. Most of these verb phrases used as stems for nouns (names) are obtainable only after the operation of syntactic transformations like deletion, adjunction, and replacement for relativization, etc., (Ekundayo, 1976; Adéniyi 1997).

We will conclude this section by saying that both morphophonological processes are optional in sentences and phrases while they are mandatory for their personal names counterparts.

5.8 Tone in Edo Personal Names

We observed in the course of analysing these personal names in Edo that there is the incidence of floating high tone across morpheme boundary when these names are formed, which is similar to what Adéniyi (2003) discussed in associative constructions. Both Omoruyi (1986) and Omozuwa (1992) are of the opinion that this floating high tone is the residue of the deleted segments of the possessive marker ɔ́yé . They further argued that in fast speech; the segments are deleted leaving only the floating high tone. Let us cite some examples from Omozuwa (1992:259).

191. a.	/ ɔwè	#	ɔ́yé	#	ɛ̀ɛ̀ki/	→	[ɔwé!ki]
	'leg'		PM		'Eki'		Eki's leg'
b.	/igà	#	ɔ́yé	#	ɛ̀ɔ̀kpà	→	[igó!kpà]
	'feather'		PM		'cock'		'cock's feather'
c.	/úkpù	#	ɔ́yé	#	ɛ̀èdó/	→	[úkpé!dó]
	'cup'		PM		'Edo'		'Edo's cup'

d. /ɔkà # ɔyé # ɛ̀ɛki/ → [ɔkɛ̀!ki]
 'corn' PM 'Eki' 'Eki's corn'

The tonal patterns of Omozuwa's example can be graphically stated thus:

192. a. LL + HH + LL → LH! L
 b. HL + HH + LH → HH! H
 c. HL + HH + LL → HH! L

He is of the opinion that only the relics of the high tones of /ɔyé/ are left behind after the deletion of the vowel and consonant segments. He contends that the two high tones are collapsed into one in fast speech, hence the floating high tone that we have. An alternative approach to the analysis of the occurrence of a floating high tone between two nouns in associative construction is to postulate that a floating high tone surfaces only between a head noun and its qualifier. This approach does away with the notion that the floating high tone is a remnant of /ɔyé/. Since we know from Autosegmental Theory that tonal and segmental tiers are autonomous, there is no need to provide segmental anchors for the 'floating tone as is theoretically imperative in the traditional linear framework' (Oyèbádé 1998). We are therefore of the view that the floating tone is not derivable from the high tones of the possessive marker /ɔyé/. Rather, it is a floating high tomorph that enables us explain the relationship the between tonal patterns of two nominals. Going by this argument, we will have the following underlying process.

193. i. LL + (H) + LL → LH! L
 ii. LL + (H) + LH → LH! H
 iii. LL + (H) + HH → LHH
 iv. LL + (H) + HL → LHF

The tonal patterns above represent examples 1 – 2 above. In conclusion, we postulate a grammatical floating high tone, which is referred to as a tomorph in Elugbe (1985).

Some of the examples of names in which these floating high tone occur in the language are:

194. a. èséè + òhé → Èsòhè
 favour gift 'Grace'
- b. àdà + ùwá → Àdúwá
 crossroad wealth 'the beginning of wealth'
- c. ìkpè + ágèlè → Ìkpágèlè
 seed bullet 'a child that is small at birth'

We also noticed that in the process of elision of vowels, it is usually the final vowel of the initial nominal in the naming process that is elided while the tone on it displaces the tone on the initial vowel of the second nominal in the naming process. These examples are numerous above.

5.9 Clipping in Edo Personal Names

Clipping, as a morphological phenomenon is very productive in Edo names. Many names in the language have been clipped to the extent that some native speakers of Edo cannot even relate the full version of the name with the clipped form.

According to Adéniyi (1997), clipping is a pseudo-lexical unit which results from the grapho-phonemic reduction of a word, which still shares the same semantic and paradigmatic relationship with the full form of the word. It can also be seen as extracting a shortened form of a word from its longer morphological form. In English, for instance, *telephone* become *phone*; *brassiere* is *bra*; etc. In some cases, the clipped form has more or less completely replaced the original longer word. Note that a clipped form is a complete lexical unit which should not be confused as abbreviation of its full form.

Crystal (1999) in his own case defined 'clipping as a type of word formation' in which new words are derived by shortening another word'. Some of the examples he gave include, *exam* from *examination* and *ad* from *advertisement*.

However, Aronoff (1997) defines clipping as a process that shortens a polysyllabic word by deleting one or more syllables. He observes that clipping is most common in personal names. He gave examples such as Liz, Ron, Rob, Sue and so on. In

all the definitions above, it is clear that both the clipped form and the word from which it originates share both semantic and syntactic features. However, the two words are distinct lexical units with separate morphological identities.

The use of the various types of clipped forms is restricted to everyday casual and informal discourse among family members, friends and acquaintances. However, the full-length of these names are usually reserved and employed for formal interactions and official records.

In the Edo language we identify three types of clippings. These are back-clipping, fore-clipping and what we referred to as free-clipping in this work.

In the case of back-clippings, an element or elements are taken from the end of a name. What we then have is an abridged version, which can still stand in its place. In English for instance, the following have undergone various back-clippings as can be seen from them. ad(vertisement), chimp(panzee), deli(catessen), hippo(potamus), lab(oratory) and many more. Clipping of names often undergo adaptations. In English, the following names have undergone adaptations to derive pet versions of the same names. Cathie Kate, Katie for Catherine, Willie, Billy or Bill for Williams etc.

In Edo, names such as *Òsàfómwán* "God is the source of one's wealth"; *Òsàìgbòvò* "God doesn't envy anyone"; *Òsàìgbè* "God doesn't kill" and many more are usually back-clipped to become *Òsà* which means 'God' in the language. Sometimes also, a clipped form acquires a curious suffix. They go to the extent of adding the English based possessive suffix *-s* to become *Òsàs*. This is however not peculiar to the Edo language alone. Òla-Orie (2002) also observed a similar situation when she said that the Yorùbá language add the Latin diminutive suffix */-ellus/* and its allomorphs (*-cellus*, *-ulus*, *-lus*) shortened to */-us/* and used as a diminutive suffix in Yorùbá. She also mentioned the use of English based diminutive suffix */-i/* and the English based diminutive suffix */-i/*. Some of the examples she gave include;

Yorùbá names	Latin -based diminutive
195.i. a. Nikèé	Nikùs
b. Gbénga	Gbéngùs

Yorubá names	English –based diminutive suffix /-i/
c. Nikèé	Niki
d. Sólá	Sòli
Yorubá names	English –based possessive suffix /-s/
e. Nikèé	Nikés
f. Gbénga	Gbéngus

We however note in this work that we are yet to come across both the Latin-based diminutive and the English based diminutive suffix in Edo language. What we have is the English-based diminutive and which is quite common in the language. We also note that in almost all cases where we have Ósá occurring as N₁ in the name, it is the N₂ that are usually clipped. Other examples of back-clipping are tabulated below;

Edo names	meaning	back-clipped forms/meaning
195.ii. a. Úwádíá	'my wealth has settled'	Úwá (wealth)
b. Ònàíwú	"this one will not die"	Ònà (this one)
c. Àgbónifò	"the world will not end"	Àgbòn (world)
d. Òkúnmárhíá	"the ocean did not spoil anything"	Òkún (ocean)
e. Ògbèíwí	"the family line will not be lost"	Ògbè (family)
f. Àbùlélé	"someone you try to meet"	Àbù (someone)

In **fore-clipping**, an element or elements are taken from the beginning of a word. We have some of these examples from English, (ham)burger, (omni)bus, (alli)gator, (tele)phone, (heli)copter and many more. This type of clipping also occurs with personal names in English. Some of these examples include; Becky for Rebecca, Drew for Andrew, Ginny for Virginia. In Edo, names such as the following are fore-clipped.

196	Edo names	meaning	fore-clipped forms/meaning.
a.	Ìzèyúwá	"I have chosen wealth"	Úwá (wealth)
b.	Àizòbò	"I refused to be a native doctor"	Òbò (native doctor)
c.	Àifíókùn	"You can't trick the sea"	Òkún (ocean)

d.	Ídémùdiá	"I stood firmly"	Mùdiá (firmly)
e.	Ízódúwá	"I have chosen the road to wealth"	Ódúwá (the road to wealth)

We also identify, in the language, what we referred to in this work as **free-clipping**. In this case, any of the two forms can be clipped by the speakers. Some of these examples include:

	Edo names	meaning	free clipped forms/meaning.
197 a.	Ógièíghò	"chieftaincy is not money"	Ógiè (title)/Íghò (money)
b.	Èdóghòghò	"day of joy"	Èdé (day)/Óghòghò (joy).
c.	Ósánógiè	"God is worth His title"	Ósá (God)/Ógiè (title)
d.	Èsòhè	"Grace"	Èsé (favour)/Óhè (gift).
e.	Àdèsúwá	"a child born in prosperity"	Àdèsé (centre)/ Úwá (wealth), Ade

Bussmann (1996) is of the view that in 'head words' it is the first part that is always left while the other part is clipped. While this view is only true to back-clipping, same cannot be said of other three types that we discussed above. It has been discovered that any part of the name can be clipped depending on other extra-linguistic factors. In determining the part of a name to be clipped, the socio-cultural factors such as the one that we discussed under the sociology of Edo personal names will come onto play. Also, another major factor that will automatically determine the portion to be clipped is the Positive Home Condition Principle that we discussed above. In this case, any part of the name that will eventually be clipped must be strictly motivated by positive and constructive home condition of both immediate and extended family.

It has also been noted that, more often than not, clipping in Edo tend to obliterate the full meaning of these names. This is because the clipped version of a word might have the same form with many other ones in the language. For instance, from the available data, there are over three hundred names where Ósá occurs as the N_i in the names. One would therefore not know which one of them is being borne when it has been clipped. In this case, there will be no cultural interrelatedness between the full name and the one that has been clipped. While this is permissible in European languages where meaning is not

attached to naming system of majority of their languages, and where names are mere identification tags given to individuals, African languages confer so much importance to naming as they see it as vehicles through which society advances and passes on cultural tenets and philosophies of life. They also see naming as something that has bearing on the destiny of the bearer. Another important point is that when some of these names are clipped, it might be difficult to know if the bearer of the clipped version is a male or female. More so, if he or she is not around when discussion is going on. This, to our mind, has negated and defeated the whole essence of naming in African languages.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION.

6.0. Summary.

We have attempted in this work to look at aspects of morphological processes in the Edo language. In this case, we examined various morphological processes such as nominalisation, reduplication, compounding, affixation, clipping, number formation and ideophone. We equally examined the structure of Edo names and the various roles that tones play in these constructions. Lastly, the work appraised the Yorùbá loanwords in Edo, and based on philological facts, we examined the relationships between Odùduwá and Òrànmiyàn within Ifè-Benin relations.

We employed different theories to capture the various facts of the morphology of the Edo language. First, we employed the theory of autosegmental phonology and morphology because it is capable of solving the various problems encountered in the language. Particularly, the theory was able to resolve the problem of tones, whereas earlier theories assumed that both segmental and suprasegmental features are not related. Autosegmental morphology was also able to solve the problem of reduplication in the language. Marantz's theory, derived from Goldsmith's autosegmental theory showed us that the former traditional transformation rules were unable to account for the various types of reduplications in a lot of African languages, and particularly the Edo language. Marantz then proposed that reduplication in general, is basically affixation but what is affixed is a CV skeleton (or prosodic template, i.e. syllable, foot, or even a phonological word) whose phonemic content is obtained by copying the complete phonemic melody of the root and linking it to the affixal CV template. Another theory that we employed is the weak lexicalist hypothesis. Our theory of head in Edo compound showed that Edo is an exception to Williams' Right-Hand Head Rule (RHR). This is because, it has been showed convincingly in this work that head in Edo, (just as also reported in Yorùbá by Ògúnkeye 2002) is shown to be subject to parametric variation, though predominantly left-head.

On nominalization in the Edo language, the various nominalization constructions were categorized on the basis of the different tones they bear. Thus we were able to make a dichotomy between LLL(L) tonal patterns and LHL(H) tonal patterns. In reduplication, we recognized the various tonal outputs too. Some of these are tone polarization, floating high tones, low and high tones spreading in various reduplication constructions such as verbs, adverbs and adjectives. Others are nominals and plurality, numeral and ideophonic constructions. Our discovery in reduplication in ideophones showed that tones in ideophones do not have any semantic connotations. This is contrary to what operates in Yorùbá when Awóyalé (1974) quoted by Ógúnkéyè (2002) observed that the functions of tones in words other than ideophones in Yorùbá are different from its function in ideophones. Whereas, in other words, in the Yorùbá language, tones are used to maintain lexical contrasts. In ideophones, they serve to maintain quasi-grammatical/attitudinal contrast as well. We also discovered that clipping in Edo names can be from any part of the names. This is against what Bussmann (1996) mentioned in his work, when he said that in 'head words' it is the first part that is always left while the other part is clipped. Our findings showed that the portion of the name to be clipped depends more often than not on other factors such as the positive home condition of both the immediate and extended families and even some other socio-cultural considerations. Our analysis of the structure of Edo personal names showed that it might even be a practicable and simpler way of analysing the structure of the language. However, these names exhibit some morpho-syntactic and lexico-semantic idiosyncracies, such as their behaviours with modifiers and qualifiers. The work also showed clearly that Edo names are abridged versions of syntactic structures which lexicalize peoples' folk-psychology and their language morphological structures as previously observed by earlier Yorùbá scholars.

Finally, the work shed more light on the relationship that existed between the Yorùbá and the Edo people. Based on available data on Yorùbá loanwords in Edo, we discovered that both Ifè and Benin have the same progenitor. However, other morphological processes such as affixation and number formations have not negated the established facts about these morphological processes both in Edo and in other related languages.

In our opinion, the above represent the major contributions of this thesis to both Edoic studies and African linguistic studies in general. The above points that we have highlighted, in our view, will go a long way at improving our understanding of the morphological structures and personal names in the language.

However, this type of study cannot claim, and will not claim to have resolved all controversies regarding the word structures and personal name constructions in the language. Because of time and space constraints, some other morphological processes such as coinage, blending, and others have not been given any attention in this work. It is our sincere hope that further researches will take a closer look at these processes. Also, only Edo personal names were discussed in this work. We also hope that other types of names and naming patterns such as place names, animal and plant names and others will be investigated.

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